

TJLG

TEERTHANKER JOURNAL OF LAW & GOVERNANCE

A Biannual Peer-Reviewed Refereed Journal

Published by :

*Teerthaker Mahaveer College of Law & Legal Studies, Faculty of Law,
Teerthaker Mahaveer University*

Address: Delhi Road, Moradabad-244001, (U.P.) India

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ISSN : 3107-7730 (Print)

TJLG

Teerthanker Journal of Law & Governance

Vol. : I, Issue No. : 01

July-December 2025

Subject : Law & Legal Studies

Language : Bilingual (English & Hindi)

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Price : ₹350 /-

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college of Law and Legal Studies, TMU,

Moradabad & Printed by Zenwaar

Imprints at Moradabad.

Cover Design & Concept by : Abhinav Chauhan

Teerthanker Journal of Law & Governance

A Biannual Peer-Reviewed Refereed Journal

Faculty of Law, Teerthanker Mahaveer University, Moradabad (U.P.)

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FROM THE CHANCELLOR'S DESK

Dear Readers

It gives me immense pleasure to extend my heartfelt congratulations to the Faculty of Law, Teerthanker Mahaveer University, on the remarkable launch of Teerthanker Journal of Law and Governance, an academic initiative of the Teerthanker Mahaveer College of Law and Legal Studies. This significant milestone reflects the University's continued commitment to fostering intellectual growth, promoting scholarly excellence, and contributing meaningfully to the field of legal education, governance and research.

The vision behind this journal, conceived by the Faculty of Law, deserves special commendation. Their dedication, foresight, and academic leadership have inspired the creation of a platform that will encourage critical thinking, informed discourse, and innovative research in law and governance. Such endeavors are vital in today's rapidly changing legal and socio-political landscape, where the rule of law and sound governance remain the cornerstones of a just and progressive society.

I am confident that Teerthanker Journal of Law and Governance will serve as a beacon of knowledge for scholars, practitioners, and students alike. It will not only enrich legal scholarship but also strengthen the university's mission to advance quality education rooted in ethics, justice, and societal well-being.

I congratulate the editorial board, contributors, and the entire team whose collective efforts have brought this vision to life. May this journal continue to inspire intellectual inquiry, uphold academic integrity, and contribute to shaping a future guided by wisdom, equity, and the spirit of Mahaveer's teachings of Right Perception (Samyak Darshan), Right Knowledge (Samyak Gyan) and Right Conduct (Samyak Charitra).

With best wishes for great success and a meaningful scholarly journey ahead.

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'Suresh Jain'.

Suresh Jain
Chancellor
Teerthanker Mahaveer University, Moradabad

FROM THE VICE CHANCELLOR's Desk

Dear Readers

It is with immense pride and academic enthusiasm that I present the inaugural issue of the Teerthanker Journal of Law & Governance a landmark initiative by the Faculty of Law, Teerthanker Mahaveer University, Moradabad.

In times of rapid social, economic, and legal transformation, the need for scholarly engagement with pressing issues such as governance, justice, constitutional values, human rights, and regulatory frameworks is more urgent than ever. This peer-reviewed, bi-annual journal has been conceptualized to meet that need offering a platform for rigorous research, critical analysis, and interdisciplinary dialogue.

The journal is not only a medium for publishing original and high-quality research but also a vehicle to encourage multidimensional perspectives on contemporary issues. I am confident that it will inspire scholars and practitioners alike to approach legal and governance challenges with deeper academic insight and innovation.

This initiative will also contribute to enhancing the university's academic standing and foster a culture of research-led policy debate and reform. I firmly believe the Teerthanker Journal of Law & Governance will evolve as a meaningful contributor to national and global discourse on law and governance.

I take this opportunity to express my heartfelt gratitude to the editorial board, advisory committee, and all contributing authors for their dedication, scholarly commitment, and shared vision. Their efforts truly reflect TMU's mission of academic integrity, diversity, and excellence.

May this journal become a beacon of scholarly inquiry and a driving force for transformative change.

Warm regards and best wishes,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'V K Jain', written in a cursive style.

Prof. (Dr.) V K Jain
Vice Chancellor
Teerthanker Mahaveer University, Moradabad

FROM THE **HEAD OF ACADEMICS**

Dear Readers

It fills me with immense pride and profound joy to extend my heartiest congratulations to the College of Law & Legal Studies on the launch of its publication, “Teerthanker Journal of Law and Governance.” This scholarly endeavour is not merely an academic milestone but a vibrant testimony to the College’s unwavering pursuit of truth, justice, and intellectual enrichment.

A journal, at its core, is the voice of an institution’s intellect and conscience, a confluence of ideas that dares to question, interpret, and illuminate. As Francis Bacon wisely wrote, “Some books are to be tasted, others to be swallowed, and some few to be chewed and digested.” May this journal belong to that rare category which nourishes the intellect and stirs the spirit, inviting scholars to think deeply, write fearlessly, and engage earnestly with the evolving paradigms of law and governance.

The release of “Teerthanker Journal of Law and Governance” embodies our shared vision of fostering a culture where learning transcends classrooms, where research becomes a dialogue with society, and where knowledge serves humanity with wisdom and grace. I envision this journal as a luminous forum where scholars, practitioners, and students come together to deliberate upon the moral, ethical, and legal foundations of our civilization, thereby strengthening the bridge between thought and action.

May this noble initiative grow into a beacon of scholarly excellence and integrity, guiding generations to uphold justice with compassion and intellect with humility. I wish this journal to soar to great heights of wisdom and repute, ever guided by truth, scholarly rigour, and the spirit of transformation.

My best wishes for its enduring success.

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'Manjula Jain', written in a cursive style.

Prof. Manjula Jain
Dean-Academics
Teerthanker Mahaveer University, Moradabad

FROM THE EDITOR-IN-CHIEF

Dear Readers

It gives me immense pleasure to present the inaugural edition (July–December 2025) of the Teerthanker Journal of Law & Governance. This first issue marks an important milestone for the Faculty of Law, Teerthanker Mahaveer University, as we create a dedicated platform for quality research, academic dialogue, and policy-oriented study in the domains of Law, Governance, and Public Administration.

The contemporary world is witnessing unprecedented changes in legal frameworks, governance structures, and administrative practices. Today, academic inquiry must go beyond theoretical understanding and engage with pressing societal challenges, technological disruptions, justice delivery reforms, and the evolving role of institutions. The journal aims to contribute to this process by encouraging scholarship that is analytical, socially relevant, and interdisciplinary in nature.

Each article published in this edition reflects rigorous intellectual effort and scholarly commitment. Together, they address key themes including legislative reform, public decision-making, institutional accountability, access to justice, and citizen-centric governance. We believe such contributions will inspire further research and stimulate meaningful academic and policy discussions.

I would like to express my sincere gratitude to all contributors, peer reviewers, and members of the editorial board for their support in bringing this publication to fruition. Their dedication to academic excellence has helped us set a strong foundation for future editions.

I invite academicians, legal practitioners, researchers, and students to read, engage, and contribute to upcoming issues. With this inaugural volume, we embark on a journey to build a credible, insightful, and impactful scholarly platform.

With Warm Regards,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to be 'H. Dixit'.

Prof. (Dr.) Harbansh Dixit
Dean, Faculty of Law
Teerthanker Mahaveer University, Moradabad

About the Journal

Teerthanker Journal of Law & Governance (TJLG) is a biannual, peer-reviewed, and refereed academic journal published by TMCLLS, Faculty of Law, Teerthanker Mahaveer University, Moradabad. The journal serves as a platform for scholarly discourse and critical analysis in the fields of law, governance, public policy, and allied disciplines. It aims to promote original and impactful research that contributes to the development of legal scholarship and informs contemporary legal and policy debates. The journal accepts original research articles, case notes, legislative and policy commentaries, and book reviews that address significant legal and governance-related issues at the national and international levels. By fostering intellectual dialogue and encouraging interdisciplinary approaches, TJLG aspires to be a valuable resource for legal education, practice, and policymaking.

Journal Particulars

1.	Title of the Journal	Teerthanker Journal of Law & Governance A Biannual Peer-Reviewed and Refereed Journal
2.	ISSN (Print)	3107-7730
3.	Format of Publication	Print (Offline)
4.	Frequency	Biannual
5.	Subject	Law & Legal Studies
6.	Language	Bilingual : English & Hindi
7.	Starting Year	2025
8.	Nature of Journal	National
9.	Publisher Details	Name: TMCLLS, Faculty of Law, Teerthanker Mahaveer University Address: Delhi Road, Moradabad, U.P., PIN-244001, India
10.	Aims and Scope	<p>The journal aims to provide a dynamic and interdisciplinary platform for scholars, academicians, legal practitioners, policymakers, and students to engage with and contribute to the evolving fields of law and governance.</p> <p>Aims : The journal is committed to encouraging original scholarship that advances knowledge, explores comparative perspectives, and offers practical insights into the working of legal and governance systems.</p> <p>Scope : The journal welcomes original research papers, case comments, book reviews, and thought-provoking essays in areas including: Constitutional Law and Governance</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Administrative and Regulatory Frameworks ▪ Criminal Justice and Human Rights ▪ Environmental and Sustainable Law ▪ Commercial and Corporate Laws ▪ International Law and Diplomacy ▪ Cyber Law and Technology Governance ▪ Alternative Dispute Resolution Mechanisms ▪ Legal Theory and Jurisprudence ▪ Socio-legal Studies and Legal Reforms ▪ Public Policy and Lawmaking Processes
11.	Review Policy	Double-blind peer review
12.	Plagiarism Policy	The Journal maintains a strict policy against plagiarism and upholds the highest standards of academic integrity. A manuscript will be considered for publication only if the similarity index is below 10%.
13.	Submission Guidelines	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ All manuscripts must be original, unpublished, and not under simultaneous consideration elsewhere. ▪ Submissions should be formatted in MS Word (.doc or .docx) using Times New Roman (For English) Mangal Unicode (For Hindi), 12-point font, 1.5 line spacing, and justified alignment. ▪ Manuscripts must include an abstract of 150–250 words and 4–6 keywords. ▪ Authors must adhere to a uniform citation style the ILI format. ▪ Submissions are accepted in English and Hindi only. ▪ Co-authorship is permissible up to a maximum of two authors. ▪ All submissions should be emailed to: dean.law@tmu.ac.in
14.	Contact Information	Contact Number : +91-9412389967, Email : dean.law@tmu.ac.in

Governance : A Triadic Framework for Collaborative Public Management

Dr. Rakesh Kumar¹

Abstract

Modern governance extends beyond the conventional bounds of the state, progressively shaped by the interlocked forces of state institutions, market systems, and civil society bodies. This article critically examines the triadic model of governance, consisting of the State, Market, and Civil Society, to explain how each pillar uniquely engages in policy development, execution, and public service provision. Based on available theoretical frameworks and empirical data from both Indian and international contexts, the study examines in detail the inherent interdependence, complementarity, and likely tensions between such varied actors. The paper critically assesses the inherent shortcomings of every sector when functioning independently and highlights the transformational possibilities of comprehensive governance models in achieving sustainable development, democratic accountability, and equitable growth. It ends with deliverable policy recommendations aimed at maximizing synergy between these three critical players to produce better governance results.

Keywords: Governance, State, Market, Civil Society, Public Policy, Collaborative Governance, Public Management, Tri-sectoral Cooperation

Introduction

Governance in the 21st century is characterized by rising complexity, ubiquitous pluralism, and deep interdependence. Conventional governance models, under which the state was imagined as the monopoly, omnipotent actor directly responsible for regulation, control, and provision of services, are clearly insufficient in tackling the multiple, fast-changing problems facing contemporary societies. As such, contemporary governance is increasingly reimagined as a dynamic and naturally iterative process, involving three cornerstones: the State, the Market, and Civil Society.

The triadic model of governance suggests that legitimate and effective governance originates from the constructive and interactive interaction of these three different but related entities. The state provides legitimacy, legislation, and means of critical public accountability. The market introduces innovation, efficiency, and important resource mobilization capabilities. At the same time, civil society promotes democratic involvement, voices equality, and develops social capital. This paper scrutinizes this complementary relationship, expressed as Governance = State + Market + Civil Society, to map its theoretical foundations, examine its reality, and delve into its policy relevance.

Theoretical Framework

Defining Governance

Governance, in its most general sense, is the complex processes, designated structures, and formal and informal institutions by which collective choices are made, power is exercised legitimately, and public matters are comprehensively administered. It is a notion precisely wider than government, involving a plurality of agents and various arenas, including a wide range of non-state actors (World Bank, 1997).

¹ Associate Professor, Faculty of Law, Teerthanker Mahaveer University, Moradabad, U.P.

Components of the Triadic Model

State: The State is a society of men in number, permanently settled in a definite region of territory, independent or almost so, of external influence and having an organized government to which the mass of population owes habitual obedience.

Market: An arrangement where two or more individuals have an exchange of goods, services, and information. In an ideal world, a market is where two or more entities are engaged in selling and purchasing. The two entities that are engaged in a deal are referred to as the buyer and seller. The seller receives money in return for selling goods and services to the buyer. There must be more than one seller and buyer for the market to remain competitive. This includes economic actors, including corporations, private businesses, and individual entrepreneurs, that are mainly occupied with the generation of goods and services, the creation of employment, and the general contribution towards economic growth and wealth creation.

Civil Society: A plural space that includes Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs), community associations, advocacy groups, social movements, philanthropic institutions, and alternative media. These institutions mostly act to voice citizens' interests, mobilize disparate interests, and check state and market institutions (Salamon, 2002).

Governance Typologies

It is only through an understanding of different conceptual typologies that the workings of modern governance can be comprehended.

Multilevel Governance (MLG): This approach recognizes that governance mechanisms occur along a range of administrative levels, from sub-national (regional and local) to national and international, frequently including complicated interactions between these levels.

Collaborative Governance: Refers to public decision-making processes marked by cooperative efforts and shared responsibility between governmental organizations, the private sector, and civil society, especially in the case of mutually shared public issues (Ansell & Gash, 2008).

Polycentric Governance: The theory refers to systems of governance where a number of centers of decision-making power exist independently but are linked and function collaboratively to solve compound collective action problems (Ostrom, 1990).

The Unique Functions of Every Sector in Governance

The State: Legitimacy and Regulative Power

The state retains a central position within the realm of governance by its distinctive legal power to implement legislation, equitably redistribute wealth, and promote social justice. Its central functions are:

- Maintenance of national security and enforcement of the rule of law.
- Supply and upkeep of vital infrastructure and basic public services.
- Enforcement of social welfare policies and mechanisms of wealth redistribution within society.
- Laying down and enforcement of environmental protection laws and sensitization.

Yet, the effectiveness of the state is often greatly hampered by systemic elements like over-bureaucracy, inherent inefficiencies, and possible political meddling, thus requiring collaborative interaction with other sectors.

The Market: Efficiency and Innovation

The market domain injects essential entrepreneurial energy, efficiency of resources, and technological innovation into the governance system mechanism. This is translated across numerous mechanisms, such as:

Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs): Cooperative arrangements between private sector entities and public institutions for provision of public services or infrastructure projects for work development.

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR): Self-initiated actions by companies to tackle social and environmental issues in their operations and stakeholder interactions for the benefit of society.

Social Enterprises and Impact Investing: Business models that integrate commercial approaches with a main purpose to accomplish social or environmental goals.

Whereas markets measurably improve the delivery of services and spur economic growth, their unfettered operation can create large inequities, exploitation, and adverse externalities, hence the need for stringent regulatory intervention.

Civil Society: Participation and Accountability

Civil society acts as a watchdog conscience and an essential bridge for citizens' participation in the governance system. Its vital roles include:

- Organizing and empowering communities, especially marginalized and vulnerable ones.
- Promoting and reinforcing different modes of participatory democracy.

- Serving as an autonomous watchdog, holding accountable both public and private sector actors through monitoring their performance.
- Filling gaps in public service provision, particularly in key areas like health, education, and humanitarian emergency response.

All the same, civil society organizations typically face inherent vulnerabilities such as limited access to resources, the possibility of state repression or overly burdensome regulatory frameworks, and co-optation by donor interests.

Interdependence and Cooperation Among Actors

Good governance is essentially improved when the state, market, and civil society act in a complementary manner and in harmony with each other instead of being competitive. Examples of good collaborative models are:

Social Accountability Programs: Processes by which citizens engage in monitoring and assessing public services, sometimes with the use of tools like community scorecards and public expenditure tracking.

Co-governance Frameworks: Local governance approaches that involve deep citizen engagement, such as in the case of Kerala's People's Plan Campaign in India, which decentralizes the plan to local institutions.

Public-Private Partnerships in Infrastructure Development: Infrastructure projects at large scale, such as India's National Highways Development Project or mass transit systems of cities, that involve private sector funds and capabilities with public regulation.

Comparative Strengths of the Triadic Actors

Function	State	Market	Civil Society
Legitimacy	Legal authority, sovereign power	Economic incentives, innovation capacity	Moral and social capital, trust
Efficiency	Bureaucratic, typically deliberative	High innovation, agility, cost-efficiency	Resource-constrained, typically nimble
Equity	Mechanisms for redistribution	Profit-driven, potential for disparity	Advocates for marginalized, inclusion
Accountability	Electoral, judicial, legislative	Regulatory oversight, consumer pressure	Citizen engagement, activism, advocacy

Global and Indian Experiences in Triadic Governance

Global Case Study: United Kingdom's "Big Society" Initiative (2010)

The "Big Society" policy, introduced in the United Kingdom, aimed to drastically minimize state interference and enable civil society bodies and private actors to take more responsibility for public service provision. Although theoretically pioneering, in practice its execution was widely criticized, most prominently with respect to its alleged function of legitimizing austerity policies and cuts in fundamental

public expenditure. This example illustrates the challenges and risks involved with the rebalancing of governance duties.

Indian Context: A Tri-Sectoral Collaboration Landscape

India's complex governance ecosystem offers rich empirical experience of wide-ranging tri-sector collaboration:

Swachh Bharat Mission: This nationwide sanitation movement is a quintessential example of a collaborative effort with direct government action, large Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) support from the private sector, and wide-ranging citizen participation and social movements for behaviour change.

Aadhaar and Direct Benefit Transfer (DBT) Scheme:

These programs are advanced technological collaborations with private stakeholders (e.g., IT companies), implemented on strong public platforms, which facilitate effective and transparent provision of welfare benefits.

National Rural Health Mission (NRHM): Although mainly state-supported, the NRHM is significantly supplemented by the very important participation of Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) and community health workers (e.g., ASHAs), who take healthcare services to inaccessible places and increase community involvement (Government of India, 2005).

Challenges in Tripartite Governance

Although the benefits are recognized, the implementation of tripartite governance models is full of a few inherent challenges:

Fragmentation and Coordination Failures: One of the key challenges is the possibility of goals being out of sync, varied operating methodologies, and lack of coordination between the three sectors, resulting in inefficiencies and inconsistencies in overall effectiveness.

Accountability Gaps: The dispersal of responsibilities among various actors could unknowingly create accountability gaps that make it challenging to identify clear ownership and responsibility for deliverables.

Power Imbalances: Natural power asymmetries can result in circumstances where powerful market forces can unduly impact or co-opt state machinery, or where the state and market together sideline civil society voices.

Civil Society Constraints: Civil society organizations themselves usually have considerable constraints, such as tenuous funding dependencies, repressive governmental regulations, and difficulty scaling their effective endeavors into wider geographies.

Recommendations for Strengthening Triadic Governance

In order to maximize the effectiveness and fairness of the triadic governance model, the following policy suggestions are essential:

Institutionalize Collaborative Platforms: Formal, inclusive, and multi-stakeholder processes for ongoing dialogue, shared planning, and collaborative problem-solving among government, private sector, and civil society representatives at all administrative levels.

Make Capacity Building Investments: Make strategic investments in building the organizational, technical, and human resource capacities of local NGOs and community-based organizations, enabling them to engage more meaningfully.

Provide Transparent Regulation for PPPs: Establish strong and transparent regulatory structures for Public-Private Partnerships, with clear social, environmental, and ethical safeguards in place to avoid exploitation and ensure public interest prevails.

Support Participatory Policymaking: Regularly embed deliberative democracy instruments, including citizen assemblies, participatory budgeting, and online consultation platforms, into policymaking processes to guarantee sincere citizen participation.

Foster Balanced Legal Frameworks: Pass and implement legal systems that not only protect the autonomous functioning space of civil society but also make it accountable through proportionate transparency rules, without restricting reasonable advocacy.

Conclusion

The interaction between the State, the market, and civil society is a rich and intricate one, with interdependence and cross-influence. Each plays a specific but complementary function in governance and contributes to the well-being and development of society. By recognizing and negotiating the challenges and opportunities of this trilateral relationship, we can strive for more effective and inclusive governance.

The abstraction of Governance = State + Market + Civil Society goes far beyond the simple mathematical formula; it is a deeper conceptual underpinning for understanding the complex processes by which public value is collectively co-produced in modern democracies. It becomes more and more clear that any single actor lacks the monolithic ability to unilaterally orchestrate the profound complexity of modern governance issues. Accordingly, efficient governance is clearly an emergent property of synergistic interaction, deep cooperation, and respectful interdependence between the state's legitimate power, the market's dynamic efficiency, and civil society's necessary moral guidance and activism. Through diligent cultivation and improvement of this triadic cooperation, societies can hope not only to produce better public service provision but also to develop genuinely inclusive, environmentally friendly, and well-anchored democratic development.

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Dowry Laws in India : A Legal Discourse in Present Scenario

Shuchita Gulyani¹
Dr. Sushim Shukla²

Abstract

Dowry continues to be a serious social issue in India, even though it is banned by law. Many women still face harassment, abuse, and even death due to dowry demands. This paper discusses the legal measures in place to stop dowry and how they are working in the current scenario. The main law is the Dowry Prohibition Act, 1961, which makes it illegal to give or take dowry. In addition to this, the Bharatiya Nyaya Sanhita (BNSS), 2023 includes important provisions like, Section 85 of BNSS deals with cruelty by the husband or his relatives, and Section 104 addresses dowry deaths. These laws are meant to protect women and punish those who misuse the dowry system. However, there have been concerns about the misuse of these laws, which can lead to false cases. This paper explores both the positive and negative impacts of dowry laws, along with suggestions for improvement. It also highlights the role of courts and the need for stronger implementation and public awareness to end dowry-related violence and ensure justice for women.

Keywords: Dowry, Women's Rights, Dowry Prohibition Act, BNSS, Legal Protection

Research Question

How effective are the dowry laws in India, particularly the Dowry Prohibition Act, 1961 and the provisions under BNSS, 2023, in addressing and preventing dowry-related crimes, and what are the legal and societal challenges in their implementation?

Hypothesis

While India has enacted comprehensive legal frameworks to curb the menace of dowry, including the Dowry Prohibition Act and relevant provisions in the BNSS, 2023, the effectiveness of these laws is hindered by implementation gaps, societal attitudes, and instances of legal misuse.

Introduction

The dowry system in India, deeply rooted in traditional practices, has evolved into a major socio-legal issue. Once a benign cultural practice, dowry has morphed into a coercive demand, often leading to harassment, cruelty, and even deaths of women. In response, India introduced the Dowry Prohibition Act, 1961, followed by penal provisions such as Section 498A and Section 304B of the Indian Penal Code. With the recent recodification under the Bharatiya Nyaya Sanhita (BNSS), 2023, these sections are now included under Sections 85 and 104, respectively. This paper analyses the legal framework addressing dowry, its practical implementation, judicial responses, misuse concerns, and offers reformative suggestions.

Literature Review

Several scholars have examined the multidimensional facets of dowry and the effectiveness of anti-dowry laws:

1. Flavia Agnes emphasized the patriarchal underpinnings of dowry violence and called for comprehensive legal reform combined with societal change.
2. Jaya Sagade critiqued the implementation mechanisms of the Dowry Prohibition Act, asserting that legal measures alone are insufficient.

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3. The 243rd Law Commission Report highlighted the misuse of Section 498A IPC, suggesting a need for procedural safeguards while protecting genuine victims.

4. Rajesh Tandon analyzed court judgements, noting inconsistent interpretations and enforcement, leading to both under-conviction and overreach.

5. Dr. Madhu Mehra, writing in the Indian Journal of Gender Studies, critiques the gender neutrality debate in criminal law and advocates for victim-centric reforms in dowry-related offences.

6. Anuja Agarwal, in her article "Dowry-Related Harassment and Legal Remedies" (2021), argues that implementation gaps arise due to lack of local accountability, under-trained enforcement agencies, and reluctance from judiciary to convict in dowry death cases without overt physical evidence.

7. Prof. B.B. Pande highlights how the framing of Section 304B has caused confusion over evidentiary standards, making convictions in dowry death cases highly dependent on circumstantial factors.

8. International Commission of Jurists published a report in 2020 emphasizing how dowry laws in South Asia, including India, fail to offer victim restitution and instead focus primarily on punitive measures.

9. UN Women's South Asia Regional Office observed that public awareness campaigns are far more successful in altering dowry practices than legislative changes alone, citing examples from Nepal and Bangladesh.

10. Ritu Menon and Kalpana Kannabiran discuss the interlinking of caste, class, and patriarchy in perpetuating dowry, and how laws are often enforced selectively depending on social status.

The introduction of BNSS, 2023 is a recent development and academic literature on its impact is currently limited. However, it reflects an intent to streamline and clarify criminal law, including dowry-related offenses.

Legal Framework Against Dowry

1. The Dowry Prohibition Act, 1961

This Act criminalizes both giving and receiving of dowry and prescribes penalties including imprisonment up to 5 years and a fine of ₹15,000 or the value of the dowry, whichever is more. However, enforcement has been inconsistent, with many cases going unreported due to social stigma and fear.

2. Provisions under the Indian Penal Code (Pre-BNSS)

- Section 498A IPC: Addresses cruelty by husband or relatives of the husband.
- Section 304B IPC: Deals with dowry deaths occurring within 7 years of marriage.

3. Provisions under the Bharatiya Nyaya Sanhita (BNSS), 2023

- Section 85 BNSS: Mirrors Section 498A IPC. It criminalizes cruelty towards a woman by her husband or relatives.
- Section 104 BNSS: Substitutes Section 304B IPC, defining and punishing dowry deaths.

These provisions are designed to provide continuity with existing law while aiming to make the legal text more accessible and logically structured.

Judicial Interpretation and Role of Courts

Indian courts have played a vital role in shaping the legal discourse on dowry:

1. In *Rajesh Sharma v. State of UP* (2017), the Supreme Court mandated preliminary inquiry before arrest in 498A cases, citing misuse.
2. In *Social Action Forum for Manav Adhikar v. Union of India* (2018), the Supreme Court modified the earlier position and emphasized a balanced approach to prevent both harassment of accused and injustice to women.
3. In *Manoj Kumar v. State of Madhya Pradesh* (2022), the High Court reaffirmed that continuous demand for dowry and associated cruelty is enough to invoke 498A.
4. In *Reena v. State of Punjab* (2023), the court stressed the evidentiary value of timely reporting in dowry death cases.
5. In *Pawan v. State (NCT of Delhi)* (2021), the proximity between dowry demand and death was emphasized for conviction under 304B.
6. In *Satbir Singh v. State of Haryana* (2021), the Court reiterated the importance of presumption under Section 113B of the Evidence Act when dowry death is established.
7. In *State of Rajasthan v. Arjun Singh* (2021), the apex court emphasized that conviction under Section 304B should not be mechanical and must rely on cogent evidence.

Judicial pronouncements reflect a cautious balancing act-protecting women while ensuring safeguards against misuse.

Misuse and Counter arguments

One of the major criticisms of dowry laws, especially Section 498A (and now Section 85 BNSS), is their

alleged misuse:

- Some cases have involved false accusations driven by personal vendettas .
- Courts have recorded increasing instances where complaints under anti-dowry laws were later found baseless.

However, it is vital to note that:

Misuse by a few should not delegitimize genuine grievances. According to the NCRB, dowry-related deaths continue to be alarmingly high, with over 6,500 cases reported annually.

Implementation Challenges

Despite stringent laws, dowry persists due to:

- Lack of awareness: Many victims are unaware of their rights or fear social ostracism.
- Police apathy: Reluctance to register cases, lack of gender-sensitized training.
- Delayed justice: Long pendency of dowry-related cases reduces faith in legal remedy.
- Patriarchal mindset: Societal norms continue to endorse dowry as a status symbol.

Comparative Perspective

Dowry is not exclusive to India—it is a socio-legal issue in various South Asian, African, and Western countries. While the cultural contexts may differ, comparative legal analysis helps to assess the effectiveness of different models of regulation and enforcement.

Nepal- Nepal outlawed dowry under the Social Practices Reform Act, 1976 and reinforced protections with the Domestic Violence (Offense and Punishment) Act, 2009. The government emphasizes grassroots engagement, public awareness campaigns, and swift justice through community courts.

Sri Lanka- Sri Lanka lacks specific dowry legislation but prosecutes related abuse through general laws covering assault, harassment, and domestic violence. It takes a gender-neutral and human rights-centric approach.

United Kingdom- The UK addresses dowry-like exploitation through laws on coercive control under the Serious Crime Act, 2015 and Forced Marriage (Civil Protection) Act, 2007. Economic and emotional abuse within intimate relationships, even if non-violent, is recognized as criminal behavior.

Australia- Victoria, Australia, became the first Western jurisdiction to specifically legislate against dowry abuse, recognizing it as a form of family violence in the Family Violence Protection Act, 2008 (amended in 2019). This approach empowers victims in immigrant communities, particularly from South

Asia.

Canada- Canada addresses dowry-related exploitation under domestic violence statutes. The Criminal Code penalizes coercion and abuse, and courts in provinces like Ontario employ cultural sensitivity protocols when addressing dowry issues among immigrant families.

Africa (Kenya & Nigeria)- In Kenya, the Marriage Act, 2014 permits customary bride price traditions but mandates consent and prohibits coercion. Nigeria follows similar norms under state-level family law, focusing on voluntariness and prevention of exploitation.

What we can consider-

Integrated Legal Frameworks: Nepal demonstrates the benefit of combining dowry regulation with broader gender justice laws.

Recognition of Coercive Abuse: The UK's and Australia's recognition of coercive control and dowry abuse in domestic contexts suggests India could broaden its definitions.

Community Engagement: Nepal's community courts and Bangladesh's public awareness strategies offer grassroots models for change.

Cultural Sensitivity in Enforcement: Canada and Kenya provide examples of how legal systems can respect cultural traditions while preventing exploitation.

Role of Civil Society and Awareness Campaigns

Legal provisions alone cannot eliminate dowry practices. Civil society must play a critical role:

- NGOs like Jagori, SEWA, and Breakthrough work on sensitization.
- Helplines and legal aid cells should be strengthened.
- Educational institutions must incorporate gender sensitization in curriculum.

Recommendations

Strengthen Implementation Mechanisms- Mandatory gender-sensitization training for police and judiciary, Set up exclusive women's cells in police departments.

Legal Reforms- Define "cruelty" and "dowry death" with greater clarity, Ensure faster trials with dedicated benches for gender-based violence.

Prevent Misuse- Establish pre-litigation mediation in non-violent cases, Mandatory counseling before FIR registration in borderline disputes.

Enhance Public Awareness- Nationwide campaigns involving media and influencers, Promote dowry-free

marriages through state incentives.

Victim Support Infrastructure- Establish crisis centers with legal, psychological, and shelter services, Ensure employment schemes for dowry victims.

Conclusion

Despite decades of legislative action, dowry remains a deeply entrenched social evil in India. The persistence of dowry-related violence, harassment, and deaths points to the limitations of a purely legalistic approach. While the Dowry Prohibition Act, 1961 and the newly codified provisions under the Bharatiya Nyaya Sanhita, 2023 (Sections 85 and 104) provide a comprehensive legal framework, their impact is often diluted by challenges in enforcement, societal attitudes, and institutional inertia. Judicial interpretations have evolved to balance protection for women with safeguards against misuse, yet inconsistencies in application continue to hinder the credibility and effectiveness of the system.

The comparative analysis of legal systems in countries like Nepal, Bangladesh, the UK, and Australia reveals that India can benefit from

integrating legal reforms with broader societal strategies. These include awareness campaigns, community-based redress mechanisms, victim compensation, and recognition of economic and psychological abuse. A holistic strategy is essential—one that involves not only strict legal penalties but also preventive and rehabilitative measures.

Moreover, addressing the implementation challenges—such as police apathy, judicial delay, lack of victim support infrastructure, and social stigma—is crucial for bridging the gap between law and justice. Legal reform must be accompanied by structural changes in administration, public awareness, and gender sensitization at all levels.

Ultimately, dowry is not just a legal problem—it is a reflection of entrenched patriarchy, gender inequality, and societal complicity. Therefore, the fight against dowry must be multi-dimensional, involving coordinated efforts from lawmakers, courts, enforcement agencies, educators, civil society organizations, and communities themselves. Only then can India hope to transform its progressive legal framework into a tool of true gender justice and social change.

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Digital Dowry : Emerging Forms of Economic Coercion in the Age of Technology and Social Media

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Abstract

In the modern digital age, the traditional practice of dowry in India has evolved into newer, less visible forms of economic coercion. While the Dowry Prohibition Act, 1961, aims to curb dowry-related abuse, it fails to address the rising trend of “Digital Dowry”—wherein demands are made for gadgets, cryptocurrency, social media-worthy weddings, and online income. This paper explores the concept of digital dowry in simple terms, highlighting how social media, influencer culture, and digital payment platforms have normalized these demands. It compares traditional and digital dowry, discusses various forms of digital coercion, and outlines the gaps in existing legal frameworks. The paper also presents case studies, legal reforms, policy recommendations, and the social impact of this silent but damaging practice. It concludes that as India embraces technological advancement, there is a pressing need to update laws and spread awareness to ensure ethical and gender-just digital growth.

Keywords : Digital Dowry, Economic Coercion, Cyber Abuse, Marriage Law, Social Media, Gender Justice, Technology Misuse, Domestic Violence, Legal Reforms, India

Introduction

The institution of marriage is one of the most important social structures in Indian society, but it has long been tainted by the practice of dowry. Traditionally, dowry involved the transfer of cash, property, and valuable items from the bride’s family to the groom’s family. Despite legal prohibitions, dowry-related demands and harassment continue to exist, evolving into less visible but equally harmful forms. One such modern variant is 'Digital Dowry,' which uses technology and social media to make demands that may seem acceptable but are rooted in economic coercion. This paper aims to understand how this practice has emerged and the consequences it has on individuals, families, and society at large.

What is Digital Dowry?

Digital dowry can be defined as the demand for digital or high-tech assets either before, during, or after marriage. Examples include the request for an iPhone, a gaming setup, high-end laptops, cryptocurrency, or even a demand to fund a wedding that looks glamorous on social media. In some cases, grooms expect the bride to contribute financially from her YouTube or Instagram income. These digital demands are often justified under the guise of 'gifting' or 'contribution,' making them hard to detect and report legally. The underlying issue, however, remains the same—economic pressure and gender-based inequality.

Historical Context: Dowry in India

Dowry as a concept is not new. It originally served as a means for the bride’s family to ensure financial security for their daughter. However, during British colonial rule, the custom transformed into a transactional system where dowry became a mandatory obligation rather than a voluntary gift. Over time, this led to severe abuse, harassment, and even deaths related to dowry disputes. Even though the Dowry Prohibition Act was passed in 1961, the problem persists

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in modern India. Now, with the advent of technology, the dowry system has taken on new digital forms, making it harder to detect and regulate.

How Technology Is Normalizing Digital Dowry

Technology has had a dual impact on society—it has improved communication and access to information, but it has also been misused. Social media platforms like Instagram and YouTube promote influencer culture, where extravagant weddings, luxury items, and idealized relationships are glamorized. Young people feel pressured to match these online standards. In this environment, digital dowry becomes normalized. Digital gift registries, cryptocurrency transfers, and social media image-building have made these demands seem less like dowry and more like 'modern expectations.' This normalization makes digital dowry a silent but serious problem.

Forms of Digital Economic Coercion

Digital dowry shows up in several forms across different phases of a marriage. Before marriage, families may demand social media visibility, expensive gadgets, or evidence of digital income. During marriage, expectations may include funding a wedding with live streaming or drone videography, giving high-end gadgets, or transferring large sums via UPI or other digital wallets. After marriage, the bride might face digital surveillance, with her online accounts and spending habits being monitored. Some women are even forced to hand over control of their social media pages or income streams. Failure to meet these expectations can result in cyberbullying or mental harassment.

Digital Dowry vs. Traditional Dowry

Traditional dowry involved visible and tangible goods like jewelry, land, and household items. These were easier to track, report, and legally address. Digital dowry, on the other hand, often occurs through untraceable channels like cryptocurrency or hidden under the guise of modern gifting. This makes it harder to classify as dowry in legal terms. Moreover, while traditional dowry is publicly frowned upon, digital dowry often escapes criticism because it aligns with modern consumer culture. This deceptive acceptance makes it all the more dangerous and deeply embedded.

Case Studies & Media Reports

Several cases reported in Indian media underline the seriousness of this issue. In one incident, a groom refused to marry a girl because she used a low-end

smartphone. In another, a bride's family was asked to provide Bitcoin as part of the wedding arrangement. NCRB (National Crime Records Bureau) data shows a significant rise in tech-enabled dowry harassment, though the numbers are believed to be underreported. The digital nature of these transactions makes them hard to prove in court, and victims often hesitate to report due to fear of social stigma.

Existing Laws and Their Gaps

Several laws exist to combat dowry and domestic violence, but they are not updated to handle digital issues. The Dowry Prohibition Act, 1961, does not mention electronic or digital assets. IPC Section 498A addresses cruelty to married women but does not include digital coercion. The IT Act, 2000, mainly handles data breaches and cybercrime, not domestic abuse. Even the new Bharatiya Nyaya Sanhita (BNS), under Section 84, talks about cruelty but fails to define it in the digital context. There is an urgent need to amend these laws to make them relevant in today's tech-savvy world.

Social and Psychological Impact

The psychological toll of digital dowry on women is massive. They often suffer in silence, trying to meet unrealistic standards. This leads to anxiety, depression, and feelings of inadequacy. In many cases, women are forced to abandon their careers or hand over control of their online earnings. The practice also widens the gap between rich and poor, as lower-income families struggle to match the digital expectations of wealthier ones. In the long run, it harms the national agenda of Digital India by turning technology into a tool of oppression instead of empowerment.

Vision for Legal Reform

To tackle digital dowry effectively, existing laws must be updated. The Dowry Prohibition Act should include digital and e-assets under its purview. IPC Section 498A and the IT Act need amendments to cover tech-based domestic abuse. Pre-marital counseling sessions should include digital literacy and cyber rights education. Law enforcement officials should be trained to handle digital coercion cases. These steps are essential to bring India's legal system in line with the realities of modern marriages.

Policy and Awareness Recommendations

Policy changes must be accompanied by awareness campaigns. Schools and colleges should include education on digital rights and gender equality.

Government campaigns can raise awareness through TV, radio, and social media. Anonymous platforms should be created to report digital dowry. Police, lawyers, and judges must be trained in identifying and acting on such cases. Use of AI to detect patterns of digital financial abuse could be explored. Only a combined legal and social approach can tackle this growing issue.

Judicial Trends & Judgments

Although digital dowry is still a grey area in Indian law, courts have begun to address its implications. In the case of *Satya Narayan Tiwari v. State of U.P.*, the court discussed indirect dowry demands and their harmful consequences. Public Interest Litigations (PILs) are being filed seeking recognition of digital

dowry as a form of domestic violence. While progress is slow, judicial awareness is increasing, offering hope for more concrete action in the future.

Conclusion

Digital dowry is a modern form of an age-old evil. As India becomes more advanced and connected, its social customs must evolve as well. The use of technology should be ethical and equitable. Digital dowry reflects the misuse of tech to continue patriarchal practices. Strong laws, social awareness, and digital education are essential to stop this silent coercion. Only then can India truly achieve its vision of *Viksit Bharat by 2047*—technologically strong, but also socially just and inclusive.

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Empowering Divorced Women and Their Children : The Impact of Government Policies and Schemes on Women's Entrepreneurship

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Abstract

Divorced women in India face numerous challenges, including financial instability, societal stigma, and limited opportunities for economic independence. These challenges are exacerbated by unreliable alimony and child support, often leaving women and their children in vulnerable positions. Government schemes such as Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana and Stand-Up India aim to address these issues by promoting women's entrepreneurship. This study examines the intersection of socio-legal frameworks and entrepreneurship schemes to understand their impact on the financial independence of divorced women and their ability to secure a stable future for their children. Adopting a mixed-method approach, the study analyzes quantitative data from government reports, including the Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana Annual Reports and NSSO data on women's economic participation, to assess the utilization of these schemes. Additionally, the paper reviews legal frameworks, such as the Hindu Marriage Act, the Domestic Violence Act, and Section 125 of the Crpc, to evaluate their role in supporting women post-divorce.

Keywords: Divorced Women, Entrepreneurship, Government Schemes, Financial Independence.

Introduction

Divorce, though increasingly acknowledged in Indian society, remains a deeply stigmatized experience for women. Post-divorce life is fraught with social alienation, financial instability, and legal ambiguities. Divorced women, especially those with children, often struggle to maintain a dignified life, as societal support systems diminish and family structures fragment. The absence of consistent financial support—either due to evasion of alimony obligations or slow judicial enforcement—further exacerbates their challenges.

In such a context, entrepreneurship becomes not just an economic activity but a form of empowerment and self-determination. The Indian government, through policies like Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana and Stand-Up India, seeks to promote entrepreneurship among women. However, divorced women occupy a unique intersection of vulnerability that these schemes rarely address in practice.

This paper critically examines the socio-legal environment affecting divorced women and explores how entrepreneurship initiatives can be better aligned to empower them and ensure better futures for their children.

Socio-Legal Challenges Faced by Divorced Women in India

1. Stigma and Marginalization

Society often blames women for marital breakdowns. Divorced women may face discrimination in housing, employment, and social circles. Such ostracization can lead to emotional distress and a lack of confidence, which hinders their ability to engage in entrepreneurial activities. Indian society, though constitutionally secular and democratic, remains patriarchal. Divorce is often

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viewed through a moral lens, casting divorced women as social deviants. This stigma leads to ostracism, affecting their social networks and, subsequently, their access to resources and opportunities.

2. Custody and Financial Strain

Divorced women often experience a sudden fall in their economic status. Many lack employable skills or face resistance from employers due to their marital status. When children are involved, the financial burden multiplies, as they become sole caregivers without adequate support from former spouses or families. While courts often grant custody of children to the mother, child support and alimony enforcement remain weak. CrPC which mandates maintenance, is limited both in terms of quantum and enforceability. As a result, divorced women are often primary caregivers without consistent financial support.

3. Limited Economic Opportunities

Despite educational qualifications, many women find it hard to re-enter the workforce post-divorce due to gaps in employment, ageism, or the need for flexible work hours. Entrepreneurship provides a flexible alternative, but capital access, financial literacy, and business networks are often out of reach.

Legal Frameworks Supporting Divorced Women

1 HMA, 1955

This statute provides for permanent alimony and maintenance. However, judicial discretion results in inconsistent awards, and enforcement remains a challenge, especially in rural areas where legal literacy is low.

2 PWDVA, 2005

This Act is instrumental in securing the rights of divorced and separated women to reside in the matrimonial home and claim maintenance. It broadens the scope of support from mere physical abuse to emotional and economic abuse, which is significant for entrepreneurship.

3 Sec. 125 of CrPC

Though secular in application, the section is conservative in scope. The term “sufficient means” remains ambiguously interpreted, and often the burden falls on the woman to prove financial need and neglect by the husband. These

laws, while progressive in intent, are often inaccessible to the very women they are meant to protect due to socio-cultural, economic and institutional barriers.

Government Schemes Promoting Women’s Entrepreneurship

1. Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana (PMMY)

Launched in 2015, this scheme provides loans up to 10 lakhs rupees without collateral. Women entrepreneurs are given preference, and interest subsidies are offered. The scheme categorizes loans into Shishu (up to 50,000), Kishore (50,000 to 5 lakhs), and Tarun (5 to 10 lakhs), enabling step-by-step growth. This scheme offers collateral-free micro-credit for small-scale business ventures. It aims to support underprivileged entrepreneurs, with a special focus on women. While it presents a promising avenue, the practical barriers often deter divorced women from applying.

Though not exclusive to divorced women, the scheme aligns with constitutional value which allows special provisions for women. Case examples like self-help groups of divorced women in Tamil Nadu starting tailoring units exemplify its transformative potential.

2. Stand-Up India Scheme

This scheme targets women and SC/ST entrepreneurs for loans between 10 lakhs to 1 crore. Each bank branch is required to support at least one woman entrepreneur. It mandates handholding support, which is crucial for first-time businesswomen.

Targeting women and SC/ST communities, this scheme encourages bank financing for new businesses. Though conceptually inclusive, divorced women face challenges in availing its benefits due to lack of documentation, low credit history, and absence of social guarantors. The scheme complements DPSP Directive Principles of State Policy by promoting equal opportunity in economic participation.

3. Mahila E-Haat and Udyam Sakhi Portal

Initiatives like Mahila E-Haat provide platforms for women to market their products. However, success on such platforms often requires digital literacy, entrepreneurial training, and product visibility—resources that many divorced women do not possess without targeted support.

These digital platforms allow women to showcase and sell products. While not directly financial schemes, they provide a vital market link, allowing divorced women to build independent economic identities.

Barriers to Accessing These Schemes

1. Bureaucratic Complexities

Lengthy documentation, lack of clear guidelines, and institutional apathy deter applicants. Many divorced women lack the formal documents (e.g., income proof, residence proof, separation decree) required to avail loans. Due to lacking in permanent addresses, bank accounts, or property in their names, made them ineligible for schemes that demand collateral, guarantors, or stable residence proof.

2. Lack of Awareness

Despite efforts by NGOs and state agencies, awareness about these schemes remains low, especially in non-urban settings. Divorced women are often excluded from mainstream communication channels.

3. Cultural Constraints

Family pressure, social stigma, and the notion of female dependency hinder divorced women from stepping into business roles. A woman starting a business may face resistance from her parental family, especially if custody responsibilities are involved. Even the bank officials consciously or unconsciously discriminate against single women or hesitate to approve loans due to perceived risk. The institutional attitude can be patronizing or dismissive.

Intersection of Legal Rights and Entrepreneurship

Thus, the intersection of law and policy does not merely serve as a support mechanism—it becomes an active driver of transformation. Legal protections ensure justice and enforcement, while policy interventions provide the practical tools and platforms for self-sufficiency. The combination of both fosters a holistic ecosystem that enables divorced women to reclaim agency, ensure the welfare of their children, and assert their dignity in society.

1. Right to Livelihood

The Supreme Court recognized the right to livelihood as part of Art. 21. Entrepreneurship as a means of livelihood for divorced women thus gains constitutional legitimacy.

2. Access to Credit as a Right

While not a fundamental right, access to financial institutions for credit is increasingly being viewed as a necessary condition for achieving equality. The legal obligation of banks to disburse under PMMY and Stand-Up India implies a quasi-right to access capital.

3. Entrepreneurship as Empowerment

Entrepreneurship fosters independence, self-esteem, and community respect—elements necessary for divorced women to break free from victimhood. When supported by legal remedies and policy interventions, it serves as a holistic empowerment tool.

Recommendations for Legal and Policy Reform

1. **Legal Literacy Camps** Targeted awareness programs through Legal Services Authorities (LSAs) should focus on informing divorced women about their rights and available schemes.
2. **Simplified Documentation** Government should consider alternative documentation (e.g., self-declaration forms) for women lacking formal records due to domestic estrangement or displacement.
3. **Financial Literacy as Part of Divorce Settlements** Courts should mandate attendance in entrepreneurship and financial literacy workshops as part of counseling or divorce proceedings.
4. **Integration of Schemes with Legal Remedies** Schemes like PMMY could be linked with maintenance orders or domestic violence judgments, streamlining access for verified claimants.
5. **Monitoring and Evaluation through Legal Forums** Periodic reviews by family courts or women's commissions could assess the economic rehabilitation of divorced women, thereby creating a feedback loop for policy improvement.

Conclusion

Empowering divorced women demands more than isolated legal remedies or stand-alone financial schemes. The transformative potential lies in the synergy between robust legal frameworks and targeted policy interventions. Together, they provide the dual support of enforceable rights and actionable opportunities. Laws such as the HMA and DVA affirm women's rights, while schemes like PMMY and Stand-Up India translate those rights into tangible economic pathways.

By bridging these domains, the State does not merely

fulfill a welfare function—it builds a resilient foundation for financial independence, self-worth, and intergenerational security. When combined effectively, legal and policy instruments uplift divorced women from passive recipients of aid to active contributors in the economic and social fabric

of the country. This integrative approach is not only just but necessary for creating a society rooted in equity, dignity, and empowerment for all, especially for vulnerable groups like divorced women and their children.

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Exploring Alternative Economic Models to Counter Dowry-Related Practices

Ravinder Sharma¹

Abstract

The concept of dowry system is not new to our society but it is an old age tradition or precisely can be called a curse for our society. The roots of this system of dowry are so persistently involved in our culture that it looks very much natural to the society. The financial implications of the dowry system in the society creates economic burden on the bride family that sometimes a kind of debt trap created

Despite various legislations available in the social discourse the economics of dowry is such that to separate the effects of dowry in the society alternative economic models need to be evolved. This essay explores how alternative economic models—such as cooperative economies, women-centric microfinance, social entrepreneurship, and Universal Basic Income (UBI)—can effectively counter the economic incentives and social structures that perpetuate dowry practices. It argues for a multidimensional approach that goes beyond legal prohibitions to economically empower women, reshape patriarchal market logic, and create communities where marriage-related transactions are irrelevant or discouraged.

Introduction

The system of the concept of dowry is not only specific to India but in economies of south Asia also. As a result gender injustice occurs due this system of dowry in various countries. It results in contribution to gender biasness despite laws such as the Dowry Prohibition Act (1961), the practice remains pervasive. Dowry, originally intended as a form of inheritance for women, has evolved into a coercive and burdensome tradition. According to the National Crime Records Bureau (NCRB), thousands of women face harassment, domestic violence, or death over dowry disputes each year.

Traditional approaches—legal, punitive, and educational—while crucial, have not succeeded in uprooting the socio-economic foundations of this practice. This essay posits that exploring alternative economic models can provide structural solutions to a problem that is as much about economics as it is about culture.

Dowry as an Economic Practice

Dowry is not merely a social custom but an economic transaction embedded in the patriarchal structure of marriage markets. Families often see daughters as economic burdens and sons as assets. Marriage becomes a transfer of wealth, with grooms' families demanding money, property, or goods as a condition for the union. This transaction mimics a market where grooms are commodities and marriage is a contract facilitated by dowry.

In this context, dowry becomes a form of social capital exchange, often rationalized as necessary for ensuring a "good match" or upward mobility. The dowry amount tends to rise in correlation with the groom's education, job status, or family wealth, reflecting a commodification of human relationships.

The Failure of Legal Frameworks Alone

Laws like the Dowry Prohibition Act and Sections 304B and

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498A of the Indian Penal Code provide mechanisms to punish dowry harassment. However, their enforcement remains weak due to deep-rooted social acceptance, lack of awareness, fear of societal ostracism, and often, the complicity of law enforcement officials.

Legal deterrents function best when societal norms support them. In the case of dowry, the economic rationale behind the practice frequently outweighs the fear of legal consequences. Therefore, alternative economic models are essential to shift the underlying economic calculus.

Cooperative Economic Models and Community Ownership

One promising alternative lies in cooperative economics, which emphasizes shared ownership, mutual support, and community welfare. In cooperatives, individuals pool resources for collective benefit, undermining hierarchical and individualistic wealth accumulation models that fuel dowry culture.

For instance, women's self-help groups (SHGs) in India often operate on cooperative principles. These groups not only provide financial services but also act as support systems where women challenge patriarchal practices collectively. SHGs in Kerala and Tamil Nadu have successfully created networks that actively resist dowry-related demands through community pressure and legal aid.

Moreover, community ownership of assets—such as land, businesses, or local banks—reduces the need for individual families to accumulate wealth as a strategy for securing advantageous marriages.

Microfinance and Women's Economic Empowerment

Microfinance institutions (MFIs) and self-help group (SHG)-linked bank programs have been instrumental in empowering women financially. When women have access to capital, savings, and credit, they gain autonomy and bargaining power within their households and communities.

Studies have shown that when women become economic contributors, families are less likely to treat them as liabilities. Their earning potential also reduces the perceived need for a dowry to 'offset' their presence in a new household. In Bangladesh, for example, Grameen Bank's initiatives significantly altered gender dynamics, with fewer dowry demands observed among empowered women borrowers.

However, microfinance must be carefully regulated to avoid debt traps and must be accompanied by capacity building, skill training, and

market access to ensure sustainable economic independence.

Social Entrepreneurship and Alternative Livelihood Models

Social entrepreneurship provides a hybrid model where profit is combined with social impact. Women-led social enterprises that hire and empower other women challenge the structural roots of dowry by:

- a. Generating local employment
- b. Creating role models of female leadership
- c. Breaking dependency cycles

For example, SEWA (Self Employed Women's Association) in India supports over two million women in various informal sectors. SEWA members are more likely to resist dowry pressures, advocate for equitable marriages, and invest in daughters' education.

Social businesses focused on gender equality not only change economic behavior but also create narratives of success that counter the idea of daughters being financial burdens.

Universal Basic Income (UBI) and Financial Dignity

UBI is an emerging economic model that involves providing citizens with a fixed, unconditional sum of money. If implemented with a gender focus, UBI could:

- a. Provide women with direct financial agency
- b. Reduce the economic dependency that fuels dowry
- c. Alter intergenerational wealth distribution

Critics argue UBI may disincentivize work, but targeted UBI for women and girls could elevate their status in both natal and marital homes, thereby challenging the economic rationale for dowry.

Pilot programs in Madhya Pradesh (conducted by SEWA and UNICEF) demonstrated that unconditional cash transfers improved nutrition, health, and schooling for girls and increased their say in household decisions.

Education and Skill Development as Economic Tools

Though not a model in itself, investing in education and skill-building acts as a powerful economic tool. Educated and employable women are less vulnerable to dowry-related exploitation. Furthermore, families that invest in daughters' futures are less likely to treat marriage as the final or most important financial goal.

The economic model of human capital investment proposes that returns on education (in the form of earnings and social mobility) outweigh dowry transfers. Governments and NGOs can enhance this effect by subsidizing girls' education, providing incentives for vocational training, and linking education with job placement.

Marriage Market Reforms: Alternative Marital Practices

Alternative economic models must also rethink the institution of marriage itself. Collective marriages, promoted by some states and NGOs, offer a low-cost alternative to lavish weddings and eliminate dowry.

Examples include:

Madhya Pradesh Mukhya-mantri Kanyadaan Yojana: Offers financial assistance to low-income families for mass weddings.

Arya Samaj Weddings: Promote simple ceremonies that explicitly reject dowry.

Changing consumer behaviour around marriage can be achieved through behavioural economics interventions—such as social nudges, reward programs for dowry-free marriages, and shame campaigns against opulent displays of wealth.

Redistribution-Oriented Welfare Models

Redistributive economic policies can reduce the wealth and status inequalities that fuel dowry. These include:

- a. Land reforms that give daughters inheritance rights
- b. Pension schemes and health insurance for women
- c. Housing subsidies for female-headed households

When women have access to public welfare and private property, their bargaining position strengthens, reducing the perceived need for dowry as a security mechanism.

Programs like PM Awas Yojana, which encourage joint or female-only homeownership, help shift cultural narratives by giving women tangible assets.

Grassroots and Community-Based Economics

At the grassroots level, community-driven development (CDD) and participatory budgeting can provide women with control over local resources. When women participate in decision-making about public goods, their economic status improves, and gendered norms are challenged.

For example, in Karnataka, village-level planning bodies that include female members have allocated funds to women-centric infrastructure like schools, health centers, and vocational hubs—thereby reshaping community priorities.

Conclusion

The persistence of dowry cannot be addressed solely by legal prohibitions. Since it is deeply embedded in economic rationale and social practices, alternative economic models offer the potential to transform the landscape in which dowry thrives.

By empowering women financially, fostering community ownership, redistributing resources, and reforming marriage-related expectations, we can construct an economic environment where dowry is not just illegal—but unnecessary, irrelevant, and socially unacceptable.

To fully dismantle dowry practices, economic transformation must go hand-in-hand with cultural shifts, and alternative economic models may just provide the blueprint for both.

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From Gifts to Graves : The Hidden Costs of India's Dowry Culture

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Abstract

This research study examines the social implications of dowry prohibition legislations in India, underlining their contribution towards altering societal mindset and promoting the vision of a developed India (Viksit Bharat) by the year 2047. The study delves into the historical development of dowry, its socio-economic impacts, and the continuance of the practice in spite of legislative interventions such as the Dowry Prohibition Act, 1961. The paper analyzes the efficiency of legal provisions, identifies implementation issues, and counters misuse issues. It also analyzes the differential effect on vulnerable communities and engages with diverse viewpoints, such as those of men's rights activists. The analysis highlights that obtaining a dowry-free, gender-equitable society involves strong legal reforms, mass education, people's participation, and participatory policy-making. Addressing these factors can help India join the vision of Viksit Bharat by 2047.

Keywords: Dowry Prohibition, Gender Equality, Social Impact, Legal Challenges, Viksit Bharat 2047, Reform2047

Introduction

Dowry is a long-standing social custom in India where the bride's family gives money, goods, or property to the groom's family as part of the marriage arrangement. While it has roots in cultural traditions, dowry has unfortunately morphed into a coercive practice that often results in gender-based violence, financial strain, and social inequality. The Dowry Prohibition Act of 1961 was introduced to tackle this issue, representing a crucial legislative move towards achieving gender equality and social justice. However, even after more than sixty years of being outlawed, dowry continues to be a significant problem, contributing to domestic violence, female infanticide, and economic hardship. This paper looks into the social effects of dowry prohibition laws, how effective they have been, and how they fit into India's goal of becoming a developed nation (Viksit Bharat) by 2047. It also explores the socio-economic repercussions, the legal hurdles, and the urgent need for comprehensive reforms to create a society free from dowry.

Historical Context of Dowry in India

The Historical Context of Dowry in India is an institution, dowry has historical and ancient roots in India where there existed the practice of families of the bride and groom voluntarily providing gifts for goodwill. While gifting still exists today, gradually, the notion of dowry shifted from gifting subjected to goodwill to a conditioned acceptance for the bride's family, primarily informed and enforced by patriarchal standards and pressures. The phenomenon of dowry developed into a practice used to establish a hierarchy of gender in the 20th century, conditioned by families demanding material gifts to inflate values of obscenely over-valued goods or resources, that exerted pressures on women's families and afforded openings for harassment, abuse, or violence where expectations were not achieved in the end. The first legislation on dowry in India was the Dowry Prohibition Act, 1961. This legislation recognizes that the giving or

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taking of directly constituted dowry is a crime and it imposed punishments on any person included in the act in certain sections of law, with the possibilities of prison or fine. The Dowry Prohibition Act and amendments to it in 1984 and 1986, increased punishment and establish cruelty occurring in association with dowry as an separate offence in Section 498A of Indian Penal Code (IPC). The persistence of dowry as a social issue is systemic, although defined by legal parameters, requires further interrogation of cultural dynamics, societal expectations and systemic structures supporting its persistence.

Socio-Economic Consequences of Dowry

Dowry has profound socio-economic implications. By, especially for families belonging to lower and middle sections, dowry imposes a huge financial burden on families that may cause debts or Liquidation of assets. A study conducted in 2018 by the National Council of Applied Economic Research (NCAER) , estimated that in some communities, dowry payments can take away as much as 50% of a household's savings and deepen poverty and create barriers for educational or health access. Dowry practices have reinforced gender inequality by developing the perspective that women are economic liabilities. This has contributed to suicidal implications in practices such as female infanticide and sex selective abortion. Ultimately, this slant has distorted the sex ratio of India. According to the 2011 Census, India's sex ratio is 943 females per 1000 males reflecting the long-run impacts of such practices. It was found that dowry requests are frequently used in regard to domestic violence, with the National Crime Records Bureau (NCRB) reporting around 7000 deaths each year due to dowry.

The Dowry Prohibition Act, 1961: Provisions and Implementation

The Dowry Prohibition Act, 1961 defines dowry as any property or valuable security that is given or agreed to be given in connection with a marriage. Important sections of the Act state the following:

Section 3: Prohibits giving or taking dowry; the punishments could be a maximum of five years' imprisonment and fine of ₹15,000 or the value of the dowry, whichever is higher.

Section 4: Imposing penalty for demanding dowry; imprisonments of maximum two years and fine.

Section 6 : Mandating a dowry that is received to be transferred to the bride within three months;

while it is held in trust for her benefit.

Even with these sections, the implementation of the Act continues to remain an issue. The combination of poor conviction rates, societal acceptance of dowry demands, as well as corruption in the enforcement agencies has severely limited the ability of the Act to be effective. In fact, a 2020 Ministry of Women and Child Development reported that only ten percent of dowry-related cases lead to convictions, with the main reasons being either lack of evidence or social pressure on the victim to withdraw their complaint.

Case Law: S. Gopal Reddy v. State of Andhra Pradesh (1996)

In this landmark case, the Supreme Court clarified that dowry demands made post marriage are also subject to the provisions of the Act. It reiterated that the objective of this statutory provision is to safeguard women against harassment and furthermore upheld the conviction of the accused under Section 4. By ruling that due to the ongoing nature of dowry demands the Act covers demands made both before and after marriage, the scope of the protection is further enlarged.

Challenges in Implementation

There are various barriers to effectively applying dowry prohibition laws:

1. **Social Acceptance of Dowry:** Dowry is perceived as a normal cultural practice where families see dowry as a stature. Perceptions of dowry as a status symbol allows individuals, and families, to normalize dowry violations which makes it even less likely that individuals will report those violations.
2. **Limited Evidence:** Evidence for dowry transactions can be difficult to prove because do wrong transactions are private, and witnesses are limited.
3. **Police and Judicial Ineffectiveness:** Police corruption, police inadequacy (poor training), and lengthy judicial processes stop victims from pursuing legal options and obtaining justice.
4. **Improper Usage of Laws:** Men's rights activists have raised the issue of improper usage of Section 498A and its devastating impact through false complaints of false dowry demands, false allegations of domestic violence, and harassment of husbands and their families. The Supreme Court in Arnesh Kumar v. State of Bihar (2014) acknowledged this issue and highlighted the importance of proper, preliminary investigations before peace officers automatically arrest, often

without proper investigation, in dowry cases specifically to limit the improper use of Section 498A.

Case Law: Arnesh Kumar v. State of Bihar (2014)

This case dealt with the misuse of Section 498A, and the Supreme Court pointed out that "non-specific or embellished" forms of complaints were impeding the judicial process, ordering that arrests are not to be made automatically and that police made a preliminary inquiry to balance harm to victim and the undeserved harm to the accused.

Impact on Marginalized Communities

Dowry prohibition laws impact the marginalized communities differentially (Scheduled Castes (SCs), Scheduled Tribes (STs), and Other Backward Classes (OBCs)). Often these communities navigate both socioeconomic pressures and caste stigma. For example, in rural areas, dowry is exacerbated by caste, in that families from lower castes must satisfy social acceptance and expect to pay more dowry (rather than less). In a 2019 study involving SC/ST families, the International Institute for Population Sciences reported that 60% of families faced financial strain related to dowry payments; while only 40% of families from upper-caste facing the same pressures. Furthermore, these women were often unable to obtain legal recourse, as they lacked the awareness to do so or were unwilling as they were economically dependent, or were subject to ostracism. Legal stipulations for dowry prohibition do not provide any targeted interventions for such communities, which further limits the law's efficacy.

Perspectives from Men's Rights Activists

Men's rights activists contend that dowry prohibition laws, particularly Section 498A, are subject to misapplication leading to the wrongful targeting of men and their families. Some organizations, such as the Save Indian Family Foundation, affirm that many dowry complaints are false and enact revenge, or that women also make use of the complaints to extort money from families. The Centre for Social Research found in 2017 that 10-15% of dowry-related cases involve exaggerated or false cases, the majority were real cases. While misapplication of the laws is a problem, it should not take away the need to protect real victims. The Supreme Court has ruled in a number of these cases, such as Arnesh Kumar v. State of Bihar, which tried to ensure due process while protecting woman's rights.

Role of Education and Community Engagement

Legal measures alone perhaps will not be enough to eradicate dowry within India. It requires social change that can only be accomplished by education and engaging the community. Awareness campaigns can serve as the initial catalyst for changing patriarchal norms and implications of dowry and towards encouraging gender equality. Programs like the Beti Bachao, Beti Padhao initiative first launched in 2015 are seeking to create the right attitude shift by ensuring girls are educated and empowered. Using community-based interventions such as self-help groups and women collectives have also been shown to reduce dowry practices and norms in rural settings.

Case Study: Tamil Nadu's Anti-Dowry Campaigns

In Tamil Nadu, local campaigns spearheaded by NGOs like the Tamil Nadu Women's Forum have generally succeeded in reducing dowry practices in some districts. The campaigns included community conversations, workshops, and coalitions of Tamil Nadu women's forum allies and local community leaders who encouraged dowry-free marriages. A 2022 evaluation noted that there was an overall 20% decrease in dowry complaints in areas where the campaign was active, suggesting the useful potential of community-based action.

Alignment with Viksit Bharat @2047

The vision of Viksit Bharat by 2047 is to create a developed, inclusive, and equitable India. To make this vision a reality, we must eradicate dowry, which represents gender inequity, economic disparities, and social injustices.

Prohibitory dowry laws support Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 5 (Gender Equality) because it focuses on empowering women and reducing violence. To achieve a dowry-free society, we require:

- 1. An Enhanced Legal Framework:** Implementation of increased penal sanctions, a streamlined justice system, and mechanisms to prevent misuse through improved investigation procedures.
- 2. Economic Empowerment:** Provide women with education and employment avenues to reduce reliance on marriage-based financial arrangements.
- 3. Cultural Paradigm Shifts:** Encourage dowry-free marriages using media, educational, and religious institutions, and/or public forums.
- 4. Inclusive Policies:** Addressing the needs of marginalized communities to ensure equitable reach and impact.

Recommendations

To enhance the social impact of dowry prohibition laws and align with Viksit Bharat:

1. Strengthen Enforcement: Train police and judicial officers to handle dowry cases sensitively and efficiently.
2. Public Awareness Campaigns: Use digital platforms, schools, and community centers to educate about the harms of dowry.
3. Support for Victims: Establish dedicated helplines and shelters for dowry victims, particularly in rural areas.
4. Engage Men and Boys: Involve men in campaigns to challenge patriarchal norms and promote gender equality.
5. Address Misuse: Implement stricter guidelines for investigating dowry complaints to prevent false allegations while protecting genuine victims.

6. Targeted Interventions for Marginalized Communities: Provide legal aid and economic support to SC/ST and OBC families to reduce dowry pressures.

Conclusion

The Dowry Prohibition Act, 1961, represents a significant step toward eradicating dowry and promoting gender equality in India. However, its social impact is limited by implementation challenges, societal acceptance, and misuse concerns. Achieving a dowry-free society requires a multi-pronged approach, combining robust legal enforcement, widespread education, and community engagement. By addressing these challenges, India can align with the vision of Viksit Bharat by 2047, fostering a society that is equitable, inclusive, and free from oppressive practices like dowry.

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BREAKING BARRIERS : The Legal and Social Dimensions of Adoption by Same-Sex Couples in India

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Abstract

The evolving discourse on LGBTQIA+ rights in India has brought the contentious issue of adoption by same-sex couples to the forefront of socio-legal debate. Despite the decriminalization of homosexuality in 2018, same-sex couples continue to face systemic exclusion from the legal framework governing adoption. This paper critically examines the multifaceted legal and social challenges encountered by same-sex couples in India seeking to adopt children. By analyzing statutory provisions such as the Hindu Adoption and Maintenance Act, 1956, the Juvenile Justice (Care and Protection of Children) Act, 2015, and the Special Marriage Act, 1954, the study underscores the inadequacies of existing laws that fail to recognize non-heteronormative family structures. The paper concludes by advocating for comprehensive legal reform, increased public awareness, and the creation of inclusive policy frameworks. The research highlights that granting adoption rights to same-sex couples is not merely a legal imperative but a moral and social necessity to uphold the best interests of the child and the fundamental rights of LGBTQIA+ individuals.

Keywords: Same-Sex Adoption, LGBTQIA+ Rights in India, Adoption Law, Legal Discrimination, Family Law Reform.

Introduction

In recent years, same sex marriage has been recognized at the national level in the US and Australia, while equal marriage rights have been granted in a growing number of European countries (Scherman et al., 2020). However, in spite of efforts made by LGBT advocates and the pressure of international human rights treaties to reform discriminatory marriage laws, same-sex marriage is still illegal in many parts of the world including Asia, Africa, Middle East. As a result, same-sex couples' access to adoption varies widely around the globe. In four states in Australia a same-sex couples could apply for adoption after being in a registered relationship for two years; another six states had laws containing inconsistencies, in some, laws were ambiguous and the legal standing of gay couples remained uncertain; in others, LGBT people were totally excluded from adoption. Adoption by gay and lesbian couples is legally permitted in three provinces. In many parts of the world both adoption and sexual minority rights were either in their infancy or not recognized at all.

Historical Context of Adoption in India

The notion that adoption is an inferior way to create a family has negatively influenced the development of adoption law in a manner parallel to the debt of social shame that surrounded single motherhood prior to its modern-day acceptance. This shame has its roots in the ancient adoptions that cast adopted children as inferiors under this religious system. The influence of these ancient adoptions on modern law is undeniable. As recently as the 1960s, the stigma accompanying a history of illegitimacy dictated that an adopted child's history be erased by sealing both the birth and the final adoption record. This disdain for illegitimacy and adoption appears to be identical in all relevant legal systems to ancient adoptions. It is this disgrace that informs the modern common law's failure to develop and thus expand adoption as a means of creating a family

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(Irene Hanan, 2010).

Even today, in an era of “out-of-wedlock” births, gay marriage, and inconsistent statutory language on adoption rights, many people still react with incredulity that a child could be adopted by something less than opposite-gender parents. It is this societal perception that has supplied legislative inertia against the expansion of adoption law in most states and all countries. Changing societal views of race relations, sexual “normalcy,” and the inevitability of social progress must take root in order for extensive change to occur. Today’s deferral of adoption will not be tomorrow’s problem (Tasker & Bellamy, 2019). The reality today is that in India many areas of law treat same-gender couples as inferior human beings who cannot make a family, be intimate with each other, care for an elderly parent, or fall under a network of rights and obligations with respect to property.

Legal Framework Governing Adoption

In the past, adoptions were granted only to charitable or public institutions or to persons unable to support their children. In the 1970s, restrictions on private adoptions loosened further concerning the need for parental consent. The legislature made it possible for adoption by a single person. The Hindu Adoption and Maintenance Act, 1956, made it available to Hindus, Buddhists, Jains, and Sikhs. An adopted child must be a Hindu, Buddhist, Jain, or Sikh, or become one under this Act. Adoption under this Act requires that the adopter be a male Hindu, a female Hindu, or by a husband and wife jointly and have the capacity to adopt (14 years older than the adopted child) and that adoption be valid in law and without any hindered prohibitions of a lawful marriage in this Act. Hindus and Muslims follow customary laws, so they cannot adopt a child if the person intended to adopt is a couple. Customary law cannot be registered, nor does the State have a record of the validity of such adoption (Scherman et al., 2020). The Adoption of Children Act, 1961 governs adoption and maintenance in Christian families, a male or female of a marriageable age as per religion customary law has the power to adopt.

Legal Recognition of Same-Sex Relationships

India's progressive social reforms, in addition to the need for thriving adoption legislation, have resulted in a global conversation on the rights of the LGBTQIA+ community and issues regarding the legality of same-sex marriages. It is currently a challenge in many nations where same-sex marriages are unrecognized, including India, Nepal, Pakistan,

Russia, Sri Lanka, and Bangladesh, to name a few. The criminalization of Article 377 of the Indian Penal Code of 1860, which bans sexual activity against the order of nature, is one of the main obstacles preventing same-sex couples from officially marrying or sharing legal rights and duties. As a result, partners face restrictions in various spheres of life, including healthcare and property rights. Marriage certificates are issued to heterosexual couples in India as public documents, enabling them to avail government schemes, insurance benefits, and succession, inheritance, and taxation rights.

Case Studies of Same-Sex Couples

The emergence of straight, gay, or lesbian couples as potential adoptive parents has sparked widespread social debate and discussion of this form of family expansion. There is debate and discussion about the potential effects on children’s social development as a result of being reared by single-sex couples. Opponents argue that children adopted by gay or lesbian couples are predisposed to social maladjustments or disorders due to their upbringing outside traditional family units. Proponents argue that the parent/guardian figure is more mythical than biological, and all minors need as much parental love and care as is attainable, regardless of the sexual orientation or identity of the parents. This study aims to answer the question: how do New Zealand lawyers and social workers perceive children being (or likely to be) adopted by gay male couples or lesbian couples? Meanwhile, this research addresses the questions: how does the literature on gay/lesbian parenting in general coalesce? And how does this literature with specific reference to New Zealand?

Impact of Adoption on Children

A critical component in determining the eligibility of a couple to adopt a child is the child's best interests. No form of adoption should be legally referred to as "other" or "superior," nor should it embody stereotyped parental models. The evidence base has widened around the equality of outcomes for children adopted by same-sex parents relative to those raised by heterosexual ones (Tasker & Bellamy, 2019). Overall, children's psychological adjustment, family relationships, and openness about adoption services have been largely studied in samples with equal gender ratios and age-matched heterosexual control families. Children's greater understanding of their adoption and its variables, including knowing even their father's identity and knowing that he was either a donor as in open lesbian families or a heterosexual or bisexual man in heterosexual families, has been

independently linked to fewer adjustment problems at ages four to six. To this end, an in-depth research program involving a longitudinal follow-up of a large sample of families living in social contexts different from those covered by earlier studies is being planned for the coming decade.

Future Directions for Policy and Reform

In India, there is a disparity of legal rights for children adopted by heterosexual and same-sex couples. Adoption of children by married heterosexual couples is legally recognized, whereas adoption by same-sex couples is currently not recognized by law. Due to the lack of rights for same-sex couples to adopt, these families often exist as single parents in the eyes of the law, creating issues of legal custodianship for children (Scherman et al., 2020). In the absence of caring adults with equal rights, these families tend to live with fear that a divorce, otherwise commonplace, can tear them apart, with no single parent receiving custody, and thus raising the children as orphans. The non-homosexual partner often lacks any legal rights in these cases (Tasker & Bellamy, 2019).

India is a signatory to the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child but while favoring children to have two parents or adult guardians, it adds that at least one parent must be Indian. The inter-country adoption pact with the Hague is limiting for Indian applicants, all of whom are heterosexual couples. Children adopted in India are not eligible for citizenship on the basis of their adoption, dissenting from other nations and from the recommendations of the Law Commission of India. Domestic adoptions, too, are fraught with legal problems, with no minimum age for children to adopt. Socially, adoption in India is often arranged through contacts and personal networks. However, same-sex couples are excluded from such networks. Adoption cannot be seen in isolation, and is more than just a question of legality. The refusal of the right to adopt is also a refusal of public visibility, cultural recognition, and social regard.

The right to adopt is an intrinsic part of LGBT rights, especially in a nation like India where LGBT relationships are not lawfully recognized. The free exercise of the right to adopt is an essential component of achieving equality under Article 14 and the right to life and to live with dignity under Article 21 of the Constitution of India. No law presently exists that makes adoption unlawful for non-heterosexual parents; because of this ambiguity same-sex couples and individuals are effectively

rendered invisible and unable to negotiate their wrestling with familial desires through formal channels.

Proposed Legal Reforms

Like in any other country where same-sex relationship has recently been recognised, the issue of adoption by same-sex couples in India has emerged as a trending topic among advocates and activists. There are two types of adoption laws in India: the Hindu Adoption and Maintenance Act, 1956 (HAMA) and the Juvenile Justice Act, 2015 (JJ Act). Given the cultural context, the question of why same-sex adoptive couples is still not treated at par with different-sex adoptive couples (with the same-sex partners of a biological parent), and the question of why there is no recognition of adoption by same-sex partners as a family unit raises both legal and social implications. This transformative social justice issue can be approached from both legal and social scientific angles. The issue of adoption by same-sex couples has been dealt with concerning the HAMA. HAMA is also referred to as the Hindu Adoption Act or the Adoption Law, which has been the paradigm reading on adoption and the exclusion of same-sex couples from its purview. Five case laws have been illustrated concerning the juvenile adoption that enabled single and hetero-parenting as a family unit while excluding same-sex couples. Both the HAMA and the JJ Act authenticate adoption, but a tacit allowance of adoption by a single individual, a biological parent, or a couple leads to multiple implications to be read between those two acts that explicitly exclude the recognition of same-sex couples as a family unit.

The discussion of the rights of a person in an intimate relationship has been limited to the recognition of that relationship. There have been only a handful of attempts in exploring the rights of the family unit of two or more intimate partners. Right to adopt of the family unit of same-sex partners extends debates on the immovable rights of a family unit like the right to cohabit, the rights of intimacy, family welfare, right to procreate, and the recently recognised reproductive rights. The text of the Constitution and the provisions of HAMA and the JJ Act of adoption highlight that, in either text, there is no mention of non-hetero-normative sexual relations. Inclusion is a policy predicated on the choice of a family unit with the genetic, sexual, and parenting industrialisation by heterosexual couples only. Adoption as a notion of illegitimacy stands rooted in the offspring of reproductive labour relation. The

significance of parenting by the same-sex couple in a kinship arrangement has yet to be explored (Scherman et al., 2020).

Journal articles concerning the heterosexuality of parenting have not been subjected to critique and resistance during the birth and care of such an illegitimate offspring. Parenting has also remained exclusive to women, with this being taboo. The language of academia concerning either understanding adoption or oathed by heterosexuality prevents the unmitigated reception of the language of the law in the Indian adoption process in terms of age, marital status, and single parenting by other-than-hetero-normative sexual relations. The absence of a representation of non-heterosexuality also creates a lacuna on issues of complex amour-propre women partnering with women by culture, by religion, or by history. In fact, the recognition of illegitimacy prevents access to the law and the window to articulate the method to redress it. Thus, answering the questions of legal and social implicatedness articulate the rights to queer time and reproduction that trump hegemonic time and genetic legacies.

Role of Public Awareness Campaigns

Today's status quo of LGBTQ+ issues in adopting/surrogacy in India is stained with inequalities and systemic oppression fueled by hegemonic normative order ((Scherman et al., 2020)). Here the legal dimension encompasses closely-sealed bureaucratic policies, eligibility, rights of biological/surrogate/foster parents, child's right to know origin, provisions for anyone wanting to become a legal guardian, and provisions for dispute resolution. The social dimension encompasses acceptance, societal hurdles of negotiation, disapproval, alienation, biases on competency as a parent, stigma based on relationships, child safety threats with regard to sexual abuse/exploitation and legitimacy, findings of children inquiring about origins, and gap in maturity of supportive parents (Tasker & Bellamy, 2019)).

Public campaigns can counter sexual/social stigma of queer families plus 3 ways to raise acceptance and alter perceptions in favour of queer families through 3 campaigns. Campaigns on education, visibility, and legitimacy of queer families that address sexual/social stigma can be envisaged. Speaking to a heterosexual audience, these campaigns would help begin and widen acceptance. First and foremost, it is pertinent to view queer families that have managed to survive within the parameters of hegemonic norms. Further, within their living situations, their choice of a family

structure, i.e. a childless intimacy instead of a conventional family structure, must not be viewed as aberrant to a normative family.

Within India's puritanical fabric, queer couples too, with the 7½-CS-layered structural constraints, are obliged to continue their families and bear children. As a means to choose a sex-responsible family, adoption/surrogacy is viewed in relation to bio-legitimacy. Hence, radicalising queer families as deviant to their parent/surrogate personas suffices to de-legitimise their family status. Hence, campaigns on the legitimacy of queer families within family studies must be undertaken. Research on queer families existing in other countries must be consulted, and relationships of social conditions and parenting/child adjustment against heteronormative parenting practices must be mapped to queer parenting practices in Urdu and brought to diverse media, including newspaper and television.

There should be a national agency responsible for queer family research to encourage and simplify the way through and provide every kind of support. The legal provision of child safety in any endeavour must foster legitimacy. Study findings must be publicised to expand the discourse across regional and academic barriers. Relevant discourses on the safety and understanding of adopting/surrogacy procedures must be brought to major platforms. Adoption by queer couples, proposals for surrogacy by queer couples, and representations in youth concerns must be greenlighted.

Conclusion

As has become abundantly clear, lesbian, gay, bisexual, and transgender (LGBT) lives and families are complex—continuously re-formed and re-imagined—and intersecting in varied ways in a globalized world. Today's challenges, as well as the research agenda, are emerging from the lived realities of normative family formations refracted through the multifaceted relationships between culture, ethnicity, class, sexuality, and, more recently, globalization (Tasker & Bellamy, 2019). Behind the seemingly coherent and united LGBT movements are fissures and contestations around race, ethnicity, nationality, morality, religion, and organizing strategies and tactics.

As the growing body of work illustrated, understanding LGBT lives and families requires seriously engaging with their particular cultural (including race, ethnicity, and religion), historical, and socio-political locations (Scherman et al., 2020). In

addition, scholars need to look beyond the West and Western paradigms to consider how LGBT lives and politics are lived, shaped, and represented in the Global South and East, and how such lived realities renarrate and remap existing analytical categories and concepts. Further, in the domain of family, it is critical to take a relational approach and see how different kinds of families are tied to variegated privileges and disparities, how power operates within and among LGBT families, and how the questions of family enable further insights into what it means to be queer in culturally specific and geopolitically sensitive contexts. In a word, there is a need to keep breaking barriers (either analytical or geographical)—not only in terms of scholarly subfields, but also between academia and activism—and listen to and amplify the voices of LGBT lives and families far removed from one's own.

Human rights—for the poor, the homeless, the crazy, the sick, the dying, the unseen, the unrecognizable—happen only when these bodies center their own lives and for a time reclaim the world. By focusing on the oppression of queer citizens—as is often the case in liberal democracies—the debt owed to the disenfranchised poor heterosexual, oft-forgotten single mothers, the sick elderly, and stray animals is obscured. The problem of the forgotten grows larger still when culture, rather than law or rights, becomes the locus of activism. In the struggle over recognition, norms also get contested, diverted, and subverted (and sometimes, ironically, reinforced). Queer cultural politics in China is remapped as a shifting struggle between civil society activism, mediated projection, and state regulation amid the tensions of a rising capitalist state wrestling with globalization.

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Evaluating The Effectiveness of Enforcement Agencies in Combating White Collar Crimes in India

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Abstract

White-collar crimes, marked by their sophistication, non-violent nature, and high-level perpetrators, have emerged as a formidable challenge to regulatory and enforcement mechanisms in India. Despite the increasing frequency and financial impact of such crimes, enforcement responses remain fragmented and often ineffective. This study critically examines the capacity, efficacy, and limitations of Indian enforcement agencies in addressing white-collar crimes, drawing on legal frameworks, inter-agency dynamics, and institutional resources. It traces the historical development of regulatory efforts, analyzes the mandates of key agencies such as the Enforcement Directorate, the Central Bureau of Investigation, and the Economic Offences Wing, and assesses their enforcement outputs relative to the scale of economic offenses. The research further explores challenges including jurisdictional overlap, resource scarcity, legislative ambiguity, and technological constraints. The study argues that while India has made notable legislative strides, enforcement remains encumbered by institutional inertia, lack of specialization, and weak deterrence mechanisms.

Keywords: White-collar crime, enforcement agencies, regulatory framework, institutional challenges, India

Introduction

White-collar crimes present diverse challenges to law enforcement personnel, victims, and society in general. Ever since Edwin Sutherland introduced the term ‘white-collar crimes’, they have been comparatively less elucidated than the traditional blue-collar crimes such as burglaries, murders, and robberies. However, white-collar crimes essentially possess the same characteristics as the traditional crimes: the absence of opportunity does not eliminate the drive to commit crimes nor acts that would be crimes if they had occurred in different circumstances. Many sectors have suffered more damages due to white-collar crimes than street riots and burglaries. It is estimated that only around 1% of white-collar crimes will serve time in prison or face criminal penalties for their actions.

Understanding White Collar Crimes

In 1939 American sociologist Edwin Sutherland suggested the concept of white-collar crime, which has been referred to as corporate crime, regulatory crime or business crime, with a myriad of definitions articulated since then. White-collar crime acts involve acts of fraud, misrepresentation or breach of trust, committed by corporate agents, that occur in the course or context of business operations or trade, but do not involve conventional property crime acts. Specialised laws, rules and regulations have been developed to prosecute white-collar criminals, such as laws prohibiting bribery and insider trading, as well as laws regulating market transactions and financial activities. Regulatory agencies in financial and company matters have also been established in the state apparatus, in tandem with specialised laws. Similarly, numerous law enforcement agencies have been set up to enforce these specialised laws and regulations. White-collar crime generally comprises crimes of business and corporate actors in the finance, company and accounting sectors, and it usually does not involve arrests, such as

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imprisonments. It has a broader meaning in the criminal law sense since it refers to crimes committed in the course or context of trade or business operations for profit or gain. It also carries a wider meaning in the regulatory context, covering various acts pertaining to the domestic operations of transnational companies. Thus understanding white-collar crime may need a systematic mapping of its several meanings and dimensions, especially in the Asia-Pacific region, where white-collar crimes are being committed at an unprecedented scale but the enforcement purported to bring white-collar criminals to justice remains hard-pressed for a lack of tradition in terms of both substantive and enforcement laws (Kilcommins & Spain, 2020).

Definition and Scope

Since Edwin Sutherland coined the term “white-collar crime” in 1939, attempts to define the concept have proven challenging (Kilcommins & Spain, 2020). Sutherland’s definition was that white-collar crime was “a crime committed by a person of respectability and high social status in the course of his occupation”. The first element entails “a person of respectability and high social status” committing a crime and it is the respectability/status of the person, rather than the nature of the crime committed, that is the key aspect. For Sutherland, this element presented the challenge to wider societal thinking about crime and the respectability of those committing crimes. It was this aspect that, for Sutherland, would necessitate a different approach to detection, prosecution and punishment. The second element in his definition was the occurrence of “the course of his occupation”. This element focuses on the professional aspect of white-collar crime, both “personal” and “organisational”. In this regard, it encapsulates the social network of a person committing a crime involving the connection to fellow offenders, victims, witnesses and law enforcement agencies. The third element, present in many definitions of corporate crime, is the notion of responsibility. One of Sutherland’s examples, General Motors, illustrated that it is not a person directly employed by the corporation that commits the crime, but it is the corporation itself that commits the crime and this should focus attention away from the culpability of the corporation and upon the individuals responsible. Prior to this, a decade of criminological research would suggest that it is this lack of a responsible social actor that would thwart attempts at detection and regulation. The notion of responsibility is key to any definition of corporate crime.

Historical Context

The history of white-collar and corporate crime in our nation has been one of toleration. Throughout much of this century, the victims, the government, and the criminal justice system have been largely inactive in attempting to control this form of law-violating behavior. As a result, occupational and organizational crime offenders have been treated preferentially in our courts compared to traditional or common crime offenders. Beginning in the 1970s, however, public attitudes began to change and the government and criminal justice system were given a mandate to pursue these offenders (Alan Johnson, 2009). Concerned about the perceived rise in white-collar crime, the newly elected President Nixon created the White House Task Force on Crime and requested that a special emphasis be placed on this form of crime. The emphasis was still qualities and ownership rather than on enforcement and punishment but, in response to the Task Force request, a division of white-collar crime and the investigation and prosecution of these offenders was a stated goal. In January 1974 the white-collar crime unit was created as it was perceived that the hands of the Bureau were tied to pursue it under existing laws and that new legislation was needed. The initial response was the formation of a committee to draft legislation to be implemented by the President’s Task Force and designed to address investigatory problems of the Bureau. It was noted at this time that laws were in existence which could reach most white-collar crime but that enforcement was a far more difficult and serious problem, which encompassed reasons for the lack of enforcement.

Types of White Collar Crimes

Few criminologists study white-collar crime. This is not due to a lack of interest; it is because few offenders are put on trial, and even fewer are sentenced to prison. Many harmful activities of businesses or occupational elites are not labeled as "crime." Instead, they are examined from the perspectives of ethics, morals, and public relations. As a matter of fact, these activities may be subject to administrative or regulatory law instead of criminal law. Under regulatory law, the penalty may not be imprisonment but financial penalties or disqualification for trade.

The Role of Enforcement Agencies

Croall argues that the term “crime” is contentious, as many harmful activities of businesses (especially large corporations) are ruled not by criminal, but administrative or regulatory law. As a result, many

activities that are deemed harmful by the general public or by people in authority, may not count as a crime in the legal or technical sense, and would not be subject to criminal sanction but rather non-criminal regulatory sanction (Gottschalk & Smith, 2016). Even where a crime is believed to have been committed, there may be other enforcement options available, such as civil action, administrative sanction or the application of regulatory enforcement. Thus, many activities that are, in the public's mind, undoubtedly a crime, remain completely unnoticed and unpunished by the criminal justice system. With regard to white-collar crime, this definition would unfortunately be true in all countries. Very few white-collar criminals come to trial, and far fewer are sentenced to imprisonment. Moreover, those that are convicted on occasion for what seems to be significant white-collar crime, often receive comparatively short sentences, or fines.

The very novelty and complexity of many modern crimes means the enforcement agency often have necessarily to rely on sophisticated investigations that take longer and need a greater quantity of evidence before action can be taken. Fraud involves using deception for illegal monetary gain. White-collar offenders are typically people in high-status positions who commit their crimes through deceit and concealment rather than through physical violence. Public corruption is a type of white-collar crime involving a breach of trust. This involves government officials using their public office for personal gain. Corruption threatens national security, undermines the public's faith in government services, and undercuts the effectiveness of government programs. Since corruption often involves a complex web of collusion between public officials, the FBI has the technical, financial, and legal resources to combat corruption.

Current Enforcement Mechanisms

The socio-economic and legal environment in which white-collar crimes occur today is characterized by the rapid growth of technology, the globalization of economies, corporatization of businesses, slowing economic growth in many countries, changes in societal values and perceptions, and regulatory and institutional approaches to combating economic crime. The enforcement mechanisms specified in laws and regulations are as diverse and complex as the environment in which white-collar crimes are committed. Indeed, the manner in which the enforcement mechanisms have evolved reflects the changing nature of white-collar crimes.

Legislative Framework

Legislative tools against white collar crimes entered into force in 1999 when the Senate and the House approved the implementing Regulations on the Code of Commerce (CC) and the General Law on Ec Shesters (GL) that paved the way for their proper application. The National Treasure and the National Banking and Securities Commissions are now in charge of monitoring compliance with the above-mentioned regulations. In October 2003, a further set of regulations was published that address the disclosure obligations of obligation of public companies' directors and officers as well as Mexican and foreign individuals with respect to important transactions involving companies governed by Mexican law. These regulations also came into force in 2003.

Regulatory Approaches

The rising class of white collar crimes, especially the one involving sophisticated corporations, proved too big to fail and evade convictions by the enforcers. It now constitutes a global system with multi layered hierarchies and is growing at a compound rate of 10%. Despite the magnitudes of damages the ill-natured activities have burgeoned beyond the estimates. The retribution mechanisms have also failed to adapt and accommodate the rapidly evolving deceptions. Class action suits have dried up due to mounting costs facing the applicants and mismatch between the damages and recovery.

Public Perception and Impact

Much, if not all, of the public perception research cites public apathy concerning elite deviance. There is a strange juxtaposition between the soaring prevalence and given attention to white-collar crime on one hand and the seemingly nonexistent public interest on the other. The fact that the massive scandal of the decade was perceived as public apathy underscores social science's relative lack of knowledge to this extent. Two probable factors for such apathy could be the aforementioned delayed harm and lack of immediacy of white-collar crime. Work-related illnesses and deaths may occur years after exposure to toxic substances in the workplace and may not shock public opinion as much as homicide (Michel, 2014). But to those that attribute so much tolerance of elite deviance to public indifference, the events surrounding the collapse of Enron sniff out the apathy. In the summer of 2001, Enron stock was in the high seventies, but by autumn, it had plummeted to below one dollar per share one

week after the company filed for bankruptcy. This event garnered national attention, and it suddenly became apparent that a huge company had used millions to hide losses (Alan Johnson, 2009). With the stock's ascent, many analysts endorsed the stock, but when it plummeted, heads rolled at Enron, and numerous lawsuits followed.

Trust in Enforcement Agencies

The 21st century has been marked by revelations of large-scale corporate financial failures and accounting scandals, giving rise to widespread corporate crime. The scandals have raised questions regarding the implications of white collar crime for corporate executives, shareholders, corporate governance, tax collection, audit firms and corporate consultants, and whether the rules and regulations that govern the corporate world were insufficient or if the latter were merely not enforced. Beyond regulatory reform, organizations increasingly seek to determine how they are likely to be affected by the current wave of corporate financial scandals and reinforce their reputations with stakeholders wary of corporate fraud. In addition to updates of rules and regulations designed to govern corporate activity, organizations can also adopt more effective self-policing and change the corporate cultures underlying corporate fraud. This may involve modifications at the board of directors, management and corporate governance firm levels, moving forward to new forms of management and corporate governance at the executive, oversight and consulting levels, education, and modification of associated cultures (Vaughan, 1982).

Evidently, both scholars and practitioners seek to understand the nature and causes of corporate fraud and how to best shape corporate governance systems, firm structures, executive attitudes, risk perceptions, and corporate cultures in order to avoid stakeholder damning revelations of large-scale fraud. While much attention has been devoted to the short-term history of a scandal in order to determine how the event occurred, scant attention has been paid to forwarding a long-term, predictive account of fraud and the environments in which it is most likely to occur. Moreover, though considerable attention has been paid to proposing ways to mitigate the occurrence of future events, organizations have tended to theorize about and implement approaches to control that are based on expected transactions and outcomes rather than individuals' socially constructed perceptions of rule, religion, sanction, and profit (Ojo, 2010).

Future Directions for Enforcement

Various regulatory bodies vested with the powers to regulate companies are important in ensuring the enforcement of laws, rules, regulations, and circulars. The enforcement mechanism plays a vital role in protecting market integrity. It is necessary to create disincentives for violators and create conditions for good conduct as market players. The enforcement actions aim to ensure a market that is free of arbitrary decisions and impropriety by the enforcement agencies. Therefore, the law that guarantees penal sanctions should be straightforward, while discretion should be regulated by law. The enforcement policy and practice must be transparent, consistent, and predictable to ensure that they do not become the tools of harassment and intimidation. Enforcement of economic regulation should not be used as a policy for macroeconomic control (Ford, 2005). To ensure that economic reinforcement is swift, transparent, and effective, it is necessary to take steps towards peer control. The controlling body must be independent and free from any other interests. The law and rules framed must be segregated from policy control, and a time-bound decision mechanism with staggered penalties must be established. A framework must be created with a generally accepted code of conduct, and the legal frameworks should begin and end with direct conditions. Alternative measures should also be defined, and facilitation should precede penal provisions. Lastly, to maintain an optimal deterrent value, penalties should be closely guarded state secrets.

Conclusion

White-collar offenders may be defined as "persons of respectability and high social status who commit a crime in the course of their legitimate occupation." The accountability process in the commission of a corporation offense must either pierce the corporate veil or identify persons responsible. Corporate crime in the context of public victimization or private victimization could be distinguished. Corporations commit crimes with the intention of enhancing their financial status. Inside-job corporations embezzled or diverted funds to their own use (Alan Johnson, 2009). Documented interpretation of criminal acts committed indicates a likelihood to victimization by a person of respectability and high social status. Constraints and checks that exist to contend corporate crime and white-collar crime, in particular, are difficult to administer, restrictive, expensive, and extra-legal deterrents which impede corporation victimization. Corporation victims traditionally

existed in the form of private concern. They acted collectively as mission planners and organizers, disobeying local regulations governing land-use and constructions. The experience of South Estes is indicated. Directors and officers of this fictitious start-up entity used outside consultants to draft the prospectus of a high-technology semiconductor business and later revised the project to grounded gasoline distribution stations at 13 sites in the local Toronto area. Inferences of individual wrongdoing are not easily captured and are inherently difficult to prove. A reference case of rare corporate sentencing was of Roman egg company that committed fraud. Watching the theatrics of mock trial is fun and innovative, but punishment and accountability of individuals is needed. Extolling the societal accountability of the corporations involved misses the deeper malaise.

The Elliott and Duran case underscored the SEC's disproportionate emphasis on violation of Sarbanes-Oxley as opposed to prior antifraud statutes. In addition to the attempts to prevent the commission of white-collar crimes, several enforcement mechanisms to restrain such misconduct or retaliate against violators exist. These include state and federal government post hoc civil actions, state and federal criminal prosecutions of individuals and corporations, dismissal and debarment, tax enforcement, and private civil actions in both state and federal courts. Such remedies act mainly to penalize the perpetrators of white-collar crimes or to recover losses inflicted

by these crimes. However, some of the remedies, such as dismissal and debarment, civil and criminal actions, seriously affect the competitive viability of corporations found responsible for white-collar crimes. These remedies are available to governmental agencies only against the corporations involved. Therefore, the analysis of the enforcement mechanisms proceeds in that context.

SEC civil actions, which stem from the violation of applicable securities regulations, are the principal enforcement mechanism available against publicly-traded corporations with regard to their white-collar crimes. The ability and willingness of the SEC to investigate potential violations and to prosecute detected violations strongly influence the probability of those violations, which is weighed against the expected losses stemming from commission of the violations in the analysis of profitability of white-collar crimes. Since 1934, the SEC has championed the federal government's efforts to prevent and remedy violations of the laws and regulations related to the offering and exchange of securities. The SEC post hoc enforcement actions against the white-collar crimes committed by publicly traded corporations or their managers has primarily relied on civil actions. Restraining violations of the Sarbanes-Oxley Act was hardly mentioned in the SEC forum speeches. A more notable deficiency in the SEC speeches was an almost non-existent mention of traditional antifraud statutes, except a few acknowledgments in the form of general statements.

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Balancing Innovation and Individual Rights : A Critical Appraisal of Online Privacy and Data Protection in India

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Abstract

The digital revolution has intensified debates surrounding online privacy and data protection, particularly in emerging economies like India, where technological innovation coexists with fragile regulatory mechanisms. This paper offers a critical appraisal of India's evolving legal and institutional framework for data protection against the backdrop of its socio-economic realities and digital ambitions. With the exponential growth of digital services, big data analytics, and AI-driven surveillance systems, concerns about individual privacy have become more urgent. The study critically examines the proposed and existing legal instruments, including the Information Technology Act and global influences like the GDPR, to highlight their conceptual, procedural, and enforcement limitations. Drawing from international comparisons, judicial precedents, and policy analyses, the paper argues that India's data protection regime must move beyond symbolic legalism to adopt a rights-based, transparent, and technologically adaptive framework. It advocates for stronger oversight mechanisms, citizen awareness programs, and privacy-enhancing technologies to balance the imperatives of individual rights and economic development.

Keywords: Data Protection, Online Privacy, Innovation, Surveillance, Indian Law.

Introduction

There has recently been a surge of interest in data protection and privacy rights issues involving the collection, storage, and use of vast quantities of personal information across the globe, primarily spurred by a significant rise in internet usage, proliferation of digital devices, and rapid growth of the information/knowledge economy worldwide, particularly in developing and emerging economies like India. Primarily because of the social, economic, and political power that result from technology, big data, the internet, and social media, after Saudi Arabia, China, Pakistan, the UAE, and Iran, the massive upsurge in the digital economy and associated political debate on right to information and individual privacy, which emboldened the civil-liberal age in many parts of the world, particularly in North America and Europe, has brought India into the limelight. In recent years, some civil society groups and judicial courts, particularly the Supreme Court, have taken a keen interest in internet privacy issues, particularly in the context of Aadhaar, a biometric and demographic database project initiated in 2009 to bring all Indian citizens under the aegis of a "unique identity" number and consequent biometric attendance in government offices and differential direct benefit transfers, which led to directives and public interest litigation owing to large scale data breaches and abuse, security concerns, and exclusion due to the unavailability of biometric "identifications."

Historical Context of Data Protection in India

The right to privacy has been accorded great significance by several countries in the world as it forms an essential component of individual liberty. The legitimacy of state interference with the fundamental rights of an individual is postulated on the principles of democracy, rule of law and constitutionalism. With a burgeoning tech-savvy populace and disruptive technology-driven start-ups, India has been hailed as the next hub of digital economy innovation.

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However, the unmitigated use of individual data by tech-intermediaries has drawn the ire of scholars, academics, media, and policy-makers alike. The issue of data protection is therefore one of great national importance (Basu, 2012). The approach has been to study the legislative developments, responses of other stakeholders, regarding data protection in India, and the objectives, limitations and extent of these legislative initiatives. Individual legislations and its limited application are now juxtaposed against the need for a comprehensive omni-bus legislation covering a common understanding of data, its processing by whom and its accountability.

Key Legislation Governing Data Privacy

The journey of Data Privacy Legislation in India

This part deals primarily with the analysis of the laws that govern the data protection and privacy issues in India and an attempt to understand how the country has evolved over the time on this aspect. The Information Technology Act, 2000, which aimed at e-commerce legislation in India, was created to replace the Intermediary Liability Rules, which do not acknowledge essential rights such as data protection and privacy within the law of India. Eventually, it is observed that in India, there is a legal void until now with reference to data protection, which affects individuals; in the present scenario also, one can refrain from approaching the Indian courts as there is no legislative framework to approach the judiciary as the area is unregulated. The researcher, therefore, attempts to discuss the comparison of legislation governing cyber privacy, with reference to the recent influential legislations in the United States of America (Sood, 2015).

Existing legislation in India

1. The IT Act, 2000: the commencement of e-commerce in India
2. The IT (Amendment) Bill, 2006: adding provision, protection and privacy of personal data
3. The Draft National Data Protection Bill 2011: protection and privacy of sensitive data
4. The Draft Data Protection Bill 2013 and 2018: recommendation and consultation with the stakeholders

Existing legislation in the United States

1. Fair Information Practice Principles (FIPPs): Employee privacy
2. Federal Privacy statute: Privacy legislation for financial services-related consumer information

Accountability Mechanisms for Businesses

In order to address data protection for individuals, the GDPR mandates a future proof, high standard of accountability to all data controllers. In a rapidly developing technological ecosystem, compliance with obligations is a key challenge that needs to be met. The WP29 views accountability from the perspective of the data protection officer in organisations and as a mere paper exercise, instead of a complex socio-technical job that needs to be done. An important part of the challenge of DP compliance by design is background work that incurs a wide range of artefacts. The background work does not stop at DP compliance by design, but is ongoing and evolves throughout the life cycle of an IoT product. Therefore, the WP29's understanding of accountability fails to see the importance of context, the granularity of accountability, and how to do accountability in practice (Crabtree et al., 2018). The GDPR mandates two kinds of accountability, viz. internal and external accountability. Internal accountability aims at controlling the responsible parties, whilst external accountability aims at disciplinary mechanisms that aim at governing behavioural compliance. In the practice of IoT development, accountability as control and assurance is often more or less obligatory internal development mechanisms, such as processes, procedures, documentation and monitoring measures to keep track of compliance as part of DP by design and default. Many of these mechanisms echo the existing requirements for data protection impact rankings. An important part of external accountability mechanisms for businesses include third-party audits and certifications, some of which are well established and some not yet developed, that assure DP compliance and operations. In order to address the wide range of control and assurance mechanisms needed to do accountability in practice, we developed a taxonomy of accountability mechanisms for businesses. To derive this taxonomy, we analysed how regulation translates into monitoring compliance. Here, the focus is on how external accountability mechanisms can be used to rank compliance regarding the access to and circulation of personal information (Urquhart et al., 2018).

Public Awareness and Individual Rights

Public awareness of online privacy rights is an essential requirement for the neutrality, fairness, and competence of any privacy legislation. Many published surveys and studies provide statistical evidence of the general population's privacy experiences, opinions, and emotions. Overall awareness is minimal in India, regarding both online

privacy rights and related data protection regulations. Responses are largely uninhibited due to ignorance of existing rights, as dramatic emotional responses may not get triggered for lack of knowledge (Sood, 2015)..

Understanding Data Rights

Data rights refer to a conceptual framework that treats data as an extension of existing human rights of individuals such as privacy, autonomy, and the free expression of ideas. In particular, data rights encompass individuals' rights to manage, control, and engage with their data. Data rights were first introduced as a response to growing concerns regarding behavioral and targeted advertising practices and their effects on privacy and public perception of online platforms. However, data rights can be more broadly interpreted to include rights to receive compensation for consumer generated data, or even the right to obtain a copy of data stored by an organization. Data rights are a specific and emerging category of rights akin to existing human rights.

Given that the concept of data rights is novel and in active development, an examination of the current practices and standards with respect to data rights is opportune. Relative to data rights ideals, what is their current state across jurisdictions, actors, procedures, and contexts? Which data rights are most frequently exercised? And which types of data rights are least appropriately addressed through existing regulation? Furthermore, are data rights being exercised equally among individual demographics? These questions endow the topic of data rights with intrinsic interest and broad significance, as achieving effective rights implementation will require an understanding of the current state of data rights enforcement.

Challenges in Enforcement of Data Protection Laws

Online information, especially information provided by users, is considered a top commodity in the web-fueled economy. Individuals willingly and thoughtlessly provide vast amounts of data, while local websites are supposed to enforce terms of use of foreign websites. India has resorted to do-nothing overzealousness about privacy and has therefore faced increasing chaos. How can a country with over 500 million Internet users protect its major assets—privacy and personal data against nefarious non-fair practices introduced by social networking sites, freely accessible public forums, and misuse by corporates in unwarranted e-marketing practices?

Protection against cyber crime is best handled as a concurrent subject as is done in developed democracies. However, such protection requires better

debate and articulation to be effective. Nevertheless, it is asserted that protecting privacy and personal data does not warrant new legislation but rather the amendment and strict enforcement of existing laws, bolstered by a better conceptual understanding of the phenomenon.

Resource Constraints

When it comes to an effective regime of protection against invasive information and surveillance technologies, resource constraints become a challenge, if not fatal, to the success of the regime. These constraints could be at various levels such as human, financial, technical, political and jurisdictional (Basu, 2012). First, a successful regime will require knowledgeable personnel grounded in the application and enforcement of rules and regulations. Another requirement will be a firm infrastructure capable of supporting privacy laws through enforcement and a dedicated body to supervise, monitor and refine its application. Third, a firm regime will have a commitment by the government to make privacy protection an integral part of broader governance frameworks as any compromise of such governance may be invited on the pretext of protecting, or surveilling for, security (Sood, 2015).

Fourth, multi-jurisdictional issues will need to be resolved and cooperation of online corporate entities will require more than legislative orders or financial threat. Fifth, in the world where freedom and security, privacy and policing are collaterals and are most sought countries such as India will always remain a soft state and every step given to protect privacy will be challenged by security arguments. These are not afterthoughts or irrelevant beside-the-point challenges but are core issues facing India's privacy regime, warranting urgent attention and discussion. The combination of a technically-savvy and politically-informed populous has favoured the development of digital rights in the developing world. On the whole, political governments have avoided sci-tech backlashes from home-grown technologies on a basis of non-interference.

However, this has resulted in the absence of a counterbalance against extreme corporate power that have a vested interest in controlling future science and technologies relating to privacy, genetic engineering, information consumption and generation. Ultimately, given the fact that privacy is a moving target and meritocracy will never be an all-around peaceful solution, there is the question how well each side of the marketing process can respond with fair adjustment to unpredictable technology-induced disputes.

Impact of Data Breaches on Individuals

In today's increasingly connected world, personal data are collected, used, and shared by entities large and small, individuals and institutions alike. Individuals' personal data have become the preferred currency for online services and usually this exchange is free. Still, a growing chorus of graduates, researchers, practitioners, and media organizations increasingly highlights invasive and reckless practices in the data economy. Digital surveillance has come to characterize many aspects of modern life and it has been caught abusing old systems and processes. Almost 390 million customers and account holders in the U.S. have been affected by a data breach since 2006. The growing sophistication, scale, speed, and impact of unauthorized access to sensitive personal data and other network security breaches constitute market failures that the free market recommends for regulation (L. Mills & Harclerode, 2018).

Psychological and Financial Consequences

Rising public concern about privacy abuses, large-scale data sharing, and increasingly intrusive online practices, particularly related to technology-based aspects of daily life, have motivated growing calls for stricter accountability measures for large internet platforms (Bondre et al., 2021). Alongside these concerns, the Covid-19 pandemic coincided with the rapid growth of online services heavily reliant on personal and behavioral data. There is therefore an opportunity to examine whether behavioral behavior across these platforms is consistent with larger policy considerations about ethical data subject rights and whether ongoing discussions about particular incidents or actors are unifying.

While the idea of "the right to be forgotten" (RTBF) has received the most widespread attention as part of the GDPR, the regulation outlines tighter constraints relative to user data and greater rights to algorithm understanding, explanation, and repercussions. Nevertheless, the enforcement of these rights is still in its infancy, and no nation yet offers the same protections as the GDPR. Moreover, it is understood that this sort of regulation on its own does not guarantee user data protection. A more inconvenient truth is that platforms may willingly enhance anti-competitive practices and harm data subject rights as they mature without external incentives to remain reasonably accountable. Nevertheless, constraints need not be purely punitive. More impactful regulation may be able to steer the trajectory of an industry toward preferred outcomes while retaining a multiplicity of actors and approaches. In amici briefs issued ahead of

the recent Supreme Court case on the right to be forgotten, noteworthy and notable privacy advocates argued that data protection could enhance the quality of knowledge production by enabling Q&A systems in news aggregative contexts.

The Role of Startups in the Data Economy

With the opening of data and massive data explosion, data has become the most important production factor alongside capital, land and labour. Governments and firms in both developing and developed countries have been clamouring to vigorously develop their own big data economy. In India, thousands of startups focusing on data collection, analysis and quasi-data brokering, particularly personal data brokering have mushroomed. As new comers of the digital economy, Indian startups are generally smaller in size and experience and therefore, likely feature data disadvantage towards larger, more resourceful and better reputed firms or incumbents. This leads to data privacy and data protection issues.

While the situations Indian startups face are similar to those of startups in other developing or under developed countries, the unique knowledge and socio-cultural immersions of these startups, are likely to greatly affect their approaches to data privacy and data protection. The consideration of data protection or privacy as disadvantages is also likely to be more profound in developing countries. While discussions have provided a number of insightful cases in the developed world, it still remains ambiguous: To what extent data protection and privacy frameworks or legal arrangements help or hinder the competition of Indian startups? And how do Indian startups cope with the challenges of data protection and privacy?.

Future Directions in Data Protection

Shifts towards datafication globally have revealed vulnerabilities in terms of the ongoing realization of human rights and civil liberties. Despite being seen as stealthy and transient, data is one of the most vital resources in the modern digital economy. Datafication has, however, acquired a negative connotation, indicating developments over time that impact society and peoples' lives in unexpected and often unanticipated negative ways. A wide range of practices associated with datafication — surveillance, privacy violation, social sorting, manipulation of behaviour, misinformation, and inequitable outcomes — have exacerbated existing inequalities and marginalized sections of society.

In short, trustworthiness has to be at the heart of datafication — in terms of all relevant actors being

prudent custodians of the data that they are collecting. This is especially vital for government actors collecting sensitive information as citizens are more vulnerable because they do not have options to opt-out. In principle, safety, security, and privacy are separate concerns. An open and transparent ecosystem is needed to elucidate and satisfy people's expectations in order to sustain the data economy in a way that is beneficial for humanity. This entails a trellising effort where individual rights are protected while innovation is enabled. This may mean reconceptualizing what it means for states to create and govern in order to avoid breaches of rights. Policy nuance is key. Foundational issues must be resolved first, and once the intentions of governments are rightly set, the devices of programmatic analysis can be questioned.

Potential Reforms in Legislation

Over the past decade, the public discourse on data protection and privacy in India has gained traction. The polar extremes of this discourse range from those who are overenthusiastic about the recent developments in technology and social media and are bent on posing data protection norms as archaic and antediluvian, while the others are sceptical of technology and are against any innovations that leverage technology over the fear of personal data breaches (Mann, 2015). Balancing the rights of an individual in terms of privacy and the protection of personal data, to be co-existing with the right to innovate and foster major economic growth from an entire industry which promises many times replicable revenue sources, is no easy task. The current regime in India with regard to online collection and processing of data is practically very vulnerable, porous and archaic. Essential legislation and enforcement mechanisms have not matured with the developments in the online world. Enactment of ITA 2000 is still seen as a watershed moment in India's entry into the Internet world, which was enacted more than a decade ago. However, the advancements in technology and the exponential growth

of the Internet in the past decade have left the conventional regime of online service delivery with many loopholes. Data privacy and protection has not been the prime concerns during the unplanned major developments with regard to the Internet in the past decade (M. Jr. Marsh, 2009). While the Indian Government is mulling over the enactment of a stricter data protection law, it is equally important to address loopholes in the existing laws in India which overlap with the domain of data privacy and protection.

Conclusion

The swift progress in science and technology has always served as an omen for the survival of humanity, giving rise to innovations, but only after a series of checklists. The extravagant use of technology has a price, too. Numerous critical issues related to the violation of individual rights fall under scrutiny while governing technology, especially in the digital sphere. The data-driven economy has led to benefits over innovation, enabling entities from the public and private sectors to intrude into individual rights, including an individual's right to privacy. The rephrasing of rights in a new era of technology has led the Supreme Court of India to examine data protection laws in the digital governance of government-initiated services. The Indian situation seems to deviate from other jurisdictions regulating data protection despite the endorsement of it as a human right. The analysis emphasizes the obstacles that have hampered the creation of privacy legislation despite multiple judicial pronouncements on the right to privacy. Besides that, the ambitions of the Digital India programme seem healthy for the nation's fledging economy driven by a blossoming information technology sector; however, implementing such programmes without a data protection framework seems asymmetric. This paper provides an elaborate analysis of the socially influencing factors, positioning the current situation in the context of privacy protection.

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Family Disputes and Dowry Cases : ADR Mechanisms, Need of Judicial Reform

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Abstract

Family disputes, particularly those arising from dowry demands, have increasingly burdened the Indian judicial system. Traditional litigation often intensifies conflicts rather than resolving them amicably. Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) mechanisms—such as mediation, arbitration, and conciliation—offer effective pathways to address such sensitive matters with empathy and efficiency. This paper explores the critical role ADR plays in de-escalating dowry-related disputes and highlights the urgent need for judicial reforms to strengthen these mechanisms. A reformed approach would not only expedite justice but also promote social harmony by reducing adversarial confrontations. Emphasizing accessibility, fairness, and timely resolution, the study advocates for a robust integration of ADR in family law practices. The evolving legal landscape necessitates reforms that are sensitive to the socio-cultural realities while ensuring the protection of vulnerable individuals.

Keywords : Family disputes, Dowry cases, ADR, Mediation, Judicial reforms

Introduction

Family disputes in India, particularly those stemming from dowry-related issues, have become a pressing concern for both the legal system and society at large. Despite decades of legislative interventions aimed at curbing the dowry menace, the persistence of such cases reflects deeply entrenched socio-cultural norms and systemic inadequacies. The traditional approach to resolving these disputes—through adversarial court proceedings—often exacerbates familial tensions, prolongs emotional and financial distress, and fails to deliver timely justice. Moreover, the overwhelming burden on the Indian judiciary has led to significant delays, thereby diminishing public confidence in the justice delivery system.

This paper aims to explore the intersection of dowry-related family disputes and ADR mechanisms in India, while critically examining the urgent need for judicial reforms to support and expand the use of ADR in such cases. By emphasizing the role of empathy, cultural sensitivity, and procedural efficiency, the study underscores the potential of ADR to transform the landscape of family justice in India.

Understanding Dowry and Its Legal Implications in India

The practice of dowry, deeply rooted in Indian society, involves the transfer of money, goods, or property from the bride's family to the groom or his family as a precondition of marriage. Despite its historical justification as a voluntary gift, in modern times, dowry has often become a coercive demand, leading to exploitation, domestic violence, and even deaths of women. The Dowry Prohibition Act, 1961 was enacted as a landmark legislation to curb this social evil by criminalizing both the giving and taking of dowry. The Act defines 'dowry' means any property or valuable security given or agreed to be given either directly or indirectly in by one party to the other party to the marriage, which is punishable under

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Section 3 and Section 4 of the Act. In addition to the Dowry Prohibition Act, several provisions of the Indian Penal Code have been invoked to address dowry-related violence. Section 498A IPC specifically deals with cruelty by the husband or his relatives, which includes harassment for dowry demands. Furthermore, Section 304B IPC relates to dowry deaths, prescribing stringent punishment if a woman dies under unnatural circumstances within seven years of marriage and soon before her death, she was subjected to dowry-related cruelty or harassment shortly before her death .

Moreover, the adversarial nature of litigation frequently turns the courtroom into a battleground, causing further trauma for women who are already victims of violence. In many instances, the prolonged legal process does not yield effective remedies but instead worsens the familial conflict. It is also worth noting that there have been concerns about the misuse of Section 498A IPC, with allegations that some complaints are filed with the intention of harassing the husband and his family. The Supreme Court, in *Rajesh Sharma v. State of U.P.*, expressed concern over the indiscriminate arrests and the need for safeguards to prevent abuse of the law. While such misuse does not undermine the necessity of protective legislation, it highlights the complexity of balancing legal accountability with procedural fairness in family disputes.

Definitions and Legal Context

Family disputes cover legal conflicts arising among relatives, spouses or couples – typically matrimonial issues (divorce, judicial separation, and restitution of conjugal rights, validity of marriage, maintenance, and custody of children) and related property or domestic matters. The Family Courts Act, 1984 was created “to help people in family and marriage disputes resolve their disagreements peacefully and quickly”. Under that Act, Family Courts have jurisdiction over divorce, annulment, maintenance, custody, inheritance and related disputes.

Dowry cases involve the illegal demands, taking or giving of dowry – defined by the Dowry Prohibition Act, 1961 as any property or valuable things given (directly or indirectly) by the bride’s family to the groom (or vice versa) at or before marriage, or even after marriage “in connection with” the marriage. Section 3 of the Act makes giving or taking dowry, a criminal offence (punishable by 5+ years’ imprisonment and fine). In practice, many dowry disputes become criminal cases under IPC

Sections 498A (cruelty by husband/relatives, punishable up to 3 years) and 304B (dowry death, punishable by life imprisonment). The Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act, 2005 and CrPC Section 125 (maintenance) also touch on marital violence and support claims often linked to dowry disputes. Thus, family-law statutes (like the Hindu Marriage Act, 1955 and Special Marriage Act, 1954), criminal laws (Dowry Act, IPC) and procedural laws (CPC, Criminal Procedure) together form the legal framework for these disputes.

Challenges in The Judiciary

Family and dowry cases burden Indian courts with complex challenges. A huge backlog looms large: as of Feb 2025, district courts had 4.60 crore pending cases nationwide (nearly half over 3 years old) – and many are family cases. Courts also face a shortage of judges, with a 27% vacancy in judicial posts. Victims (especially women) may avoid litigation due to social stigma and costs; one report notes that the “stigma associated with legal battles in domestic violence and dowry disputes prevents women from approaching the judiciary”.

Alternative Dispute Resolution Mechanism

Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) offers non-judicial paths to settle disputes. ADR methods like mediation, conciliation, arbitration, negotiation and Lok Adalat – are designed to be faster, cheaper and more flexible than litigation. The Constitution’s Directive Principles emphasize the goal of speedy justice, and ADR aligns with that vision. The Civil Procedure Code (Sec. 89, now Order X Rule 1-A CPC) explicitly authorizes courts to refer civil and matrimonial disputes to ADR methods when settlement seems possible. In 2024, the government noted that Section 89 “recognises Arbitration, Conciliation, Mediation and Judicial Settlement including Lok Adalat” and mandates court referral when a compromise is feasible. The new Mediation Act, 2021 (effective 2023) even allows courts to refer compoundable matrimonial offences (e.g. IPC 498A cruelty) to mediation, provided the parties agree.

Under the Family Courts Act 1984, courts are legally required to try to reconcile the parties. Section 9(1) states that “endeavour shall be made in the first instance to assist and persuade the parties in arriving at a settlement”. Similarly, the Hindu Marriage Act (s. 23) directs that before granting any relief, the court “make every endeavour to bring about reconciliation” between spouses. Common ADR modes in family dowry contexts include:

- **Mediation and Conciliation:** A neutral mediator (or conciliator) helps the spouses or family members negotiate terms (e.g. divorce settlement, alimony, asset division, or return of dowry gifts). Mediators focus on communication and mutual agreement. Mediation need not involve lawyers and is strictly confidential. Because it is voluntary and private, parties often feel safe expressing needs.
- **Arbitration:** While rare in family matters, couples can agree to arbitrate certain disputes (like property division) under the Arbitration & Conciliation Act, 1996. An arbitrator's award is binding enforceable just like a court decree. .
- **Lok Adalat:** Established under the Legal Services Authorities Act 1987, Lok Adalat are statutory conciliatory forums that can take up pending or the pre-litigation stage. Lok Adalat frequently organize special drives (e.g. National Lok Adalat) to settle large numbers of family and maintenance cases in bulk.
- **Nari Adalat (Women's Courts):** These are community-based women's courts (part of the Mission Shakti initiative) that mediate local disputes. Typically composed of trained local women ("Nyaya Sakhi"), Nari Adalat handle issues like domestic violence, dowry harassment and inheritance claims at the grassroots level. The WCD Ministry, under Mission Shakti, has piloted Nari Adalat in village panchayats – in 2023–24 over 1,000 meetings led to 497 registered cases– providing an accessible ADR option in rural areas.
- **Counselling and Court Settlement Programs:** Family courts often have family welfare committees or panel counsellors who seek to reconcile spouses. Initiatives like mandatory pre-divorce counselling or court-annexed mediation (under judicial supervision) fall under this approach.

These ADR methods contrast with litigation. As Justice M.R. Shah observed, "When a plant is tender, you can mould it. But if a dispute goes to court, there will be difficulty in settling it... it will save cost, time and relationship among parties". In other words, nurturing a resolution early (through ADR) preserves relationships better than adversarial trials.

Effectiveness of ADR in Family/Dowry Contexts

Empirical data indicate that ADR is widely used and often successful in family matters. A Vidhi Centre study (cited in Mapping ADR) found that out of 46,000 court-referred mediations, 41,503 (90%) were

family disputes. In 2011–2015 alone, over 25,000 matrimonial and maintenance cases (about 80% of all mediations) were referred to court-connected mediation. It includes petitions under the Dowry Act, maintenance, Domestic Violence Act, Guardianship Act, divorce and related cases. This large share reflects that parties and courts increasingly turn to ADR in domestic cases.

Studies of Nari Adalat (a form of ADR) report high "success" rates. For example, one UP study found 65% of cases handled by Nari Adalat were resolved without formal litigation. Government reports confirm that many women prefer the non-adversarial Nari Adalat, finding its mediations more timely, affordable and fair compared to court trials. In Gujarat, for instance, over 400 Nari Adalat achieved a 75% resolution rate in women's cases. By contrast, similar disputes take 2–5 years in regular courts but only 3–6 months in Nari Adalat.

Advantages of ADR include speed, lower cost and confidentiality. Mediation can conclude in a single day (with follow-ups) versus years of litigation. It keeps family matters private (citing *Moti Ram v. Ashok Kumar*, Indian courts emphasize confidential ADR for sensitive issues). Lok Adalat settle tens of thousands of cases in one day, and their awards – though final – often reflect compromise and cooperation.

However, ADR has limitations in family cases. It cannot legally resolve non-compoundable offenses like dowry death (IPC 304B) or serious cruelty; such cases must proceed in court. Since ADR (except Lok Adalat) is generally voluntary, either side can walk away, forcing litigation.

Overall, case studies suggest that well-structured ADR can produce durable resolutions. For instance, through a Nari Adalat a woman in Patna successfully reclaimed a rejected dowry gift, and in Varanasi another secured alimony and child custody via mediation.

Need for Judicial Reform

First, the shortfall of specialized courts and personnel must be addressed. Currently only 848 family courts exist for 1.4 billion people (covering a fraction of districts), leading to over 12 lakh pending family cases nationwide. Legal scholars urge creation of many more Family Courts staffed with "trained counsellors, mediators... and specialist family law judges" to form a multi-disciplinary team capable of ADR. Increasing judicial vacancies (filling the 27% gap) and adding evening or fast-track benches for matrimonial cases (as the Law Ministry proposes)

would also cut delays.

Second, the ADR framework needs strengthening. The government has already enacted laws (CPC 89, Mediation Act) and policies (Mission Shakti's Nari Adalat) to promote ADR. These should be fully implemented: for example, making family mediation mandatory in tribunals and recognizing mediated settlements in dowry/maintenance cases. Lok Adalat should regularly host special matrimonial sessions.

Third, procedural reform is needed. Provisions like Hindu Marriage Act Section 23 and Family Courts Act Section 9 already require efforts at conciliation, but in practice judges do not always enforce them. Use of technology – online mediation platforms, virtual family hearings, and digital monitoring of settlements – could make dispute resolution more accessible.

Fourth, legal aid and protection must be expanded. Many litigants are poor and unaware of ADR options. Strengthening free legal services and conducting awareness campaigns about family counselling or

Lok Adalat can improve uptake.

Finally, expert guidance and jurisprudence should evolve. High courts and the Supreme Court have repeatedly noted that “family matters should not be litigated in any court unless of an extraordinary grave nature; they should be amicably resolved”. Judicial policy should embody this. Law commissions have long recommended instituting mandatory ADR for matrimonial disputes.

Conclusion

In my conclusion, comprehensive reform – expanding specialized courts, mandating ADR, easing procedures, and resourcing support – is needed to make justice in family and dowry cases faster, fairer and more humane. As one senior judge aptly put it, resolving disputes early “will save cost, time and [preserve] relationships among parties”. By combining ADR mechanisms with targeted judicial reforms, India can better uphold the interests of families and vulnerable spouses alike.

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Relevance of Dr. B.R. Ambedkar's Social Justice in Contemporary Age

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Abstract

Through this research I attempt to understand and discuss the new political structure with special emphasis on the scenario of the Dr. B.R. Ambedkar and his Social Justice in India. Social Justice being a multi-dimensional concept has been viewed by scholars of Law, Philosophy, Political Science and History differently. The term social Justice is quite comprehensive. Social Justice is a bundle of rights, it is balancing wheel between haves and have not. It is a great social value in providing a stable society and in securing the unity of the country. In general, Social Justice may be defined as "the right of the weak, aged, destitute, poor, women, children and other under-privileged persons." Justice is a matter of social conflict. In a one-person world, justice is pointless. It is only when people interact and their Interests collide that justice enters the scene. In this sense, the very concept of "social" Justice is ill-defined since Justice is always a social issue, the attribute "social" must take on special connotations if any meaning at all is to be given to the term "social Justice."

Key Words: *Dr. B.R. Ambedkar; Privileged Persons, Social Justice.*

Introduction

At the end of the nineteenth century, when the term "social Justice" came to prominence, it was first used as an appeal to the ruling classes to attend to the needs of the new masses of uprooted peasants who had become urban workers. Theorizing about social Justice became a major concern in the early years of the twentieth century, and the first book actually called Social Justice was published in New York in 1900. Its author was Westel Willoughby, a professor of political science at Johns Hopkins University who was influenced by the late idealist philosophy of the school of T.H. Green. According to John Rawls,¹ the concept of social Justice is "all social primary goods—liberty and opportunity, income and wealth, and the basis of self-respect are to be distributed equally unless an unequal distribution of any or all of these goods is to the advantage of the least favoured." The contents of the "social primary goods" specified by Rawls are of particular importance, for the fair distribution of them, namely, liberty and opportunity, income and wealth and basis of self-respect in a society will undoubtedly help to achieve the much needed social Justice.

The term "social Justice" was first used in 1840 by a Sicilian priest, Luigi Taparelli d'Azeglio, and given prominence by Antonio Rosmini-Serbati in *La Costituzione Civile Secondo la Giustizia Sociale* in 1848. Later, British authors such as John Stuart Mill, Leslie Stephen and Henry Sidgwick referred from time to time to social Justice, although without marking it off sharply from distributive Justice generally.²

The concept of social Justice is closely linked with human rights as envisaged by the United Nations in its 1948 declaration and fundamental rights as provided in the Constitution of India but they are not synonymous. Fundamental rights, i.e. the right to freedom and equality, the right against exploitation, and right to constitutional remedies, etc. are essential for the free and natural development of

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the human personality and hence are the backbone of a just social order but they are subject to control or limits if they adversely affect the pattern of social justice in society. Social Justice encompasses economic justice. It is the virtue which guides us in creating those organized human interactions which we call institutions. Social justice is also equated with equality, liberty and dignity; which mean that all three are essential for social justice and that denial of any one of them is a denial of justice. Dignity is generally coterminous with freedom and equality.³ An illiterate, poor and ill fed person is hardly said to have any dignity.

The concept of social justice has been enshrined in the Indian Constitution. The fathers of the Indian Constitution had the dream of a new social, economic and political order, the soul of which was social justice. Dr. Ambedkar was the chief architect of the Indian Constitution. He was fully aware of the pattern and problems of the society and their conflicting interests. The Constitution is a monumental example of social engineering.⁴ Social justice is not defined in the Indian Constitution but it is relative concept taking in its wings the time and circumstances, the people their backwardness, blood, sweat and tears. Justice is very complex concept as it has a number of sources (as example religion, nature economics needs an ethics) and dimensions. It has been examined by different people from different view points within the limits of the time, place and circumstances they lived in. Social justice is one of the dimensions of the concept of justice which stands for organization society based on the principle of equality, liberty and fraternity. Its greater emphasis is on the principles of equality both social and economic and fraternity with a view to create such human social condition which ensure free and fair development of all human beings. As such, the concept of social justice sometimes require unequal or preferential treatment for, certain sections of population, who have been deprived of certain 'values' for ages, with a view to bring them on an equal footing with the other sections of population.⁵ After independence, India received only political freedom "social and economic freedom" was yet to be fought. Because feudal hijacked the economic freedom in their favour, fate of Scheduled Castes remained hanging on the peg of reservation, so that neither they should economically grow nor they should revolt against the non-fulfillment of social justice. Thus social justice is not yet reaches to the Scheduled Caste people in India even today who are subjected to recurrence of killing, burning and gang rape of their women folk. Many people question,

why do Scheduled Castes not fight against such atrocities done to them? How can they fight with empty stomach against feudal-land lords who are rich and resourceful, police and courts are also hand in glove with them, therefore, the social justice still beyond their reach even after 69 years of independence.⁶

The Constitution of India brings a renaissance in the concept of social justice when it weaves a trinity of it in the preamble, the fundamental rights, and the directive principles of state policies and this trinity is the "the core of the commitments to the social revolution. This is the conscience of the Constitution. The preamble of the Indian Constitution is the mirror of social justice. It provides social, economic and political justice to the citizen of sovereign, socialist, secular, democratic, republic of India. The first task of the Assembly was to formulate the objectives and the guiding principles of Indian Constitution. Therefore the resolution of the preamble and objective of the Constitution was discussed in the Constituent Assembly for nine days from December 13 to 19 and January 20 and 22 of 1947. Before the actual work of the constituent Assembly had commenced in full seeing, Dr. Ambedkar proposed a memorandum on 15 March 1947 entitled "States and minorities".⁷ What are their rights and how to secure them in the Constitution of free India? This proposed explained the aspect of social justice for minorities in free India. Although no cognizance was taken on this memorandum on the ground of academic interest. However, feeling expressed by Dr. Ambedkar in this memorandum was special to protect the minorities and weaker section.⁸ Besides, the proposed memorandum submitted, he was himself presided the meeting of draft for the preamble of the Constitution.

Dr. Ambedkar's concept of social justice stands for the liberty, equality and fraternity of all human beings. He stood for a social system which is based on right relations between man and man in all spheres of life. For the proper grasp of Dr. Ambedkar's concepts of social justice, one has to go through his view about religion particularly Hindu religion which is the source of exploitation and injustice. His concept of social justice is closely connected with his concept of religion and morality. Dr. Ambedkar was not closely connected with his concept of religion and morality. Dr. Ambedkar was not an atheist.⁹ He was a religious minded man. He writes "It pains me to see youths growing indifferent to religion. Religion is not an opium as it is held by some. What good things I have in me or whatever have been the benefits of my education to society, I owe them to the religious

feelings in me". But the religion which he conceives is a rationale ethical spiritual and humanitarian and full of 'Karuna'. It is a religion which grants equality and treats all its believers equal. To him, the religion which discriminates between tow fellows is a partial religion. The religion which treats crores of its adherents worse than dogs and criminal and inflicts upon the insufferable disabilities is no religion at all. DrAmbedkar a rationalist and humanist did not approve any type of hypocrisy, injustice and exploitation of man by man in the name of religion. He stood for a religion which is based on universal principles of morality and is applicable to all times, to all countries and to all races. It must be in accord with reason and must be based on the basic tents of liberty, equality and fraternity.¹⁰ He was highly dissatisfied with Hinduism as it gives no support to principle of social unity and believes in social separation and discrimination.

According to Ambedkar, the term "social justice" is based upon equality, liberty and fraternity of all human beings. The aim of social justice is to remove all kinds of inequalities based upon Caste, race, sex, power, Position, and wealth. The social justice brings equal distribution of the social, political and economic resources of the community. Ambedkar was the chief architect of the Indian Constitution. He was fully aware of the pattern and problems of the Indian society. The aspirations of the different sections of the society and their conflicting interests. He tried to achieve social justice and social democracy in terms of one man-one value. He treated social justice as a true basis for patriotism and nationalism. Ambedkar did not accept the theories of social justice as propounded by the Varna system,¹¹ the Aristotelian order, Plato's scheme, Gandhiansarvoday order and not even the proletarian socialism of Marx.

Dr. Ambedkar wanted to reform and restrictive the Hindu social system which ascribes status to man on the basis of his birth in a particular low or high caste. In this social system. Individual's personal achievements have no value and his status is treated as divinely ordained. He stood for a social system in which man's status is based on his merit and achievement and where no one is noble or untouchables because of his birth.¹² He stood for society where human beings live a human life based on the principle of liberty, equality and fraternity. He stood for a social system where the liberty of an individual is to slavery of his fellow being. He advocated the policy of preferential treatment for the socially oppressed and economically exploited people of the country. The Constitution of India, which was

drafted under his chairmanship, contains a number of provisions which enjoins the state to secure to all its citizens justice, social economic and political, along with liberty, equality and fraternity. It also contains a number of provisions which guarantee a preferential treatment to the down-trodden people in various sectors or life. Dr. Ambedkar was really interested in the welfare of the down-trodden people of the country, because instead of accepting any assignment abroad he preferred to live amidst them. He was really the savior of the down-trodden people in Indian.¹³

TheSupreme Court has explained the concept of social justice i.e. "the Constitution commands justice, liberty, equality and fraternity as supreme values to usher in the egalitarian social, economic and political democracy". Social justice, equality and dignity of persons are corner stones of social democracy. The concept of "social justice" which the Constitution of India engrafted consists of diverse principles essential for the orderly growth and development personality of every citizen.⁵⁴Social justice is thus an integral part of justice in the generic sense. Justice is a genus of which social justice is one of its species. Social justice is a dynamic device to mitigate the suffering of the poor, weak, Dalits, Tribes and deprived sections of the society. This indeed is social justice guaranteed by the Constitution of India because it strives to create a "balancing wheel between freedom, political and economic indeed, makes the survival of democracy" Dr.Ambedkar concluded the debate on the preamble in these words."I say that this preamble embodies what is the desire of every member of the house that this Constitution should have its roots its authority, its sovereignty from the people, that it has.¹⁴Part III of the Constitution as fundamental rights is related to the social justice. The fundamental rights inculcate the sense of reconstruction and foster social revolution by generating equality amongst all, prohibiting discrimination on the grounds of Caste, religion, sex, creed, place of birth, abolishing untouchability and making its practice punishable by law, banning trafficking in human beings and forced labour. Moreover, the Indian Constitution has empowered the states to make special provisions for the advancement of any socially, educationally backward classes and also for the Scheduled Caste and Scheduled Tribes.¹⁵These provisions of the fundamental rights of the Constitution are related to the real concept of social justice.

Ambedkar was concerned with man, his status and well-being in this world man is centre of his thoughts and action. Men are the masters of their fate they are

also captains of their souls. He says, “we will attain self-elevation only if we can learn self-help, regain our self-respect and gain self-knowledge”, According to Dr. Ambedkar, “the belief in soul is also unprofitable as the belief in God because it not only creates priesthood but it gives priesthood complete control over man from birth to death”. He also rejected the theory of past karma which holds that man take birth in a rich family because of his past good karma. It is a dangerous doctrine as it creates a mentality which makes man helpless and hopeless.¹⁶ Dr. Ambedkar was dead against the Hindu Caste structure as he was of the view that this structure has been primarily responsible for committing all sorts of atrocities on the various sections of the society particularly the weaker sections Scheduled Caste and Scheduled Tribes. He was against Manusmriti as it gives a blank Cheque to the Brahmins to commit all sorts of atrocities on Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes and justify their evil designs.¹⁷ In this regard at the time of constituent Assembly debate Dr. Ambedkar expressed his views that “All of us desire that this unfortunate class could be entitled to the same privileges as members of the other Communities without any let or hindrance from anybody. He recreated that if any community or person will violate this provision it will impose duty on the state to stop such violation through the law, because the Constitution contains ample provisions. The important part of the Social justice is the part IV of the Constitution as directive principles of state of policy. Although this part of Constitution is not enforceable by any court. However the principles laid down there are nevertheless fundamental in the governance of the country and it shall be the duty of the state to apply these principles in making laws. In this regard Dr. Ambedkar Said “It is not the intention to introduce in this part these principles as more pious declarations.¹⁸

It is the intention of the assembly that in future both the legislature and the executive should not merely pay lip service these principles enacted in this part but that should be made the basis of all executive and legislative action that may be taken hereafter in the matter of the governance of the country”. The ideology of the Dr. Ambedkar influenced the Indian judiciary on the basis of this ideology supreme court of India declared that directive principles of state policy are enforceable with the fundamental rights.¹⁹ Dr. Ambedkar was a social reformer. He stoically suffered the humiliation of his birth and was determined to redeem the Scheduled Castes by the sacrifice of his life. Poverty, misrepresentation,

jealousy, scandals and even threats of violence had not deterred him from his chosen path. His whole life was a sage of sacrifice for the cause of the downtrodden. Dr. Ambedkar stood for the independence of the country. While he stood like a rock in the cause of the backward communities, he did not fall a prey to blandishments of power or manoeuvres of the enemies of the country.²⁰ He was a great patriot who fought for the Scheduled Castes without sacrificing the wider interest of the nation. Dr. Ambedkar’s undoubted talents had been fully utilized by the nation. The nation was poorer for this default. A nation which neglects brilliance and encourage mediocrity, discourages intellectual honesty and courage of conviction but favours courtiers and yes-men, is bounded to go caliber had been in charge of the constructive activities of our country. Every Hindu must learn a lesson from the life of Dr. Ambedkar. The blackest spot in Hindu religion is the action of the doctrine of Untouchability. It has become a hereditary sin of every Hindu.²¹ It is not enough that the Constitution has redeemed his sin by going all out to eradicate this stigma from Hinduism.”

Dr. Ambedkar’s greatest contribution to our social and political life has been that he made the socially-oppressed sections like the Scheduled Castes to challenge the social orthodoxy, with the piercing questions which Abraham Lincoln had asked, “It might be in your interest to be our masters, but how is it in our interest to be your slaves?” To the extent this question finds its echoes in the remotest corners of India with the requisite follow-up action,²² Dr. Ambedkar’s life-long dream of ensuring social liberation of the oppressed and the downtrodden will be translated into reality.

Conclusion

Dr. Ambedkar’s social vision is reflective in his own words. As an economic system permits exploitation without obligation untouchability is not only a system of unmitigated economic exploitation, but it is also a system of uncontrolled economic exploitation.¹⁹ That is because there is no independent public opinion to condemn it and there is no impartial machinery of administration to restrain it, there is no check from the police or the judiciary for the simple reasons that they are all down from the Hindus, and take side of exploiters. The contents of Ambedkar’s concept of social justice included unity and equality of all human beings, equal worth of men and women, respect for the weak and the lowly, regard for human rights, benevolence, mutual love,

sympathy, tolerance and charity towards fellow being. Humane treatment in all cases dignity of all citizens, abolition of Caste distinctions, education and property for all and good will and gentleness, He emphasized more on fraternity and emotional integration. His view on social justice was to remove man-made inequalities of all shades through law, morality and public conscience, he stood for justice for a sustainable society. According to Dr. Ambedkar the root cause of social injustice to the Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes is the Caste system in Hindu society.¹⁷ He observed, Castes are enclosed units and it is their conspiracy with clear conscience that

compels the ex-communicated to make them into a Caste.

The logic of their obdurate circumstance in merciless and it is in obedience to its force that some unfortunate groups find themselves closed out with the result that now groups by a mechanical law are constantly being converted into Castes in a widening multiplicity.¹⁸ He further maintained that the root of untouchability is the Caste system and the root of the Caste system is religion, the root of the religion attached to varnashram and the root of the varnashram is the Brahminism, the root of Brahminism lies with the political power.

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युवा न्याय की दिशा : अपराध से निपटने में किशोर न्यायालयों की भूमिका और सुधार का विश्लेषण

सारांश

यह पत्र किशोर न्याय प्रणाली का एक व्यापक विश्लेषण प्रदान करता है, जिसमें युवा अपराध को संबोधित करने में किशोर न्यायालयों के विकास, कार्य और सुधार पर जोर दिया गया है। पुनर्वास के आदर्श से उत्पन्न, किशोर न्यायालयों को युवा अपराधियों के साथ वयस्कों से अलग व्यवहार करने के लिए डिज़ाइन किया गया था, जो सज़ा के बजाय देखभाल पर ध्यान केंद्रित करते थे। हालाँकि, समय के साथ, दंडात्मक उपायों ने प्रणाली में तेजी से घुसपैठ की है, जिससे इसके मूलभूत सिद्धांतों से समझौता हुआ है। समकालीन किशोर न्यायालयों को महत्वपूर्ण चुनौतियों का सामना करना पड़ता है, जैसे कि प्रणालीगत पूर्वाग्रह, प्रक्रियागत असंगतताएँ और अपर्याप्त मानसिक स्वास्थ्य संसाधन। मुख्य हितधारकों-न्यायाधीशों, परिवीक्षा अधिकारियों, परिवारों और सामुदायिक संगठनों की भूमिकाओं का विश्लेषण किया जाता है, जिससे सिस्टम लक्ष्यों और वास्तविक प्रथाओं के बीच वियोग का पता चलता है। अंत में, यह एक अधिक न्यायसंगत और प्रभावी किशोर न्याय प्रणाली को बढ़ावा देने में माता-पिता की भागीदारी, शिक्षा, वकालत और प्रणालीगत सुधार के महत्व को रेखांकित करता है। अनुभवजन्य शोध, नीति विश्लेषण और अंतरराष्ट्रीय सर्वोत्तम प्रथाओं का उपयोग करके, यह अध्ययन एक युवा-केंद्रित दृष्टिकोण की वकालत करता है।

कीवर्ड : किशोर न्याय, युवा अपराध, पुनर्वास, पुनर्स्थापनात्मक न्याय, न्यायालय सुधार।

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परिचय

वा न्याय प्रणाली वयस्क न्याय प्रणाली से अलग है। शुरुआती किशोर न्यायालय पश्चिमी यूरोप में प्रचलित पितृसत्तात्मक और अनौपचारिक मॉडल पर आधारित थे। पहला विशेष किशोर न्यायालय 1899 में शिकागो में स्थापित किया गया था, और जल्द ही पूरे अमेरिका में फैल गया। शुरू में राज्य का हस्तक्षेप केवल विशिष्ट अपराधों पर आधारित था, लेकिन बाद में यह युवाओं की स्थिति (जैसे उपेक्षा, गरीबी) पर भी आधारित हो गया। किशोर न्यायालयों ने बच्चों के साथ वयस्कों से अलग व्यवहार किया, और पारंपरिक कानूनी सुरक्षा उपायों (जैसे वकील, जूरी परीक्षण, आदि) को किशोरों के लिए अनुपयुक्त माना गया।

परिवीक्षा जांचकर्ताओं और न्यायालयों की सिफारिशों में विविधता थी, जो अपराध के प्रति अलग-अलग दृष्टिकोण को दर्शाती थी। कुछ न्यायाधीशों और अधिकारियों ने अपराध को सामाजिक परिस्थितियों का परिणाम माना और पुनर्वास पर जोर दिया, जबकि अन्य ने दंडात्मक दृष्टिकोण अपनाया, युवाओं को केवल नियंत्रण की आवश्यकता के रूप में देखा। जिन्हें औपचारिक रूप से "अपराधी" माना जाता था, उन्हें पुनर्वास के रूप में नहीं देखा जाता था।

"देखभाल की जरूरत वाले बच्चों" बच्चों को तकनीकी अपराधी माना जाता था और उनके अधिकार सीमित थे। अन्य विकल्प उपलब्ध होने पर भी उन्हें आश्रय गृहों या हिरासत केंद्रों में रखा जाना आम बात थी। परिवीक्षा जांच व्यापक और मनमानी थी, जिसमें घर के दौरे, रिकॉर्ड जांच और सामाजिक इतिहास के माध्यम से बच्चे की मानसिक, शारीरिक, पारिवारिक और सामाजिक स्थिति का विवरण एकत्र किया जाता था।

किशोर न्यायालयों का ऐतिहासिक अवलोकन

किशोर न्यायालयों की भूमिका को समझने के लिए उनके विकास के इतिहास को जानना ज़रूरी है। 1899 में इलिनोइस में स्थापित पहला किशोर न्यायालय वयस्क न्याय प्रणाली से मौलिक रूप से अलग और क्रांतिकारी था। यह इस विश्वास पर आधारित था कि बचपन वयस्कता से एक अलग अवस्था है, और बच्चों को उनकी अपरिपक्वता के कारण विशेष सुरक्षा और मार्गदर्शन की आवश्यकता होती है। इस न्यायालय का कामकाज अनौपचारिक, गोपनीय और पुनर्वास-उन्मुख था। न्यायाधीश एक अभिभावक की तरह

¹रिसर्च स्कॉलर, तीर्थकर महावीर विश्वविद्यालय, मुरादाबाद।

²प्राचार्य, टीएमसीएलएलएस, तीर्थकर महावीर विश्वविद्यालय, मुरादाबाद।

काम करते थे, जो बच्चे के सर्वांगीण विकास के लिए पुनर्वास योजनाएँ बनाते थे।

बचपन को एक सामाजिक रूप से निर्मित अवधारणा के रूप में देखते हुए, विकलांग या अपराधी युवाओं के संदर्भ में इसका स्वरूप भिन्न होता है। बाल संरक्षण आंदोलन और किशोर न्यायालयों ने मुख्य रूप से इस "विकृत बचपन" को नियंत्रित करने और अपराध को रोकने पर ध्यान केंद्रित किया, न कि बच्चों को अपराध से बचाने के तरीके खोजने पर। इस अवधारणा ने किशोर न्यायालय को एक आदर्श और स्थायी संस्था के रूप में स्थापित किया। 20वीं सदी की शुरुआत में, समाज ने किशोरों और न्यायालयों को सामाजिक परिवर्तनों से बचाने की कोशिश की, जो युवा अपराध के बारे में समाज की शुरुआती सोच को दर्शाता है।

युवा न्याय में सैद्धांतिक रूपरेखाएँ

न्याय के सिद्धांत यह समझने के लिए एक रूपरेखा प्रदान करते हैं कि युवा अपराध का सबसे अच्छा जवाब कैसे दिया जाए। वकीलों, मनोवैज्ञानिकों और सामाजिक कार्यकर्ताओं द्वारा प्रस्तुत इन सिद्धांतों का लगातार विश्लेषण किया जाता है और अदालत और शिक्षा जगत में उन्हें चुनौती दी जाती है। ये सिद्धांत अक्सर ओवरलैप होते हैं, जिससे व्यावहारिक समझ जटिल हो जाती है। दंड के उद्देश्य और औचित्य अपराध विज्ञान में सबसे विवादास्पद विषयों में से एक हैं। पिछले 30 वर्षों में, दंडात्मक प्रतिक्रियाओं की आलोचनात्मक जांच बढ़ती जा रही है। प्राचीन काल से ही दंड को न्याय व्यवस्था का अंग माना जाता रहा है, लेकिन युवा अपराध के संदर्भ में इसे उतनी गंभीरता से नहीं लिया गया है। जबकि युवाओं की मानसिक, भावनात्मक और संज्ञानात्मक अपरिपक्वता उन्हें वयस्कों की तुलना में कम दोषी और अधिक कमजोर बनाती है, दंडात्मक प्रतिक्रियाएँ अभी भी हावी हैं। युवा न्याय व्यवस्था में नस्लीय, जातीय और लिंग आधारित पूर्वाग्रह भी मौजूद हैं, जो नीति और व्यवहार के बीच असंतुलन को दर्शाते हैं। इसलिए, केवल गंभीर अपराधों पर ध्यान केंद्रित करने के बजाय, सभी प्रकार के युवा अपराध को समग्र दृष्टिकोण से देखना आवश्यक है।

1. पुनर्स्थापनात्मक न्याय सिद्धांत

पुनर्स्थापनात्मक न्याय एक प्राचीन दर्शन है जिसका आधुनिक अपराधिक न्याय में उपयोग बढ़ रहा है। इसका उद्देश्य अपराधी को केवल दंडित करने के बजाय अपराध के परिणामस्वरूप होने वाले नुकसान को समझना और उसकी मरम्मत करना है। यह दृष्टिकोण मानता है कि अपराध का शिकार न केवल आर्थिक रूप से बल्कि भावनात्मक और सामाजिक रूप से भी प्रभावित होता है, और अपराधी स्वयं एक सामाजिक-आर्थिक पृष्ठभूमि से होता है। इस मॉडल में सभी पक्षों की जरूरतों और भावनाओं को समझकर सामूहिक उपचार और पुनः एकीकरण सुनिश्चित करने के लिए सामुदायिक भागीदारी की आवश्यकता होती है। किशोर न्याय प्रणाली पारंपरिक रूप से चार-चरणीय प्रक्रिया का पालन करती है: गिरफ्तारी, न्यायनिर्णयन, दोषसिद्धि और उपचार। यह

ढांचा अपराध को नियंत्रित करने में प्रभावी है, लेकिन सामाजिक और भावनात्मक जरूरतों की उपेक्षा करता है, जिससे पीड़ित हाशिए पर और अपराधी शक्तिहीन महसूस करता है। एक नया चौथा चरण- पुनर्वास- जोड़ा गया है, लेकिन इससे वांछित परिणाम नहीं मिले हैं। अमेरिका में कई किशोर इस प्रणाली में उलझ जाते हैं, जो अक्सर उन्हें आर्थिक और सामाजिक रूप से कमजोर बना देता है। पुनर्वास प्रयासों के बावजूद, यह एक अधूरी और दोषपूर्ण न्याय प्रणाली की ओर इशारा करता है।

2. प्रतिशोधात्मक न्याय के दृष्टिकोण

हाल के वर्षों में, पुनर्वास-आधारित किशोर न्याय प्रणाली के बारे में संदेह बढ़ा है। जिसे कभी बच्चों के हितों के रक्षक के रूप में देखा जाता था, उसे अब अक्सर दमनकारी और यथास्थिति को बनाए रखने वाला माना जाता है। पुनर्वास के असफल परिणामों ने इस दृष्टिकोण पर पुनर्विचार करने के लिए प्रेरित किया है। कई क्षेत्रों में, किशोर न्यायालयों की संरचना वयस्क आपराधिक न्याय प्रणाली की तरह हो गई है, जिसमें दंड और नैतिक जिम्मेदारी पर जोर दिया गया है। जबकि एक प्रगतिशील दृष्टिकोण किशोरों को उनकी मासूमियत और सीमित जिम्मेदारी के आधार पर देखता था, अदालतों ने अब कठोर दंडात्मक प्रक्रियाओं को अपनाया है। अतीत में, किशोरों को कलंक, आपराधिक जांच और सजा से बचाने पर जोर दिया जाता था, लेकिन अब यह दृष्टिकोण बदल गया है। फिर भी, यह भी स्वीकार किया जाता है कि किशोरों में नैतिक परिपक्वता की कमी है, जिससे उन्हें दोषी ठहराने की प्रक्रिया पर सवाल उठते हैं।

किशोर न्यायालयों की वर्तमान संरचना

किशोर न्यायालयों की स्थापना "पैरेंस पैट्रिया" सिद्धांत पर हुई थी, जिसका उद्देश्य युवाओं को दंडित करने के बजाय पुनर्वास और उपचार प्रदान करना था। न्यायाधीशों को व्यापक विवेकाधिकार दिए गए थे ताकि वे प्रत्येक युवा की परिस्थितियों के अनुसार निर्णय ले सकें और समाजहित में विकल्प चुन सकें। लेकिन व्यवहार में, किशोर न्यायालय अपने परिकल्पित आदर्श से भटक गए। युवाओं को "अपराधी" मानने की बजाय, उन्हें अधिकारियों से टकराव के आधार पर दोषी ठहराया गया। पुनर्वास प्रयासों की विफलता के कारण दंड की मांग बढ़ने लगी, और अदालतों द्वारा सुझाया गया मानसिक स्वास्थ्य उपचार भी देखभाल से अधिक सजा के रूप में देखा जाने लगा। अंततः, युवाओं को दूरस्थ संस्थानों में भेजे जाने की प्रवृत्ति ने पुनर्वास की जगह दंडात्मक दृष्टिकोण को बढ़ावा दिया।

न्यायालय की प्रक्रियाएँ

किशोर न्यायालय की प्रक्रिया को समझने के लिए, इसकी शब्दावली और संरचना को जानना महत्वपूर्ण है। वयस्क प्रणाली के विपरीत, किशोर न्यायालय में एक "याचिका" दायर की जाती है, जिसमें अपराध के बारे में जानकारी और किशोर का विवरण होता है। याचिका

पर परिवीक्षा अधिकारी या जिला अटॉर्नी द्वारा हस्ताक्षर किए जाते हैं। यदि किशोर सुरक्षा के लिए खतरा पैदा करता है, तो उसे सुनवाई से पहले हिरासत में लिया जा सकता है। किशोरों के लिए हिरासत केंद्र वयस्क जेलों से अलग होते हैं और अधिक स्वतंत्रता और देखभाल सेवाएँ प्रदान करते हैं। गिरफ्तारी के समय एक जोखिम मूल्यांकन किया जाता है, जिसमें किशोर का इतिहास, जनसांख्यिकीय विवरण, हिरासत की स्थिति आदि दर्ज की जाती है। किशोर अभियोग में "दोषी" या "दोषी नहीं" होने का दावा नहीं करता है, बल्कि "सच्चा" या "झूठा" होने का दावा करता है। यदि किशोर झूठा दावा करता है, तो मामला किशोर परीक्षण में चला जाता है, जिसे जूरी के बिना एक न्यायाधीश द्वारा संचालित किया जाता है।

किशोर न्याय नीतियों का प्रभाव

किशोर न्याय नीति में बढ़ती कठोरता ने युवा अपराध के प्रति त्वरित और संवेदनशील प्रतिक्रिया की संभावनाओं को कम कर दिया है। मीडिया और बजट नीतियों के प्रभाव में दंडात्मक दृष्टिकोण हावी हो गया है, जिससे पुनर्वास संबंधी चर्चाएँ कमजोर हो गई हैं। किशोर अपराध के इर्द-गिर्द डर का माहौल बना हुआ है, जिससे अदालतों पर कठोर दंड लगाने का दबाव बढ़ रहा है। नतीजतन, पुनर्वास और सामुदायिक सेवा जैसे मानवीय विकल्पों में कमी आई है, जबकि मौद्रिक दंड और बर्खास्तगी में वृद्धि हुई है। आर्थिक असमानता और युवा लोगों की कमजोरी ने इस समस्या को और बढ़ा दिया है। हालाँकि कुछ मीडिया पुनर्वास की संभावना को उजागर करते हैं, लेकिन दंडात्मक दृष्टिकोण अभी भी व्यापक नीति पर हावी है।

1. शून्य सहनशीलता नीतियाँ

"शून्य सहनशीलता" नीति स्कूल अनुशासन में न्यायसंगत होने का दावा करती है, लेकिन निलंबन, निष्कासन या पुलिस के पास भेजने जैसी सजाएँ व्यवहार की गंभीरता की परवाह किए बिना दी जाती हैं। हालाँकि इसे निष्पक्ष कहा जाता है, लेकिन शोध से पता चलता है कि यह नीति नस्लीय असमानताओं को बढ़ावा देती है। उदाहरण के लिए, अश्वेत छात्रों को प्रिंसिपल के पास भेजे जाने की संभावना श्वेत छात्रों की तुलना में दोगुनी है, भले ही सजा समान हो। यह नीति अश्वेत और लैटिनो छात्रों के किशोर न्यायालय में शामिल होने की संभावना को भी बढ़ाती है, खासकर जब स्कूलों को पुलिस स्टेशन में बदल दिया जाता है। व्यक्तिपरक आरोप - जैसे "अनादर" या "अवज्ञा" - अश्वेत छात्रों पर असंगत रूप से लगाए जाते हैं। एक रिपोर्ट के अनुसार, "स्कूल व्यवधान" मामलों में आरोपी बनाए गए लोगों में से 69% अफ्रीकी अमेरिकी छात्र थे, और उन्हें जेल की सजा भी अधिक मिलती है।

2. डायवर्सन कार्यक्रम

कभी-कभी माता-पिता, शिक्षक या पुलिस अधिकारी ऐसे किशोरों को डायवर्सनरी कार्यक्रमों में भेजते हैं, जो अपराध के

जोखिम में होते हैं। ये कार्यक्रम अपराध के खिलाफ एक सक्रिय उपाय हैं।

इनका उद्देश्य युवाओं और उनके माता-पिता के बीच संचार को बढ़ावा देना, भावनाओं को व्यक्त करने का अवसर प्रदान करना और परिवारों को एक-दूसरे को बेहतर ढंग से समझने में मदद करना है। यह प्रक्रिया किशोर अपराध को एक बड़े परिवार या सामाजिक चुनौती के संकेत के रूप में देखती है, जिससे समस्या की जड़ों को समझने और उसे ठीक करने में मदद मिलती है।

किशोर डायवर्सन कार्यक्रम तब शुरू किए जाते हैं जब कोई युवा पहली बार किशोर न्याय प्रणाली के संपर्क में आता है। यदि अपराध हल्का हो और पिछला आपराधिक रिकॉर्ड न हो, तो उसे औपचारिक न्यायिक प्रक्रिया से हटाकर डायवर्सन की ओर भेजा जा सकता है।

● इन कार्यक्रमों के प्रमुख उद्देश्य हैं:

1. न्यायालय के रिकॉर्ड से कलंक से बचाना,
 2. परिवार और समाज में बेहतर समायोजन कराना,
 3. न्याय व्यवस्था की लागत घटाना, कार्यक्षमता बढ़ाना।
- ये कार्यक्रम विभिन्न रूपों में हो सकते हैं, जैसे:
1. स्कूल से निष्कासन के स्थान पर जवाबदेही योजनाएँ,
 2. प्रारंभिक चरण में परिवारों से संवाद और हस्तक्षेप,
 3. जिला अटॉर्नी या स्थानीय एजेंसी द्वारा रेफरल।

कुछ कार्यक्रम सीधे न्यायालय से जुड़ते हैं और युवाओं को हिरासत से बचाने या सजा की योजना को कम करने का विकल्प देते हैं।

3. कारावास बनाम पुनर्वास

किशोर न्यायालयों की स्थापना का मूल उद्देश्य युवाओं का उपचार और पुनर्वास करना था। लेकिन हाल के वर्षों में, सवाल उठाए गए हैं कि क्या उनका प्राथमिक उद्देश्य अभी भी पुनर्वास है या क्या यह सजा और सामुदायिक सुरक्षा बन गया है।

"सख्ती अपनाओ" जैसे आंदोलनों और नए विधायी परिवर्तनों ने गंभीर अपराध करने वाले किशोरों को न्यायालय के दायरे में लाकर पुनर्वास की भावना को कमजोर कर दिया है। "शून्य सहनशीलता" की नीतियाँ अपनाई गई हैं, खासकर स्कूलों में, यहाँ तक कि छोटे-मोटे अपराधों या पहली बार अपराध करने वालों के लिए भी, जिससे न्यायालय की भूमिका पर फिर से सवाल उठ रहे हैं। पिछले 25 वर्षों में, किशोरों को वयस्क आपराधिक न्यायालयों में स्थानांतरित करना किशोर न्याय नीति में सबसे अधिक बहस और शोध किए गए मुद्दों में से एक रहा है। अधिकांश अध्ययनों ने इस बात पर ध्यान केंद्रित किया है कि क्या न्यायाधीशों के निर्णय युवाओं के पुनरावृत्ति की संभावना या उनके व्यवहार के निष्पक्ष मूल्यांकन पर आधारित हैं।

अधिकांश विशेषज्ञ इस बात पर सहमत हैं कि वयस्क न्यायालयों की दंडात्मक प्रणाली और किशोर न्यायालयों के

पुनर्वास-आधारित दृष्टिकोण के बीच बहुत बड़ा अंतर है। किशोरों को वयस्क न्यायालयों में स्थानांतरित करने से उनके पुनर्वास की संभावना कम हो जाती है। समय के साथ, किशोर न्यायालयों में सुधार की आवश्यकता महसूस की गई और कई राज्यों में डायवर्सन कार्यक्रमों और पुनर्वास-आधारित हस्तक्षेपों को बढ़ावा दिया गया। रिपोर्टों के अनुसार, शुरू में किशोर न्यायालय ज्यादातर गंभीर अपराधों तक ही सीमित थे, लेकिन सुधारों के साथ इसकी भूमिका और दायरा दोनों बढ़ गए हैं।

● हाल ही में विधायी परिवर्तन

1996-97 के दौरान एरिजोना राज्य ने किशोर न्याय प्रणाली में कई विधायी बदलाव किए। इन सुधारों का उद्देश्य युवाओं के साथ कठोर व्यवहार को बढ़ावा देना था:

1. कुछ मामलों में किशोरों को वयस्क न्यायालय में भेजने की न्यूनतम आयु घटाई गई।
2. पहले अवसर पर अपराध करने वाले युवाओं के लिए भी दंड सख्त किया गया।
3. सबूतों की प्रक्रिया में बदलाव कर, किशोरों को खतरनाक अपराधी घोषित करना आसान बनाया गया।
4. याचिका दाखिल करने की समय-सीमा में बदलाव और संस्थानों की स्थिति रिपोर्टिंग मानकों को बदला गया।

● **संवैधानिक चिंताएँ** : कुछ नए कानून अत्यधिक व्यापक हैं और अस्पष्ट भाषा में लिखे गए हैं, जिससे किशोरों के अधिकारों का हनन हो सकता है। विशेष रूप से वयस्क अदालत में स्थानांतरित किशोरों के खिलाफ सबूतों के इस्तेमाल को लेकर विवाद है।

● **राजनीतिक प्रभाव**: ये परिवर्तन एरिजोना अर्टोर्नी जनरल कार्यालय के प्रभाव से प्रेरित थे, जिससे कानूनी प्रणाली में सत्ता संतुलन और निष्पक्षता पर सवाल उठे।

समुदाय-आधारित विकल्प

पिछले दशक में किशोर न्याय नीति में बदलाव आया है—1980 और 1990 के दशक की "सख्त" नीति की जगह अब सामुदायिक-आधारित सुधार ने ले ली है। पारंपरिक संस्थागत देखभाल से हटकर, अब निजी और स्थानीय स्तर पर चलने वाले कार्यक्रमों पर जोर दिया जा रहा है।

एक सर्वेक्षण में पाया गया कि 16 प्रमुख शहरों में निजीकरण तेजी से बढ़ रहा है।

- यह कई सवाल खड़े करता है:
 - a. निजी बनाम सार्वजनिक सेवा?
 - b. लाभ आधारित बनाम गैर-लाभकारी संगठन?
 - c. क्या निजी सेवाओं को वही अधिकार मिलने चाहिए जो सार्वजनिक सेवाओं को मिलते हैं?
- **लाभ** :
 - a. सामुदायिक कार्यक्रमों से युवाओं का पुनर्वास बेहतर होता है।

b. पुनरावृत्ति दर घटती है।

c. सेवाएं सस्ती होती हैं और परिवारों को एकजुट रखती हैं।

किशोर न्यायालयों के सामने चुनौतियाँ

आज के किशोर न्यायालय कई महत्वपूर्ण चुनौतियों से जूझ रहे हैं। जहाँ पहले इनका उद्देश्य पुनर्वास और कानूनी कलंक से सुरक्षा था, वहीं अब वे अधिकतर दंडात्मक हो गए हैं।

- a. किशोरों का वयस्क न्यायालयों में स्थानांतरण बढ़ रहा है।
- b. निजता और डायवर्सन नीति कमजोर हुई है।
- c. रिकॉर्ड सार्वजनिक होने, सख्त सजा और कठोर प्रक्रिया अब आम बात है।

इससे किशोरों का "नागरिक जोखिम" बढ़ गया है — यानी वे वयस्कों जैसी कानूनी प्रक्रिया और सजा का सामना कर रहे हैं।

हालांकि अब भी समय है कि किशोर न्याय में व्यापक और परियोजना-आधारित सुधार एजेंडा को अपनाया जाए, ताकि यह प्रणाली अपने मूल उद्देश्य यानी किशोरों के पुनर्वास और भविष्य सुधार की ओर लौट सके।

1. भीड़भाड़ और संसाधन आवंटन

किशोर हिरासत प्रणाली में भीड़भाड़, अपर्याप्त संसाधन, और प्रभावहीन पुनर्वास कार्यक्रम प्रमुख समस्याएँ हैं। कई बार युवाओं को गैर-राज्य या विदेशी संस्थानों में भेजना पड़ता है, जिससे स्थिति और जटिल हो जाती है। हालाँकि पुनर्वास के प्रयास आवश्यक हैं, पर यदि ये प्रभावशाली न हों, तो वे भीड़भाड़ कम करने में असफल रहते हैं। इसके अलावा, कुछ राज्यों में सुधार प्रयास अधिक कठिन साबित हो रहे हैं, और जहाँ सुधार हुए हैं, वहाँ भी प्रगति अस्थायी हो सकती है।

स्थानिक स्तर पर, न्यायालय और निरोध केंद्रों के बीच समन्वय की कमी है, और राज्य स्तर पर, नई तकनीकों से डाटा तो जुटाया जा रहा है, लेकिन उसके आधार पर प्रभावशीलता का मूल्यांकन अभी भी अपर्याप्त है।

2. न्यायालयों में तकनीकी एकीकरण

विघटनकारी नवाचारों ने वैश्विक न्यायालयों के कामकाज को बदला है। वेबकैम, लैपटॉप और आभासी सुनवाई जैसे माध्यमों ने तब भी न्यायिक प्रक्रिया को जारी रखा जब आमने-सामने की उपस्थिति संभव नहीं थी। कई बदलाव अब स्थायी हो चुके हैं, जिनके गंभीर प्रभाव न्याय प्रशासन पर पड़े हैं। आधुनिक न्यायालयों में टेक्नोलॉजी का समावेश, जैसे रिकॉर्डिंग डिवाइस, वीडियो कैमरा, डिस्प्ले स्क्रीन आदि, सभी न्यायिक भूमिकाओं को प्रभावित कर रहा है। अमेरिका सहित अन्य देशों में न्यायालय के डिजाइन और कार्यप्रणाली में विविधता देखी जाती है।

इस तकनीकी एकीकरण में सबसे बड़ी चुनौती है — न्यायिक प्रक्रिया की निष्पक्षता को बनाए रखना। भविष्य के लिए एक स्पष्ट दिशा और संतुलन आवश्यक है, ताकि तकनीकी नवाचार न्याय की वैधता और जनविश्वास को कमजोर न करें।

किशोर न्याय में मानसिक स्वास्थ्य की भूमिका

किशोर अपराधियों में मानसिक स्वास्थ्य संबंधी समस्याएं आम हैं, लेकिन शैक्षिक और किशोर न्याय प्रणालियाँ उनकी ज़रूरतों को अलग-अलग और असंबद्ध तरीकों से संबोधित करती हैं। अक्सर, युवा लोगों को पर्याप्त मनोवैज्ञानिक मूल्यांकन या उपचार के बिना न्याय प्रक्रिया में लाया जाता है। न्यायालय और परिवीक्षा प्रणालियाँ भी नियमित पूर्व-रिहाई मानसिक स्वास्थ्य सेवाएँ प्रदान नहीं करती हैं। इससे समस्या और बढ़ जाती है और युवा लोगों का व्यवहार खराब हो सकता है।

समाधान के लिए यह आवश्यक है कि सभी हितधारक सामूहिक जिम्मेदारी लें और एक संवेदनशील, संसाधनपूर्ण और एकीकृत उपचार मॉडल अपनाएँ। इससे युवा लोगों को बेहतर देखभाल मिल सकती है और सामाजिक-आर्थिक बोझ भी कम हो सकता है (फ्रैट, 2017)।

1. मूल्यांकन और उपचार

किशोर न्याय प्रणाली में जोखिम और पुनर्वास आवश्यकताओं का मूल्यांकन मुख्य रूप से पुनः अपराध की संभावना और मानसिक स्वास्थ्य की स्थिति पर केंद्रित होता है (Scott & Grisso, 1997)।

हालाँकि अधिकांश राज्य ऐसे मूल्यांकन उपकरण प्रदान करते हैं, उनकी गुणवत्ता और उपयोग में भारी अंतर है। जोखिम मूल्यांकन युवाओं के अपराध दोहराने की प्रवृत्ति बताते हैं, जबकि सहायक मूल्यांकन सुधार की दिशा में आवश्यक क्षेत्रों को दर्शाते हैं। लेकिन इन मूल्यांकनों का न्यायालयों द्वारा पूर्ण उपयोग नहीं किया जाता। इसलिए इन प्रणालियों का मानकीकरण और प्रभावी उपयोग ज़रूरी है ताकि उपचार सेवाओं के लिए सही रेफरल और प्रभावी पुनर्वास सुनिश्चित हो सके (Gebo, 2002)।

2. मानसिक स्वास्थ्य का अपराध पर प्रभाव

मानसिक स्वास्थ्य समस्याएँ, जैसे अवसाद और चिंता, किशोरों के अपराधों—विशेषकर हिंसक अपराधों—से जुड़ी होती हैं (Stoddard-Dare et al., 2011)।

किशोर न्याय प्रणाली में मानसिक विकारों वाले युवाओं की भागीदारी सामान्य आबादी की तुलना में अधिक है।

इस जानकारी का उपयोग न्यायाधीश और परिवीक्षा अधिकारी युवाओं को उचित सेवाओं और संसाधनों की ओर मार्गदर्शन करने के लिए कर सकते हैं, जिससे न्यायालय की भागीदारी को रोका जा सकता है।

- मानसिक स्वास्थ्य, व्यवहारिक समस्याएँ और किशोर न्याय
 - a. अवसाद व चिंता से पीड़ित किशोरों के हिंसक अपराध में हिरासत में जाने की संभावना 340% तक बढ़ जाती है, जबकि सीखने या आचरण विकार वाले किशोरों में यह जोखिम 200% तक बढ़ जाता है।
 - b. शहरी क्षेत्रों में अल्पसंख्यक युवाओं को पहली गिरफ्तारी में भी ज्यादा हिरासत में लिया जाता है, जिससे न्यायिक असमानता झलकती है।

c. व्यवहारिक समस्याओं जैसे ध्यान की कमी और आवेगशीलता को नजरअंदाज किया जाता है।

d. समस्या की पहचान और समय पर हस्तक्षेप से डायवर्जन सुधार, पुनरावृत्ति में कमी और निवारक सेवाओं से जुड़ाव संभव है।

- किशोर न्याय में माता-पिता की भूमिका
 - a. कानून के साथ संघर्ष कर रहे किशोरों के माता-पिता अक्सर असहाय, गिल्ट और चिंता में होते हैं। वे या तो कठोर नियंत्रण अपनाते हैं या देखरेख में कमी कर बैठते हैं।
 - b. अध्ययन बताते हैं कि सकारात्मक पालन-पोषण, जैसे गर्मजोशी, निगरानी और संवाद, किशोरों के असामाजिक व्यवहार को रोक सकता है।
 - c. किशोर लड़कियाँ माता-पिता को बहुत सख्त मानकर विद्रोही हो जाती हैं।
 - d. नैतिक दिशा, मूल्य आधारित मार्गदर्शन, और सक्रिय सहभागिता ही किशोर अपराध रोकने में सबसे कारगर उपाय हैं।

परिवारों के लिए सहायता प्रणाली

किशोर न्यायालयों की स्थापना बच्चों को अपराधी नहीं बल्कि सुरक्षित और प्रशिक्षित करने के उद्देश्य से हुई थी। इन्हें बच्चों के दुर्व्यवहार को "आपराधिक" के बजाय सहायता आधारित दृष्टिकोण से देखने के लिए बनाया गया था। समय के साथ, कई किशोर न्यायालय "मिनी-आपराधिक" अदालतों में बदल गए हैं, जहाँ कारावास और दंड पर अधिक जोर दिया जाने लगा। इसके कारण हल्के अपराधों को भी गंभीरता से लिया जाने लगा। हालाँकि, कुछ क्षेत्रों में विकल्प आधारित दृष्टिकोण अपनाया गया है – जैसे डायवर्शन, पुनर्स्थापनात्मक न्याय, शिक्षा और पारिवारिक भागीदारी, जो अधिक प्रभावी साबित हुए हैं। इससे पुनरावृत्ति में कमी, क्रोध में नियंत्रण और सकारात्मक सामाजिक जुड़ाव में वृद्धि देखी गई है (गेबो, 2002)।

शिक्षा और जागरूकता कार्यक्रम

शिक्षा और जागरूकता कार्यक्रम किशोर अपराध रोकथाम की समग्र रणनीति का अहम हिस्सा हैं। इनका उद्देश्य स्कूली बच्चों, युवाओं और आम जनता को किशोर अपराध से जुड़े कारकों और चुनौतियों के बारे में जानकारी देना है। यह कार्यक्रम जागरूकता बढ़ाकर, बच्चों और हितधारकों को सकारात्मक सोच और व्यवहार की ओर प्रेरित करते हैं (ऐनी लेबे, 2015)। शिक्षा व जागरूकता कार्यक्रम आमतौर पर नैतिक विकास और अवैध व्यवहार के परिणामों पर केंद्रित होते हैं, पर इनके डिजाइन, प्रस्तुति और प्रभावशीलता पर कम ध्यान दिया जाता है। व्याख्यान-आधारित तरीकों की बजाय मीडिया आधारित प्रस्तुतियाँ अधिक प्रभावी साबित हो सकती हैं। किशोर न्याय प्रणाली की जानकारी की कमी से जुड़ी गलत धारणाएँ युवा अपराधियों के प्रति भय और कठोर दंड की माँग को बढ़ा सकती हैं। ऐसे में जागरूकता कार्यक्रम सही सामाजिक दृष्टिकोण बनाने और 'नैतिक आतंक' से बचने में सहायक होते हैं।

किशोर न्याय में नैतिक विचार

फिर, गॉल्ट के अनुसार, किशोर न्यायालयों में न्यायाधीशों, अभियोजकों और वकीलों की नैतिक अपेक्षाओं को स्पष्ट और परिष्कृत करना जरूरी है। आज, जब जवाबदेही की मांग बढ़ रही है, एक सामान्य नैतिक संहिता बनाना आवश्यक हो गया है, जो न्यायिक आचरण के मानकों से मेल खाए।

साथ ही, इंटरनेट और तकनीकी नवाचारों ने किशोर न्याय प्रणाली को भी प्रभावित किया है। इंटरनेट के प्रयोग ने प्रशासन में बदलाव लाए हैं, लेकिन इससे प्रथम संशोधन अधिकारों और उचित प्रक्रिया के बीच संघर्ष भी बढ़ा है, विशेषकर स्कूल हिंसा जैसे मामलों में (नीत्ज़, 2011)। तेजी से बढ़ती तकनीक, इंटरनेट और वैश्वीकरण के प्रभाव ने किशोर न्याय के भविष्य को अनिश्चित बना दिया है, विशेषकर अधिकार क्षेत्र, पहचान और युवाओं से जुड़े मुद्दों के संदर्भ में।

1. बाल अधिकार

यह खंड बाल अधिकारों पर आधारित किशोर न्याय प्रणाली की संरचना की समीक्षा करता है, विशेषकर बाल अधिकार कन्वेंशन (CRC) और अन्य अंतर्राष्ट्रीय संधियों के संदर्भ में। अनुच्छेद 40 विशेष रूप से 12 वर्ष से कम उम्र के बच्चों के अपराधीकरण पर रोक और उनके साथ न्यायपूर्ण व्यवहार की बात करता है। CRC के अनुसार, 18 वर्ष से कम आयु का प्रत्येक व्यक्ति "बच्चा" माना जाता है (गुराहू, 2016)। बाल अधिकार कन्वेंशन और सामान्य टिप्पणी 10 न्यूनतम

अपराधीकरण आयु 12 वर्ष निर्धारित करने की सिफारिश करते हैं, लेकिन वैश्विक स्तर पर यह मानक व्यापक रूप से लागू नहीं है। 12 वर्ष से कम आयु के बच्चों के अपराधीकरण को लेकर गंभीर चिंताएं हैं, क्योंकि इससे बच्चों की सुरक्षा और अधिकार खतरे में पड़ते हैं। इसके अलावा, यह न्यूनतम आयु मानक सभी बच्चों के लिए पर्याप्त सुरक्षा सुनिश्चित नहीं कर पाता, खासकर विविध वैश्विक संदर्भों में।

2. गोपनीयता और निजता के मुद्दे

किशोर न्याय प्रणाली में रिकॉर्ड की गोपनीयता पुनर्वास को बढ़ावा देने और कलंक से बचाने के लिए महत्वपूर्ण मानी जाती है। शुरुआत में इसे किशोरों की मदद करने वाले दयालु दृष्टिकोण के रूप में देखा गया था। लेकिन आधुनिक तकनीक, मीडिया का प्रभाव और अपराध के लिए जवाबदेही की मांग ने गोपनीयता पर नई चुनौतियाँ पैदा की हैं, जिससे रिकॉर्ड सार्वजनिक होने लगे हैं।

निष्कर्ष

यह लेख अमेरिका में किशोर न्यायालय की उत्पत्ति, प्रकार और वर्तमान सुधारों का सार प्रस्तुत करता है। इसकी स्थापना युवाओं के पुनर्वास, अधिकारों की रक्षा और समाज की सुरक्षा के उद्देश्य से हुई थी। हालांकि, वर्षों में प्रणाली में कई चुनौतियाँ और असहमतियाँ आई हैं। फिर भी, किशोर न्यायालय आज भी हस्तक्षेप और पुनर्वास का प्रभावी माध्यम बना हुआ है।

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झारखंड के जनजातीय विकास में महात्मा गाँधी की प्रसंगिकता

सारांश

गांधीजी की दूरदर्शिता इतनी प्रखर थी कि वे आज से 100 वर्ष से भी पहले ही भौतिकतावादी सभ्यता में निहित बुराईयों को महसूस कर चुके थे। औद्योगिक पश्चिमी समाज की आलोचना करते थे। अपनी पुस्तक 'हिन्द स्वराज' में उन्होंने पश्चिमी सभ्यता को शैतान की संज्ञा दी है। उसके समाधान के लिए अब दुनिया महात्मा गांधी के विचारों को उपयोगी मानकर आशा भरी नजरों से देख रही है और उन्हीं के विचारों को अपनाने से उसका समाधान दिखाई पड़ रहा है। गांधीवाद की अपरिहार्यता वर्तमान समस्याओं के निदान हेतु विश्व के सभी देश मानने लगे हैं। महात्मा गांधी के विचार दिन पर दिन ज्यादा से ज्यादा पढ़ा जाने लगा है और आज के लिए और ज्यादा प्रासंगिक माना जाने लगा है। महात्मा गांधी के जीवन दर्शन ने लोगों का ध्यान खींचा है। ऐसे समय में महात्मा गांधी के जीवन दर्शन और विचार पर जीवन यापन करने वाले के रूप में पहचाने जाने वाले आदिवासी समुदाय के जीवन के बारे में जानने की उत्सुकता लोगों में बढ़ना स्वभाविक है। वर्तमान सभ्यता मशीन आधारित उद्योग प्रधान उपभोक्तावादी है इस सभ्यता ने मानव के सामने विकराल समस्याएँ खड़ी कर दी है, जिसपर नियंत्रण पाना बहुत मुश्किल लग रहा है। तकनीकी और औद्योगिक क्रांति के कारण मनुष्य के स्थान पर मशीनें अपना प्रभुत्व जमाने लगी हैं।

कीवर्ड : किजनजातीय, महात्मा गांधी, आदिवासी समुदाय, आन्दोलन।

सोनाली सांगा¹

भूमिका

दक्षिण अफ्रीका में अपने आन्दोलन की सफलता के बाद 9 जनवरी, 1915 को मोहनदास करमचन्द्र गांधी भारत लौटे। भारत में उनका व्यापक स्वागत किया गया। उन्हें भारत के लोग जानने लगे थे। लेकिन चंपारण में आन्दोलन के बाद महात्मा गांधी को भारत में ज्यादा लोकप्रियता मिली। और यही वह समय है जब आदिवासी समुदाय महात्मा गांधी के बारे में जानने लगे क्योंकि चंपारण का आन्दोलन उसी प्रांत में हो रहा था जहां के आदिवासी समुदाय निवासी थे। इसी दौरान गांधीजी को भारत में किसानों की पीड़ा से पहली बार सामना हुआ। उनका चंपारण में ठहरने से अपने देश के किसानों के जीवन का सीधा अनुभव उन्हें मिला।

आदिवासी समुदाय भी मूल रूप से किसान ही थे तथा वे स्थानीय जमींदारों और शोषकों के खिलाफ आन्दोलन भी 1914 से चला रहे थे। चंपारण आन्दोलन के लिए गांधीजी उत्तरी बिहार के सबसे बड़े शहर मुजफ्फरपुर 11 अप्रैल 1917 को पहुंचे। 20 जून 1917 के शुरुआत में आन्दोलन के दौरान गांधीजी को बिहार की ग्रीष्मकालीन राजधानी रांची में लेफ्टिनेंट गवर्नर से मिलने आना पड़ा था। उस समय लेफ्टिनेंट गवर्नर सर एडवर्ड गेट थे। रांची वही जिला था, जहां आदिवासी समुदाय की बहुलता थी (आज यह जिला कई जिलों में विभक्त हो गया है- 1983 में रांची तीन जिलों में विभक्त हुआ - रांची, गुमला, लोहरदगा: 22 12 सितंबर, 2007 में पुनः रांची से खूंटी जिले का निर्माण हुआ और गुमला जिला से 30 अप्रैल, 2001 में सिमडेगा जिला बना। ये सभी जिले मिलकर वर्तमान में दक्षिणी छोटानागपुर प्रमंडल का गठन करते हैं।

आदिवासी शब्दगांधीजी के एक सहयोगी ठक्कर बापा द्वारा गढ़ा गया था, जिन्होंने गांधीजी के उदाहरण और प्रेरणा पर अपना जीवन आदिवासियों के कल्याण के लिए समर्पित कर दिया था। जिनका पूरा नाम अमृतलाल विठ्ठलदास ठक्कर था। उनकी पहचान महात्मा गांधी के विचारों पर चलने वाले समुदाय के रूप में की जाती है। आदिवासी महात्मा गांधी के अनुयायी माने जाते हैं। यहां कोई एक व्यक्ति नहीं बल्कि एक पूरा समुदाय सामान्यतः महात्मा गांधी के विचारों पर चलता है। ऐसे समुदाय दुनिया में विरले ही दिखायी देते हैं। और यह भी की महात्मा गांधी के देहांत के कई दशक बीत जाने और उपभोक्तावादी पश्चिमी सभ्यता का परचम पूरे जोश से पूरी दुनिया में लहरते इस इक्कीसवीं सदी में आदिवासी समुदाय महात्मा गांधी के विचारों पर चल रहा है। यह बात उनकी ओर सभी का ध्यान आकर्षित करता है।

¹शोधार्थी, स्नातकोत्तर, इतिहास विभाग, विनोबा भावे, विश्वविद्यालय, हजारीबाग, झारखंड।

जनजातीय आन्दोलन और स्वतंत्रता आन्दोलन में जनजातीय लोगोंके द्वारा सक्रिय भाग लेने के कारण अहिंसक व्यवहार अपनाने के बावजूद उन्हें ब्रिटिश जुल्म का शिकार होना पड़ा। अंग्रेज सरकार ने कृषि भूमि को जिस पर खेती करते थे नीलाम कर दिया। इससे स्वतंत्रता संग्राम में संघर्ष करने हेतु उनके मनोबल में गिरावट के स्थान पर और अधिक प्रेरणा का संचार देखा गया। उन्होंने छोटानागपुर में निवास करने वाली अन्य जनजातियों के समक्ष विशेष रूप से तथा देशवासियों के समक्ष सामान्य रूप से यह उदाहरण प्रस्तुत किया कि देश की स्वतंत्रता सर्वोच्च मूल्य है जिसे हासिल करने हेतु बड़े से बड़े त्याग की आवश्यकता पड़ती है। त्याग करने का जज्बा सिर्फ शिक्षित और संपन्न वर्ग में ही नहीं होता बल्कि हाशिए पर रहने वाले गरीब जनजातीय चाहे वे जनजातीय समुदाय से ही क्यों न हो उनके पास भी त्याग करने का जज्बा होता है। उनका देश प्रेम भी किसी अन्य समुदाय के देश प्रेम से कम नहीं है।

आदिवासी ईमानदार और सीधे-साधे होते हैं। झारखण्डी स्वयं को महात्मा गांधी का अनुयायी मानते हैं इसलिए महात्मा गांधी के प्रमुख सिद्धांत सत्य और अहिंसा के पालन पर उनका जोर होता है। 'सत्य और अहिंसा का महात्मा गांधी व्यापक अर्थ लगाते हैं। भले ही उस व्यापक अर्थ को जान लोग समझे या न समझे उसके स्थूल अर्थ को वे समझते हैं और हर संभव उसका पालन करते हैं। यह उनके स्वभाव का एक अंग हो गया है। जनजातीय लोग आन्दोलन में हिंसा का सहारा नहीं लेते हैं। महात्मा गांधी से संपर्क में आने से पहले भी उनका आन्दोलन अहिंसक था। लेकिन जब महात्मा गांधी द्वारा चलाये गये स्वतंत्रता आन्दोलन से जुड़े तो उन्हें अहिंसक आन्दोलन का और प्रशिक्षण प्राप्त हुआ क्योंकि महात्मा गांधी अहिंसा के पूजारी थे और उनका सख्त निर्देश था कि आन्दोलन में हिंसा का प्रयोग नहीं हो इस तरह महात्मा गांधी के विचारों के प्रभाव से जनजातीय समुदाय सामान्यतः अहिंसा का पालन करते हैं।

छोटानागपुर की जनजातियों में नशा करने की प्रवृत्ति प्रबलता से रही है। वे हड़िया - शराब आदि का सेवन करते हैं। कई लोग इसे बेचकर पैसा कमाते हैं। जनजातीय लोग महात्मा गांधी के समान मद्यपान के विरोध और मद्यनिषेध के समर्थक हैं। इस तरह के धंधे को नहीं अपनाते हैं। आदिवासी किसी भी तरह के नशीले पेय पदार्थ का सेवन नहीं करते हैं। वे मद्यनिषेध का पालन करते हैं और शराब, हड़िया आदि के बिक्री के भी विरोधी रहे हैं। स्वतंत्रता आन्दोलन के दौरान महात्मा गांधी के निर्देशानुसार वे लोग शराब की दुकानों पर धरना भी देते थे जिससे कई जनजातीय लोगोंको जेल की सजाएं भी काटनी पड़ी थी।

मोहनदास करमचन्द गांधी को राष्ट्रीय चेहरा बनाने में सबसे महत्वपूर्ण योगदान रौलट कानून के विरुद्ध अप्रैल 1919 में हुए सत्याग्रह का रहा। जिसमें गांधीजी को संपूर्ण भारत का नेतृत्व करने का मौका दिया। उनके द्वारा बुलाए गए 6 अप्रैल के आम हड़ताल को जनता का व्यापक समर्थन मिला। गांधीजी से भारतीयों में एक नई आशा का संचार हुआ। रौलट कानून के खिलाफ सत्याग्रह ने उन्हें पूरे भारत का चेहरा बना दिया, उन्हें इस उपमहाद्वीप के प्रमुख शहरों और नगरों में जाना जाने लगा। फिर भी महात्मा गांधी को भारत की राजनीति के सर्वोच्च नेता के रूप में 1920-22 के असहयोग आन्दोलन ने ही स्थापित किया।

महात्मा गांधी का भारत के सर्वोच्च नेता के रूप में उदय के संबंध में

कलकत्ता के विशेष अधिवेशन के महत्व को जवाहरलाल नेहरू कुछ इस तरह उल्लेख करते हैं, "कलकत्ता के विशेष अधिवेशन ने कांग्रेस की राजनीति में गांधी - युग शुरू किया, जो तब से अब तक कायम है- हां, बीच में थोड़ा-सा समय (1922 से 1929) जरूर ऐसा गया, जिसमें गांधीजी ने अपने-आपको पीछे रख लिया था और स्वराज्य- पार्टी को, जिसके नेता देशबंधुदास और मेरे पिताजी थे, अपना काम करने दिया था। तबसे कांग्रेस की सारी दृष्टि ही बदल गई; विलायती कपड़े चले गये और देखते-देखते सिर्फ खादी - ही खादी दिखाई देने लगी; कांग्रेस में नये किस्म के प्रतिनिधि दिखाई देने लगे, जो खास करके मध्यम वर्ग की निचली श्रेणी के थे। हिन्दुस्तानी, और कभी-कभी तो उस प्रांत की भाषा, जहां अधिवेशन होता था, अधिकाधिक बोली जाने लगी, क्योंकि कितने ही प्रतिनिधि अंग्रेजी नहीं जानते थे। राष्ट्रीय कामों में विदेशी भाषा का व्यवहार करने के खिलाफ भी लोगों के भाव तेजी से बढ़ रहे थे, और कांग्रेस की सभाओं में साफतौर पर एक नई जिन्दगी, नया जोश और सच्चाई दिखाई देती थी।"

जनजातीय लोग प्रथम बार महात्मा गांधी के विचारों के संपर्क में सन् 1920-22 के असहयोग आन्दोलन के दौरान आए और उसी समय से महात्मा गांधी की व्यस्तता भी बहुत बढ़ गयी। इस तरहजनजातीय लोगों का महात्मा गांधी से बहुत कम प्रत्यक्ष संपर्क हो पाया। महात्मा गांधी के सत्य, अहिंसा, चर्खा और खादी के सिद्धांत से प्रभावित होकर लोगों ने कांग्रेस में प्रवेश किया और देश की स्वतंत्रता के लिए लड़ाई की। टाना भगत जो गया कांग्रेस में आए थे, उससे बहुत प्रभावित हुए। रांची लौटने पर उन्होंने कई सभाएं की। इनमें राष्ट्रीय कांग्रेस के हेतु एक कार्यक्रम निर्धारित किया गया।

गया अधिवेशन में महात्मा गांधी से मिलने की इच्छा अधुरी ही रह गई। बाद में महात्मा गांधी से मिलने का मौका 1925 में प्राप्त हुआ। हरिवंश भगत लिखते हैं कि 1923 ई. (यहां 1925 होना चाहिए क्योंकि 10 मार्च 1922 को महात्मा गांधी को गिरफ्तार करके उन पर सरकार के प्रति असंतोष भड़काने का आरोप लगाया। गांधीजी को छह वर्षों की कैद की सजा सुनाई गई। स्वास्थ्य-संबंधी आधार पर 5 फरवरी 1924 को रिहा कर दिए गए थे।) में महात्मा गांधी रांची पधारे (जनजातीय लोगों ने उनके स्वागत के लिए चरखा अपने अपने कंधों पर ढोकर ले गए थे जिसका उन्होंने प्रदर्शन किया। महात्मा गांधी भोले भाले जनजातीय लोगों को देखकर बहुत खुश हुए। उनके तकलीफों को सुने और बोले कि आप लोगों के सभी प्रकार के दुख दूर होंगे। आप लोग चरखें से सूत काटकर खदर पहनों और कांग्रेस का म्बबर बनो। इसी समय से टाना भगतों ने हार्दिक दिल से कांग्रेस में भाग लिया। उस समय टाना भगतों का साथ श्री पूर्णो चक्र मित्र और रांची के देवकी नन्दन प्रसाद दे रहे थे। टाना भगतों ने गांधीजी के कहने पर खादी पहनी और विदेशी कपड़े की होली जलायी।

1925 के बाद महात्मा गांधी 1927 में झारखंड आये: फिर 1934 में अप्रैल के अंत में वे चार दिनों तक रांची रहे. यहां वे काफी व्यस्त रहे। तदुपरांत वे उड़ीसा चले गए। एक बार फिर झारखंड 1940 में कांग्रेस के रामगढ़ के राष्ट्रीय अधिवेशन में ही आ सकें। 6 जून को बड़ी संख्या में जनजातीय लोगों ने जुलूस निकाला और थरपखना से अपर बाजार और अंत में बाजार रोड, पहाड़ी टोला भट्टी से होते हुए हिन्दपीढ़ी गये।

पं. जवाहरलाल नेहरू को 1929 के लाहौर अधिवेशन में कांग्रेस का

अध्यक्ष बनाया गया। इस अधिवेशन में पारित एक प्रस्ताव में पूर्ण स्वराज्य को कांग्रेस का उद्देश्य घोषित किया गया। 31 दिसंबर 1929 को स्वाधीनता का नया नया स्वीकृत तिरंगा झंडा लहराया गया। 26 जनवरी 1930 को पहला स्वाधीनता दिवस घोषित किया गया। तब टाना भगत क्षेत्र में भी इसका प्रभाव पड़ा। रांची में स्वाधीनता दिवस को एक विशाल जुलूस निकाला गया। इसमें अन्य लोगों के साथ स्थानीय संस्थाओं के छात्र एवं जनजातीय समुदाय के लोगों ने भाग लिया। सभा 4 बजे शुरू हुई। स्थानीय कांग्रेस कमिटी के अध्यक्ष डॉ. पी. सी. मित्र ने “वन्देमातरम” और “भारत माता की जय” के नारों के बीच राष्ट्रीय झंडा फहराया। इस अवसर पर दो राष्ट्रीय गीत गाये गये। ये गीत मुजफ्फरपुर के सूरजदेव नारायण सिंह और कलकत्ता के आर. सन्याल के रचे हुए थे। सविनय अवज्ञा आन्दोलन तक जनजातीय समुदाय के लोग कांग्रेस के साथ गहराई से जुड़ गये थे। 1936 तक जनजातीय समुदाय के लोग कांग्रेस के कट्टर समर्थक बन गये थे और कांग्रेस के राष्ट्रीय और स्थानीय नेताओं और कार्यकर्ताओं के साथ उनके संबंध धनिक हो गए थे। कांग्रेस संगठन में उनका पर्याप्त प्रभाव था। 1937 में हरिवंश भगत को मांडर थाना कांग्रेस कमिटी का सचिव बनाया गया। उसी वर्ष झारखण्ड की जनजातीय गोआ भगत रांची जिला कांग्रेस कमिटी के अध्यक्ष बने।

जब 1940 में 19 और 20 मार्च को मौलाना अबुल कलाम की अध्यक्षता में रामगढ़ में अखिल भारतीय कांग्रेस कमिटी का अधिवेशन हुआ तब अधिवेशन में लाओ भगत, एतवा भगत, सोमा भगत, विश्वामित्र भगत, खबिया भगत और बिशुनपुर, चंदवा, कुडू, घाघरा, ओपा, मांडर के गांवों से बड़ी संख्या में झारखण्ड की जनजातीय लोगों ने भाग लिया। भारत छोड़ो आन्दोलन शुरू करने से पूर्व अक्टूबर 1940 में महात्मा गांधी ने कुछ चुने हुए व्यक्तियों को साथ लेकर सीमित पैमाने पर सत्याग्रह चलाने का निर्णय किया। महात्मा गांधी ने 1942 में अखिल भारतीय कांग्रेस समिति के वर्धा-अधिवेशन में कहा था. “मेरे लिए अहिंसा एक धर्म है, मेरे जीवन का सार है; लेकिन मैंने हिन्दुस्तान के सामने या किसी भी दूसरे व्यक्ति के सामने सरसरी तौर पर आपसी बातचीत के अलावा कभी इसे धर्म के रूप में रखने की कोशिश नहीं की। मैंने कांग्रेस के सामने इसे राजनीतिक पद्धति के रूप में रखा, जिसका इस्तेमाल राजनीतिक समस्या को सुलझाने के लिए किया जा सकता है।

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15 अगस्त, 1942 को 1500 से 2000 की संख्या में जनजातीय लोगों ने बिशुनपुर थाने पर राष्ट्रीय ध्वज फहराया और उस थाने के उप निरीक्षक और सिपाहियों को उनके साथ शामिल होने और सभी सरकारी रिकॉर्ड को जलाने का आह्वान किया। इसके जवाब में पुलिस ने बिशुनपुर कांग्रेस कमिटी कार्यालय में रखे सभी कागजात, नकदी और चावल जब्त कर ताला लगा दिया। कई जनजातीय लोगों को गिरफ्तार किया गया, उन पर जुर्माना लगाया गया और उन्हें अलग-अलग अवधि की कारावास की सजा सुनाई गई। 18 अगस्त को चैनपुर तथा बिशुनपुर थाना के टाना भगतों ने सदर अनुमंडल के बिशुनपुर थाना को जला दिया। उस दिन खूंटी अनुमंडल में बूडू नामक स्थान पर हड़ताल रही।

निष्कर्ष :

इस तरह से स्पष्ट होता है कि झारखण्ड की जनजातियों की जीवन-शैली और विचारों पर महात्मा आदिवासी गांधी के सिद्धांतों और विचारों का प्रभाव है। वे गांधीवादी हैं। आदिवासी पहले से गांधीवादी थे जिसे महात्मा गांधी के विचारों ने पुष्ट किया है और उनके आचरण में गांधीवाद के कई तत्वों को जोड़ा है। महात्मा गांधी एक ऐसी जीवन-शैली के पक्ष में थे जो सर्वसुलभ और नैतिक हो। ऐसा जीवन जो भी जीता है चाहे वह महात्मा गांधी को जानता हो या नहीं उसे गांधीवादी जीवन-शैली की श्रेणी में रखा जा सकता है। आदिवासी सामान्यतः एक परंपरा और आदत के रूप में लेकिन चेतना के साथ गांधीवाद को आत्मसात किये हुए हैं। वे महात्मा गांधी से प्रेरित हैं। आदर्श गांधीवादी बनने की भी उनमें प्रेरणा देखी जा सकती है और उन्हें ऐसा बनाया भी जा सकता है।

झारखंड के जनजातियों ने हमेशा अनेक विद्रोहों, सामाजिक आन्दोलनों तथा स्वतंत्रता संग्राम में सम्मिलित होने के बावजूद, नियंत्रित पैमाने पर ही सही, जनजातीय लोग सामान्य भारतीय जनमानस की चेतना की परिधि तक ही सीमित रहे। यहाँ सदियों से जनजातियों की परंपरागत व्यवस्था स्वायत्त रूप में कायम थी। परंपरागत व्यवस्था में छेड़छाड़ और शोषण के खिलाफ यहां की जनजातियों ने हिंसक संघर्ष किया। विदेशी पराधीनता और शोषण के खिलाफ हुए प्रारंभिक लड़ाईयों में झारखंड की जनजातियों के संघर्षों का प्रमुख स्थान है।

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सारांश

डा० सरिता कुमारी¹

बुद्ध ने “नारियों को भी बौद्धिक स्वतंत्रता का उपदेश दिया और पुरुषों से कहा कि उन्हें भी नारियों का सम्मान और सेवा करनी चाहिए। केवल नारियों से ही सेवा की अपेक्षा करना गलत है।” उन्होंने पुरुषों और नारियों में किसी प्रकार का भेद नहीं किया। नारी और पुरुष समाज में एक साथ जीवनयापन करते हैं। नारी पुरुष के सभी कार्यों में हिस्सा बटाती थी। तथागत बुद्ध उस गृहस्थ को अधिक महत्त्व देते थे जो अपने परिवार में अच्छी तरह से नारियों का पालन-पोषण करता है। महात्मा बुद्ध द्वारा भिक्षुणी संघ की स्थापना का इतिहास भिक्षु संघ से सर्वथा भिन्न है। महात्मा बुद्ध ने जिस समय अपने धर्म का प्रवर्तन किया था, उस समय केवल भिक्षु संघ की स्थापना की थी और उसके विस्तार के लिए अथक प्रयास किया था, किन्तु उन्होंने भिक्षुणी संघ की स्थापना भिक्षु संघ के स्थापना के पाँच वर्ष बाद अनिष्ठापूर्वक की थी। उनके द्वारा भिक्षुणी संघ की स्थापना का नारियों ने हृदय से स्वागत किया था तथा उसमें प्रविष्ट होने के लिए अभूतपूर्व उत्साह दिखलाया था। बौद्ध धर्म में पुरुषों तथा नारियों को समान स्थान प्राप्त था। सभी अपने कर्मों के अनुसार सद्गति और दुर्गति को प्राप्त होते हैं। बुद्ध नारी जाति की समानता के लिए विश्व के पहले समर्पित महामानव थे।

कीवर्ड : भिक्षुणी संघ, बुद्ध, नारी, बौद्धिक स्वतंत्रता।

भूमिका

बौद्ध काल में नारियों पर बुद्ध के विचारों का मानसिक, सामाजिक, धार्मिक एवं पारिवारिक प्रभाव अधिक दिखाई देता है। बहुत सारी नारियों ने अपना सर्वस्व धर्म की सेवा में लगा दिया था। तथागत बुद्ध द्वारा श्रावस्ती के महाविहार में भिक्षुसंघ को दिये धम्मोपदेश को सुनकर विशाखा के मन में संघ को कुछ दान देने का विचार आया। तब उसने अपने बहुमूल्य गहनों को बेचकर जिसकी कीमत लगभग नौ करोड़ रुपये थी, भूमी खरीदकर दो मंजिल का महाविहार निर्माण करवाया। महाविहार में ध्यान साधना के लिए एक हजार छोटे-छोटे कमरे (शून्यागार), चंद्रमण, जन्ताधर (स्नानाघर) और सभागार आदि की व्यवस्था थी। इस विहार का नाम पूर्वाराम (पुब्बाराम) महाविहार रखा गया और इस भिक्षुणीसंघ को दान दिये। दीघनिकाय के ‘सिंगालोवाद सुत्त’ में पति-पत्नी के कर्तव्यों को बताते हुये तथागत कहते हैं कि पति अपनी स्त्री की पाँच प्रकार से सेवा करें। (1) वह अपनी स्त्री का सम्मान करे (2) वह उसको अपमानित न करे (3) वह पर-स्त्री गमन (व्यभिचार) न करे। (4) वह उसे आर्थिक रूप से मजबूती प्रदान करे और घर की स्वामिनी बना दे। (5) वह उसकी उचित देखभाल, वस्त्र, आभूषण आदि से करे। बौद्ध साहित्य से ज्ञात होता है कि तत्कालीन समाज में न केवल परिवार की स्त्रियों को पुरुषों के समान धर्म का पालन करने का अधिकार था, अपितु उन्हें पुरुषों के समान गृहवास त्याग कर महात्मा बुद्ध के स्थापित संघ में प्रवेश करने का भी अधिकार प्राप्त हो गया था।

संघ में पुरुष एवं नारी क्रमशः भिक्षु एवं भिक्षुणी के रूप में रहकर दुःखों के विनाश के लिए साधना करते थे। बौद्ध काल में जब बौद्ध संघ की स्थापना हुई, उसके कुछ दिनों बाद से स्त्रियों को भी भिक्षुणी बनने का अधिकार एवं संघ में प्रवेश करने का अधिकार प्राप्त होने लगा। प्रारम्भ में बौद्धकालीन समाज में भिक्षुणी बनने का कोई अधिकार नहीं प्राप्त था। यद्यपि जैन धर्म के अन्तर्गत प्रारम्भ में अनेक जैन भिक्षुणियों का उल्लेख मिलता है। जैन धर्म में भिक्षु संघ एवं भिक्षुणी संघ की स्थापना साथ ही साथ हुई थी। इस बात की सत्यता इस तथ्य से स्पष्ट होती है कि आचारांग जैसे प्राचीन ग्रन्थों में भिक्षु एवं भिक्षुणियों के नियमों की व्यवस्था साथ-साथ की गयी है।

विनयपिटक ग्रन्थ भिक्षुओं की धार्मिक संहिता है। उसमें जो “दो अनियत धम्म है उसके बारे में भिक्षुओं को दोषी ठहराने का अधिकार और उसके लिए उसे दंड देने का अधिकार भी बुद्ध ने श्रद्धावान विश्वासपात्र उपासिकाओं को दिया था।” शीलसंपन्न उपासिकाओं को

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जो अधिकार बुद्ध ने दिया था वह पुरुष प्रधान भारतीय समाज में और धर्म में भी नारी को सर्वोच्च आदर देने वाला बुद्ध का क्रांतिकारी निर्णय था। दो हजार पाँच सौ साल पहले भारतीय समाज में नारी के अस्तित्व का जब कोई भी मूल्य नहीं था वह शोषित पीड़ित थी, तब भगवान बुद्ध द्वारा नारी सम्मान एवं अस्मिता हेतु जो कार्य किये गए वह आज भी हमारे लिए अनुकरणीय है।

बौद्ध धर्म नारी - पुरुष के भेद को नहीं मानता। उस समय नारियों के पालन-पोषण को अधिक महत्त्व दिया जाता था। उनको समाज में हेय दृष्टि से देखना उचित नहीं माना जाता था। "समाज का उत्थान पुरुषों के उत्थान के साथ नारियों के उत्थान पर अधृत था। इनकी गणना सप्त रत्नों में हुई है। वे सप्त रत्न इस प्रकार हैं- 1. चक्ररत्न, 2. अश्वरत्न, 3. हस्तिरत्न, 4. स्त्रीरत्न, 5. गृहपतिरत्न, 6. परिणायकरत्न और 7. मणिरत्न।" इन रत्नों में नारी का उल्लेख हो जाने से इसकी महत्ता और अधिक बढ़ जाती है तथा समाज में इनका स्थान ऊँचा हो जाता है। "जिस तरह पुरुष को नारी के त्याग का अधिकार था उसी तरह से पत्नी भी पति को छोड़ सकती थी।" जातक में इन उदाहरणों के आधार पर पुरुष और नारी के समान अधिकार की बात सिद्ध हो जाती है। जहाँ पुरुष समाज में प्रतिष्ठित होता था वहीं नारियाँ भी समाज में प्रतिष्ठा प्राप्त करती थीं। समाज में नारियों को पूरी स्वच्छन्दता तो नहीं थी परन्तु बौद्ध साहित्य के आधार पर हम उनकी स्वतंत्रता का दिग्दर्शन कर सकते हैं।

एक समय तथागत बुद्ध श्रावस्ती के अनाथपिण्डिक द्वारा निर्मित जेतवन में भिक्षु संघ के साथ धम्म- चर्चा कर रहे थे। उसी समय विशाखा ने भिक्षुसंघ सहित बुद्ध को भोजन के लिए आमंत्रित किया। भोजनोपरान्त विशाखा ने तथागत बुद्ध से कहा भगवान मैं आपकी अनुमति से चाहती हूँ कि आजीवन भिक्षु संघ को आठ प्रकार का दान देना चाहती हूँ। विशाखा कहती है कि धम्मसेवा से सबको पुण्य-संचय होता है। तब भगवान बुद्ध ने भिक्खुणी संघ से कहा कि दायिकाओं में विशाखा मिगारमाता अग्र है। हम देखते हैं कि तथागत बुद्ध के विचारों से प्रभावित होकर ही विशाखा इस प्रकार का महादान संघ को देती थी।

पुणिका सेठ अनाथपिण्डिक के घर को दासी की पुत्री थी। वह भी चोरी-छिपे बुद्ध का उपदेश सुनती थी। उसका कार्य यह था कि अचिरवती नदी से जल भर कर लाना। एक दिन उसने तथागत बुद्ध के उपदेश को सुना। वह उपदेश से अत्यन्त प्रभावित हुई। एक दिन प्रातःकाल शीत ऋतु में अचिरवती गंगा जल से शुद्धि मानने वाले (उदकशुद्धिक) एक ब्राह्मण से कहती है कि- "हे ब्राह्मण! यदि नदी-स्नान से पापकर्म धुल जाते हैं तो जल में रहने वाले मेढक, मछली, कछुए आदि जलचरों की सुगति तो सुनिश्चित है।" इस प्रकार धर्म के नाम पर पाखण्ड का समर्थन करने वाले को जवाब देने का साहस बुद्धोपदेश के कारण ही दासी पुत्री को प्राप्त हुआ। उसने वास्तविक विशुद्धि के मार्ग (बुद्ध धम्म) में उसे पहुँचा दिया छ इससे अनाथपिण्डिक दासी पुत्री से बड़े प्रभावित हुए। उन्हें लगा कि इसमें तो ब्राह्मण से भी ज्यादा योग्यता है। अतः अनाथपिण्डिक ने पुणिका को दासत्व से मुक्त कर दिया।

एक समय भगवान बुद्ध वैशाली के कोटिग्राम में ठहरे हुए थे। यह समाचार सुनकर आम्रपाली भगवान बुद्ध से मिलने गई और

अभिवादन कर एक ओर बैठ गई। आम्रपाली को तथागत बुद्ध ने धार्मिक उपदेश दिया। उपदेश सुनने के बाद आम्रपाली ने बुद्ध सहित भिक्षु संघ को भोजन के लिए आमंत्रित किया और अपना आम्रवन दान दिया। भगवान बुद्ध ने उसे धम्मोपदेशना देते हुए कहा कि- "सभी प्राणियों के प्रति मैत्रीभाव, दुखियों के प्रति करुणाभाव, संसार के सभी प्राणियों के प्रति समभाव रखना ही धम्म है। काय-वचन-मन से जीवन पवित्र रखना ही धम्म का कर्तव्य है।" इस धम्मोपदेश के बाद आम्रपाली के मन में सद्धर्म का अंकुर विकसित होने लगा। जीवन के अंतिम दिनों में उसने प्रव्रज्या ग्रहण की और भिक्षुणी संघ में सम्मिलित हो गई। वृद्धावस्था में जब वह अपने जीर्ण शरीर को देखती है तो उसे संसार की अनित्यता का बोध होता है। आम्रपाली ने भिक्षुणी के रूप में विपश्यना (साधना) द्वारा अपने अन्तर्मन में जीवन की अनित्यता की सच्चाई का साक्षात्कार कर लिया था। उसने कृतज्ञता विभोर होकर कहा कि महाकारुणिक तथागत बुद्ध के विचारों के कारण आज मेरे सारे दुःख दूर हो गए हैं।

तथागत भिक्षुओं के साथ अनाथपिण्डिक के घर धम्मोपदेश के लिए गए। महाश्रेष्ठी भी बुद्धोपदेश सुनने के लिए तथागत के पास बैठे थे। उसी समय सुजाता दास कर्म-करों के साथ झगड़ रही थीं। बुद्ध ने धर्म-कथा रोकर पूँछा-यह कैसा शब्द है? अनाथपिण्डिक ने बताया कि भन्ते! यह मेरी कुलवधू है गौरवरहित है सास-ससुर और स्वामी के प्रति इसका कोई कर्तव्य नहीं है दिन रात कलह करती रहती है। बुद्ध ने कहा उसे यहाँ बुलाओं। भगवान ने सुजाता को उपदेश दिया कि सुजाता! पुरुष की सात प्रकार की भार्या होती है उन सातों में तुम कौन सो हो? इस प्रकार बुद्ध ने सुजाता को पत्नियों के सात प्रकार बतलाकर अच्छी पत्नी किसे कहते और उसके क्या लाभ है यह बतलाया। उसके बाद परिवार की सुख-शान्ति के लिए उसने अच्छी पत्नी बनने का बुद्ध के सामने निश्चय किया। बुद्ध के उपदेश के प्रभाव से खुज्जुतरा का जीवन परिवर्तित हो गया। यह एक निम्न जाति नारी थी तथा वह कौशाम्बी के राजा उदयन की पटरानी की दासी थी। रानी उससे रोज आठ कार्षापण के पुष्प मंगवाती थी।

खुज्जुतरा आठ कार्षापण में से चार कार्षापण चोरी से अपने पास रख लेती थी और चार कार्षापण के ही पुष्प खरीदकर ले जाती थी। एक दिन खुज्जुतरा रानी के लिए पुष्प खरीदने जा रही थी तभी मार्ग में तथागत बुद्ध लोगों को उपदेश दे रहे थे कि- "जब व्यक्ति दुराचार को पहचान लेता है और मूल कारण विदित कर लेता है। सदाचार को पहचान लेता है और उसका भी यथार्थ कारण विदित कर लेता है तब उसकी दृष्टि सम्यक हो जाती है। इसलिए स्वयं का पर्यवेक्षण श्रेयस्कर है यही सम्यक् दृष्टि का रहस्य है।" उपदेश सुनकर वह मनन करती हुई पुष्प खरीदने चली गई और उसने जान लिया कि तुच्छ क्षणभंगुर जीवन में चोरी जैसा आचरण कर रही हूँ। मेरी स्वामिनी मुझ पर विश्वास करती है और मैं उसके साथ विश्वासघात कर रही हूँ। यह जानकर उसने निश्चय किया कि अब वह चोरी नहीं करेगी वह रानी के सामने अपना अपराध स्वीकार कर लेती है। श्यामावती रानी ने सोचा कि एक नासमझ दासी में जिनके उपदेश से इतना परिवर्तन हो गया उनका उपदेश कितना कल्याणकारी होगा। तब वह खुज्जुतरा को दासी पद से मुक्त कर राजमहिलाओं में स्थान देती है। उसका कार्य था कि बुद्ध के उपदेश सुनना और श्यामावती

तथा उसकी सखियों को सुनाना।

कुमारदेवी गया जिले के पीठी प्रदेश के सामंत देवरक्षित की पुत्री थी। उसका विवाह काशी और कन्नौज के एकमात्र अधिपति राजा मदनचन्द्र के पुत्र गोविन्द चन्द्र के साथ हुआ था। वह बुद्ध के विचारों से बहुत प्रभावित हुई और उसने सारनाथ में धम्मचक्र - जिन विहार का नौ मंजिल भवन का निर्माण करवाया जो 800 फुट लम्बा था। कुमारदेवी ने इस विहार के खर्च के लिए काशी की सबसे बड़ी तहसील जम्बुकी को अर्पित कर दिया था। धर्म शिक्षा की ओर भी उसकी बड़ी रुची थी। शिक्षा केन्द्र नालंदा और महाबोधी महाविहार, बोधगया के लिए भी उसने बहुत धन दिया था। सहस्रों भिक्षुओं ने इनके दायकत्व में धर्म शिक्षा प्राप्त की। शील पालन, विरक्त-अर्चना एवं दान पुण्य रानी कुमारदेवी का लक्ष्य था। इसी में उन्होंने अपना समस्त जीवन समर्पित कर दिया। आज भी यह स्तूप ध्वंसावशेष के रूप में धार्मिक महारानी की धर्मसेवा का यशोगान कर रहा है। बुद्ध के विचारों से प्रभावित होकर ही धर्म के प्रचार-प्रसार हेतु नारियों द्वारा किया धार्मिक योगदान प्रशंसनीय है।

“सम्राट अशोक ने अपनी प्रिय पुत्री संघमित्रा को धर्म प्रचार के लिये बोधी वृक्ष की शाखा लेकर बौद्ध धर्म के प्रचारार्थ सिंहल द्वीप (श्रीलंका) भेजा। श्रीलंका के अनुराधापुर में स्थित महेन्द्र और संघमित्रा द्वारा लगाया गया बोधीवृक्ष जो संसार का सबसे पुराना लगभग 2200 वर्ष का है जो आज भी विद्यमान है। संघमित्रा ने श्रीलंका के राजा तिष्य के आमन्त्रण पर उसकी बहन राजकुमारी अनुला और उसकी पाँच सौ सहचरियों को बौद्ध धर्म में दीक्षित किया। भिक्षुणी संघमित्रा का महापरिनिर्वाण भी श्रीलंका में हुआ। सम्राट अशोक की इन दोनों संतानों ने अपने देश से दूर विदेश में जाकर बौद्ध धर्म के लिये अपने आप को समर्पित कर दिया और बौद्ध धर्म को अन्तर्राष्ट्रीय धर्म का रूप देने में महत्वपूर्ण योगदान दिया। आज श्रीलंका बौद्ध राष्ट्र है एवं भिक्षुणियों के बड़े-बड़े संघ भी हैं इसका श्रेय संघमित्रा तथा महेन्द्र को ही जाता है।

निष्कर्ष :

इस प्रकार से हम देखते हैं नारियाँ बुद्ध के विचारों से अत्यधिक प्रभावित थीं नारी- जाति का जितना गौरव बुद्ध ने बढ़ाया उतना शायद ही दुनियाँ के किसी भी धर्म संस्थापक ने बढ़ाया होगा। जो नारी पुरुष प्रधान समाज में किसी भी अधिकार की अधिकारिणी नहीं थी उसको सभी प्रकार के अधिकारों की अधिकारिणी बनाना, ज्ञान प्राप्त करने की, ज्ञान का उपदेश देने की और निर्वाण, परमशान्ति को प्राप्त करने की अधिकारिणी घोषित करना एक क्रान्तिकारी कदम था। डॉ. सुरेन्द्रनाथ दुबे ने स्पष्ट रूप से उल्लेख किया है कि - “बौद्ध परम्परा में स्त्री को हीन नहीं माना गया। इतना ही नहीं, पुत्र और पुत्री की कामना समान रूप से की जाती थी। 17 नारियों के प्रति बुद्ध के समतावादी दृष्टिकोण ना उनकी स्थिति में महत्वपूर्ण सुधार किया।” इंग्लैंड की अनुसंधानकृति होर्नर ष्वेउमद न्दकमत च्त्तपउपजपअम ठनककीपेउष्णामक पुस्तक (शोधग्रंथ) में लिखा है कि-“बौद्ध काल में नारियों की सामाजिक स्थिति में काफी सुधार हुआ। नारियाँ अधिक समानता का उपभोग ले सकीं। अधिक आदर और अधिकार जो अब तक कभी भी नारियों को नहीं मिला था वे उन्हें प्राप्त हुए। 18 बौद्धकाल में नारियों का विकास हुआ था। उन्हें पुरुषों के समान ही अधिकार प्राप्त थे। बौद्धकाल नारियों की उन्नति का काल था। जीवन यापन करते हुए भी उन्होंने एक ओर बुद्ध की शिक्षाओं को जन-जन तक पहुँचाने में तथा धर्म सेवा में अपनी सम्पूर्ण सम्पत्ति और समस्त जीवन लगा दिया। वहीं दूसरी ओर अपनी दासियों से मानवता पूर्व व्यवहार किया और कुछ नारियों ने तो उन्हें दासत्व से मुक्त कर दिया। बुद्ध के विचारों से प्रभावित होकर ही नारियों ने भिक्षुणी संघ में प्रवेश कर अध्ययन, अध्यापन और ज्ञानार्जन किया जिसका परिणाम थैरीगाथा ग्रन्थ का निर्माण है, जिसे नारियों की स्वतंत्रता की अभिव्यक्ति को प्रकट करने वाला प्रथम अनुपम ग्रन्थ भी कहा जाता है।

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Teerthanker Journal of Law & Governance

ISSN 2359-8565

9 772359 856904

Price : ₹350 /-

Printed For Teerthanker College of Law and Legal Studies, TMU, Moradabad, U.P.
Printed by Zenwaar Imprints, Moradabad, U.P.

#Zenwaar Imprints. 9027256993